

Chapter 3. How transformative change occurs

Supplementary Material

Contents

Annex 3.1. Additional in-depth case studies of transformative change	1
Annex 3.2. Grouping theories into six approaches.....	15
Annex 3.3. Summaries of the theories, frameworks and fields of study assessed	16

Annex 3.1. Additional in-depth case studies of transformative change

Case 1. The transformative impacts of railroads – an example of the multiple, cascading dimensions of large-scale transformative change

The construction of railroads is of a deliberate pursuit that had rapid transformative impacts on societies' economies, trade, demography, social relations and ecosystems as they swiftly spread across the world in a few decades in the mid-19th century (Hobsbawm, 1995). In the words of historian Eric Hobsbawm (Hobsbawm, 1987): "They were part of the most dramatic innovation of the century, undreamed of ... a century earlier." Railroads played a crucial role in propelling trade and mobility of goods and people, which was essential in the integration of industrial economies.

The construction of railroads not only transform societies; it also altered ecosystems. Forests and vegetation were cleared to create space for railway tracks, often cutting through natural habitats, leading to fragmentation and isolation of plant and animal populations. The tracks supplied corridors where invasive alien species could spread, such as the spread of cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*) along railroad tracks in the western United States, which has displaced native grasses and increased fire risk (Austen, 2015; Knapp & Rice, 1996).

Transformation led by the widespread construction of railroads has clear connections to the science and technology cluster of theories, but it is also closely related to structural theories. The construction and spread of railroads inferred profound structural changes that "collectively constitute the most massive effort of public building as yet undertaken by man" (Hobsbawm, 1987). While the economic effects on societies have been debated in economic historiography, the concentration of infrastructure, economic opportunities and resources along specific routes created new nodes in societies while marginalizing others (Tsey & Short, 1995). For example, the urbanization that followed railroad development led to fundamental social and cultural changes. Railroads strengthened the colonial powers' means of control by facilitating the movement of goods, settlers, labourers, colonial administrators and military units (Osterhammel, 2014; Tsey & Short, 1995). By connecting different regions, the railroads provided efficient transport of minerals, agricultural products and other valuable resources from the interior regions to coastal areas for export, thus contributing to the economic integration of the broader colonial system.

The introduction of railways also entailed inner transformations, by for example, altering perceptions of time, space and the experience of landscapes (Schivelbusch, 2014). Timekeeping, which previously often was local and based on the position of the sun, became more standardised for an efficient scheduling of train departures and arrivals. This led to the creation of time zones, which divided the world into distinct regions with the same standardised time. Long-distance travelling time was radically reduced, which gave a sense of a smaller and more interconnected world (Osterhammel, 2014; Zerubavel, 1982). Ideas and knowledge proliferated more easily as people, books and newspapers could be more rapidly transported across long distances. The railroad infrastructure was, for example, ideal for laying telegraph lines alongside the tracks, connecting distant locations, which enabled near-instantaneous long-distance communication, revolutionising business communication and news dissemination (Hobsbawm, 1995).

Case 2. Abolition of slavery

The abolition of slavery, primarily in the British Empire, has also been used in the literature as an analogy for today's sustainability transformations (Azar, 2007; Chapin et al., 2022; Hochschild, 2005; Linnér & Wibeck, 2019). The plantation economy that followed European colonisation transformed the Americas through the transatlantic slave trade, promoting monocultures that undermined biodiversity, extractivism¹ and the subsequent exploitation of natural resources, racialised discrimination and the grabbing of lands and livelihoods from local people (Carney, 2021; Mehta, 2022; Tsing, 2012). The abolition movement challenged a practice long seen as essential to the world economy: "the thought that anyone might ever want to ban this lucrative business was inconceivable" (Hochschild, 2005). This quote illustrates that the dominant narratives at the time did not even consider that enslaved individuals would conceive of a world without slavery. The notion of the Plantationocene (Haraway, 2015) captures how plantations represented a "transformational movement in human and natural history" (Carney, 2021). The plantation encompassed the "large-scale cultivation of an exotic crop produced by enslaved labour" (Tsing, 2012) and monocultures that undermine biodiversity. Plantations in the Americas resulted in the transatlantic slave trade and massive wealth generation for a few and grave injustices for most. Even though plantations laid the foundation for unsustainable agricultural processes that resulted in carbon-consuming and emitting food systems¹, biodiversity loss and nature's decline, emerging research is revealing how they also contained alternative food systems on smallholder farms that enabled subsistence farming, drew on Indigenous knowledge of the enslaved and promoted agrobiodiversity with plants from two continents in dense spaces and so called marginal lands, deemed 'unproductive' for commodity crops (Carney, 2021).

The abolition of slavery took place for a host of reasons, including economic, but also mostly due to moral imperatives. The formal abolition of slavery in the British Empire illustrates that the priorities and values of the general public can change within a relatively short period and that radical transformation takes place not just through structural change (e.g., macro political or economic processes or war, as theories in the structural change cluster would have it) but also through changes in discourses, ethics¹ and inner transformation. It is important to note that the abolition of slavery was not without contestation, nor has the vision of abolition been fully realized, given the civil war in the United States and enduring structural racism across the Americas.

Most historical research points to multiple drivers of the abolition, which can illustrate the role of the ideas promoted by all six clusters of theories of transformation presented in this chapter. Abolition involved enhanced knowledge as increased information via newspapers, books and public meetings were vital to inform public opinion. The knowledge of the Enlightenment further underpinned the changing views on humankind and human rights. Abolition can also be understood from a systems approach, e.g., emphasizing the interconnectedness between the Enlightenment, industrialization, geopolitical rivalry, new modes of production, market-based economy and changing ethics. Inner transformations perspectives point to the role of religious groups' moral stance and the changing world views following the Enlightenment. The empowerment of a new middle class in the industrial economy, which made their fortune outside the plantation and slave shipping economy, through a parliamentary reform that made the abolition decisions politically possible. Structural factors also involved the several slave revolts in the Caribbean and the compensation of plantation owners, who received £20 million in

¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

government bonds, approximately 40 percent of the British national budget at the time. All of these aspects interacted to make possible that slavery could go from a lucrative, unquestioned, back bone of the economy to being abolished.

While official, State-sponsored slavery has been abolished, it is important to note that many modern forms of slavery continue. Today plantations are expanding across Asia and Latin America and modern slavery persists in the seafood industry (Tickler et al., 2018). These dynamics continue to threaten biodiversity and the lives and livelihoods of small farmers, as well as ocean health. Grave conditions remain and ending modern slavery is included in SDG target 8.7. Growing research is documenting links between modern slavery, biodiversity loss and nature's decline and climate change (Brickell et al., 2018), which highlights the incomplete and continual nature of transformative change.

Case 3. Udege People

The Udege People are an Indigenous tribe in the Far East of Russia who have lived in isolation in the Bikin River Valley for centuries. In recent years, the Udege People have faced increasing pressure from outside forces, which has led to near-constant conflicts since 1990, when the Udege protested against poaching, illegal logging, overfishing and the threats of outside businesses that wanted to extract resources from their lands.

In 2011, the Udege People appealed to the President of the Russian Federation and the governor, proposing to create a federal traditional nature management territory. This proposal was realized in 2015 with the creation of Bikin National Park, which aims to protect the key habitats of the iconic Amur tiger. The creation of the park was a compromise between environmental interests and the interests of local residents. The most important requirement put forward by local residents was participation of the Udege people in the management of the park through the Council of the Indigenous Peoples. Local residents succeeded in gaining significant guarantees based on co-management principles and more than 70 percent of the area is now reserved for the Indigenous Peoples' exclusive use to pursue their traditional subsistence activities. In 2018, the park was given World Heritage Status by the United Nations Education, Science and Culture Organization's World Heritage Committee.

This example illustrates how empowerment can lead to transformative change through bottom-up drivers that contest existing power relations and structures. After the creation of the park, the Udege People felt empowered to maintain their traditional subsistence activities and the park's governance. This example can also be understood from the perspective of knowledge co-creation theories, as Indigenous Peoples co-produced, co-designed and co-implemented initiatives and policies with non-governmental organizations, State agencies and academics, which led to their empowerment. A systems approach can also help to understand the importance of Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' cultural values and management practices (park co-governance) as drivers of social-ecological transformations. Finally, in order to guarantee the Udege People's interests and rights, structural transformations related to legal changes were needed.

A related example is the creation of Canada's first "Tribal Park" on Meares Island in a bid to stop logging plans of its old-growth forests. On April 21, 1984, the Tla-o-qui-aht and Ahousaht First Nations bands declared this island to be a conservation area. The effort began as an attempt to block logging by MacMillan Bloedel, a forestry company, via a stated need to settle Indigenous land claims. The Tla-o-qui-aht Tribal Parks are now recognized as a model in the global

conservation arena through the Indigenous Peoples' and Community Conserved Territories and Areas consortium (ICCA Consortium, 2023).

Case 4. The Lake Tana Watershed

Lake Tana is located in Ethiopia, approximately 1786 m above sea level. At 3,000 square kilometres, Africa's highest lake plays an important role in the region's biodiversity. The grand opening of the Lake Tana Biosphere Reserve in December 2015 marked a milestone. The nearly 700,000-hectare reserve was officially included in the world network of biosphere reserves with non-use core areas covering almost four percent (24,157 hectares; Kalmbach, 2017). Lake Tana and its surroundings are not only ecologically significant, but also culturally important, as the region is home to historical sites, monasteries and communities that are closely linked to Ethiopian history and culture. The Lake Tana watershed in Ethiopia, with its 15,000 km², plays a crucial role in the ecological balance of the region (Aynalem et al., 2013).

Lake Tana and its wetlands face significant ecological challenges due to ongoing encroachment on the sensitive habitat. Deforestation and agriculture have led to forest loss and erosion, threatening numerous animal and plant species. Unregulated fishing, intensive agriculture (including the use of pesticides) and infrastructural developments threaten water quality and endanger the livelihoods of millions of people (Gebremedhin et al., 2018). In addition to smallholder farming, the region is considered one of five national economic growth corridors (NABU, 2013). Irrigation and infrastructure development, hydroelectric power plants and acreage for export are leading to agricultural intensification, population influx and deterioration in water quality (Alemu et al., 2020; NABU, n.d.).

Efforts to develop a systemic and co-creative transformation approach for Lake Tana began in 2010, when The Nature and Biodiversity Conservation Union worked together with the Ethiopian Government towards the acknowledgement of the area as a UNESCO Biosphere reserve. An initial feasibility study included important stakeholders in the planning for protecting the unique ecosystems and creating sustainable sources of income for the local population. The case also involved empowering local communities. Over 1,500 people from 75 communities were trained to participate in the zoning of the protected area. An administrative unit within the local government was established. Management and ecotourism plans were developed, focusing on a combination of nature conservation, sustainable development and education (Karlberg et al., 2015). The approach included the restoration of wetlands and forests together with the local population, the conversion of agriculture to organic methods and regional product development such as herbal teas and oils. The interventions were guided by a system-thinking logic where large-scale changes encourage societies to interact differently with their natural environments.

The creation of the biosphere reserve was embedded in the co-creation practice of a regional multi-stakeholder partnership that continued into 2023 to ensure long-term sustainable water supply and quality for all users (NABU, 2020). It included actors from government, civil society, business and academia and developed co-designed strategies to preserve and restore the physical and biological integrity of the watershed. The local Nature and Biodiversity Conservation Union facilitated the communication, learning and collective implementation processes of the partnership. Governance structures within the partnership ensured participatory decision-making and cooperation between government institutions, the private sector, civil society organizations

and educational institutions. Partners developed thematic packages of measures, which regularly reported on their results at board meetings and annual stakeholder conferences.

The Lake Tana transformation approach is an impressive example of the impact of a complex, yet well-structured collaborative transformation effort engaging all stakeholders. The success hinged on a systemic approach based on joined strategy development, collaboration in implementation, fostering innovative approaches, keeping all actors in dialogue, showcasing and measuring impact and ensuring value of project results for all. The challenges of the Lake Tana watershed were not viewed in isolation but were addressed as part of a complex system. Recognition as a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve was not only an honour but seen also a commitment to protect future generations.

Case 5. Population Growth

The quadrupling of world population over the past century, associated with a 16-time increase in fossil fuel use, 35-time increase in fisheries output and a 9-time increase in water use, has contributed to a dramatic and unwanted transformation of the biosphere. Dramatically slowing rates of population growth could also have transformative impacts on society, as fewer people of productive age will support an aging population (Naso et al., 2020). The world population growth rate has fallen from 2.1 percent per year in the late 1960s to below one percent in 2020 and is expected to continue to fall to negative numbers at the end of the century (Population Division of the Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2001).

The rich literature on the drivers of the population transition is not in full agreement on the drivers of this change and reveals some important cultural variations. Nevertheless, the key drivers appear to be in line with structural approaches, such as improved income, human security, female education and to some extent coercive policies like the People's Republic of China's now abandoned one-child policy and empowerment approaches primarily human security, maternal and child health, education, gender equality and access to contraceptives.

Figure SM 3.1. World population growth 1700–2100. World population in billion and annual global growth rate (Linnér, 2023).

Case 6. European Green Deal

The European Green Deal is an example of an ongoing effort to achieve transformative change to reach climate neutrality, biodiversity, healthy soils and food, clean air and water, fresh air, clean water, sustainable fisheries and blue economy, competitive industrial advantage and future job markets, among others (European Commission, 2019). As such it is an example of deliberate attempt to achieve a society-wide transformation. The European Union Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 is one of the strategic documents that have been adopted as part of the European Green Deal Strategic Framework.

It is mainly a structural approach, with connections to Keynesian approaches to the environment. For instance, it aims to mitigate climate change by effective carbon pricing. For the European Commission, the European Green Deal is “... Europe’s structural response and new growth strategy that sets out ambitions to transform the European Union into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy” (European Commission, 2019). To do this, the Commission proposes a wide set of evolving governance mechanisms, including legislative measures, market mechanisms, influencing citizen behavioural change and technological and infrastructural measures.

The components of the European Green Deal package also incorporate knowledge-based approaches. For instance, the European Green Deal aims at energy transition by promoting energy-efficiency and renewable technologies (Almeida et al., 2023). Education and training are also needed for the new green jobs and secure just transitions (European Commission, 2019; **box 3.3** on just transitions).

While the European Green Deal recognizes the need to ensure a just transition globally, it has also been criticised for reproducing colonial injustices by leveraging the green transition to

ensure economic growth (Almeida et al., 2023). As such, the example illustrates the fundamental challenges to achieve societal transformations that ensures sustainability globally.

Case 7. Montreal Protocol

In 1985, scientists identified a hole in or severe thinning of the ozone layer over Antarctica (Farman et al., 1985) which was caused by ozone-depleting substances called chlorofluorocarbons. Chlorofluorocarbons were used widely as refrigerants, in aerosol sprays and other consumer products. Ozone depletion has negative impacts for human and ecological health (e.g., marine ecosystems, plants). In response to evidence about the ozone hole, governments universally ratified the Montreal Protocol in 1987; the initial agreement phased out the use of chlorofluorocarbons and halons. Additional amendments in 1990, 1992 and 1997 phased out other chemicals and accelerated the phase-out process. The Montreal Protocol is considered to-date the only successful international environmental agreement. Addressing the use of these chemicals led to reductions in temperature and reduced cases of skin cancer (UNEP, 2020). The policy intervention efficiently addressed a simple, yet global problem raised by scientists to policymakers, in part because a technical solution was available - substitutes for chlorofluorocarbons, including hydrofluorocarbons. The ozone hole is on track to heal by 2060 (Knox, 2018). However, the case may not be directly transferable to other environmental problems like climate change, given the relatively simple nature of the problem and availability of a technical solution that did not impose an economic burden.

Case 8. Energy transitions

The literature includes a large set of examples on energy transitions. For instance, historically, rising oil prices led to a strong transformation in many countries (Acar & Lindmark, 2017). Preceding the oil crises of 1973 and 1979, oil had transformed the economies and energy systems in the western countries after World War II. Cheap oil flowed into Western Europe after 1948 and it was also a commodity that was included in the Marshall plan. In short, oil was an integrated part of the technologies, industrial and geographical structures that emerged around the internal combustion engine. As such it was an important determinant for several structural changes during the period. Furthermore, oil did not only substitute for other energy carriers, such as coal, but was also added on top of the existing energy systems, allowing an overall increase of the energy use. Not the least, heavier oils were used in thermo-electrical power plants and for domestic heating. This confluence of factors had by the 1970s made several Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development countries dependent on oil as a strategic energy commodity over which considerable market power could be exercised.

Increasing energy prices means that the conversion efficiency of energy into an economic service flow may be improved, if the service flow is to remain constant. This is why the oil crises of 1973 and 1979 constituted a powerful transformation pressure and incentive for technological change in the western economies. In the aftermath of these crises, it became an important political objective to decouple oil from economic growth. This 'oil dependency' made the western world vulnerable to embargos. Acar and Lindmark (2017) show that the decoupling was indeed successful, which was compatible with period specific occurrences, such as the introduction of an active climate policy with the European Union Emissions Trading System as a system. Moreover, the coal industry underwent substantial structural changes in the 1970s and the 1980s, with the

coal miners' strike in the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland in the early 1980s as an example.

In the extant literature, energy transition implies the transformation of the modes of energy production and consumption, which mainly targets the mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions by limiting or reducing consumption of fossil fuels (Swartenbroekx, 2018). It entails the deployment of renewable energy, which met around 13% of global final energy demand in 2020 (REN21, 2022). Yet, as the energy transition is land-based (e.g., wind farms can be based onshore or offshore, space is needed in order to install solar panels, or water dams affect landscape around, etc.), there are also large controversies on the impacts of these transitions given current power structures and possible external costs on the environment and society (despite being negligible when compared to the externalities from fossil fuel use). For instance, the transition to biofuels that took place particularly in the tropical countries has triggered fear about an unstoppable process of “destroying rainforests, wrecking ecosystems, leaching the soil, creating fertiliser and pesticide runoff s that will poison the oceans” (Mathews, 2008). Besides, the transition needs to be accelerated and reflected in dedicated and coherent policies and regulations under the urgency of climate change mitigation, which is vital for biodiversity and the protection and restoration of ecosystem services.

Recently, the literature focuses increasingly on just energy transformations towards decarbonisation of regions where there has been a historical dependence on fossil fuel industry parts. These examples suggest that a successfully managed coal mining transition can take up to 25 years to ensure new jobs for the workforce, regional economic restructuring and new investment in business alternatives (*Home | Coal Transitions*, n.d.). They also indicate the need for a sense of security in times of structural, legitimate dialogue processes, proactive social movement discourse, national or regional transition bodies, providing funding for diversifying of current industries, job retraining programmes, regional infrastructure investments and “soft attractiveness factors” (e.g., beautification, education investments or enhanced internet access (Crowe & Li, 2020; Herdic, 2019; Newell & Simms, 2020; Olson-Hazboun, 2018; Snyder, 2018).

Case 9. Seeds of change in Indonesia

Illegal logging in tropical rainforest in Indonesian Borneo, combined with poor quality of life for local people is a major issue in this region. By listening carefully (called ‘radical listening’) to the needs of local people, the founder of Health in Harmony learned that much illegal logging was happening because people needed money for health care. She devised a solution that involved providing free or low-cost health care to communities that agreed to work together to stop illegal logging. Health care came from volunteer North American doctors, who eventually trained local doctors in Borneo. She started to work in Gunung Palung National Park, reconnecting rainforest ‘health’ to human health and has now expanded to other areas. The outcome is that 52,000 ha of rainforest have been regenerated, that there has been a 90% decline in illegal logging households, that 120,000 people are now able to access health care, that infant mortality declined by 67% and that the births per mother declined by 54% (Health In Harmony, n.d.; Jones et al., 2020).

Case 10. Transformation in the coastal city of Mumbai

In urban Mumbai, coastal ecosystems and wetlands (e.g., mangrove forests and biodiversity creeks) have been systematically appropriated by the State and private actors for commercial and infrastructure development purposes. Combined with flooding, sea-level rise and coastal erosion, this has created severe risks for coastal regions and their populations, especially the Koli fishers, the native fishing community in Mumbai. To address these issues, an innovative fishing net installation was co-created in synergy with the Koli community and the think tank Bombay 61, which has traditionally served as the first line of defence for the coastal ecosystem of the city. This initiative has collected around 500 kg of waste from a single outlet in Malad creek in three days. This not only helps clean the creek and local mangroves but will also revive local fishing livelihoods around the creek for the artisanal fishers (Nair, 2022; Ulman et al., 2008).

Case 11. Costa Rica

Costa Rica is an ongoing case of transformative change towards increased biodiversity and forest recovery. This Central American country was able to reverse its forest loss in only two decades, create a system of national parks and protected areas, develop laws to protect its rivers from damaging exploitation and forbid wildlife trade as a commercial activity as a way of protecting biodiversity from aggressive exploitation. These achievements produced positive changes and economic gains in rural areas, such as the generation of economic revenues from ecotourism and an uncommon labour influx from urban to rural (Andam et al., 2010; Robalino & Villalobos, 2015). The process of transformative change is far from complete. Costa Rica has transformed its rural areas in detriment of its urban ones, where most of its environmental weaknesses rely (Alpízar et al., 2018). Indigenous issues also remain a challenge.

Costa Rica's environmental progressiveness started early on with the Law of Waters No. 276, written in 1942. The first national Law of Waters, written in 1884, granted public and private domain of water and riverbeds, depending on certain conditions. However, the second Law of Waters, No. 276, turned water into a public affair with very few instances of private domain. In terms of the governance, this second law created the Water Department as the regulating body for the natural resource. Updates to this law have taken place in 1996, 2009 and 2012.

Later, in 1969, the first Forest Law No. 4465 was signed. This law enabled the creation of the Department of National Parks, key for the establishment of a system of national parks, biological corridors, forest reserves, protective zones and wildlife refuges. Almost three decades afterwards, in 1996, the Law No. 4465 was reverted and a new Forest Law, No. 7575, was published. By that time, Costa Rica had to deal with a trepid deforestation rate, as forests went from covering 75% of the national territory in the 1940s to only 21% by the late 1980s. Through this new law, Costa Rica pioneered a Payment for Ecosystem Services scheme, which turned out to become a worldwide renowned example of how to tackle deforestation. Transformative change becomes visible as protected areas currently cover one quarter of the national territory. Furthermore, forest loss was reverted and the national forest cover was more than duplicated in only two decades.

Before the turn of the century, the Biodiversity Law No. 7788, published in 1998, awarded the State the complete and exclusive sovereignty over the elements of biodiversity. This law sought for biodiversity conservation, the sustainable use of natural resources and a fair distribution of the societal costs and benefits. It also encouraged environmental education and local participation

from peasants, Indigenous Peoples, the private sector and the scientific and environmental communities.

Costa Rica was not isolated from international interests and social movements and the 1970s were crucial for the country's environmentalism growth and green transformation. This decade saw the rise of social movements claiming for a better environment, which only became stronger in the 1980s. The return of investments in education made since the 1940s, when the army was abolished and its budget was redirected to education, became increasingly evident in the 1970s. Biologists and ecologists trained abroad returned to Costa Rica, bringing international environmental ideas and adapting them to the local context. Well-renowned international scientific organizations made Costa Rica their homebase. The Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (1942), the Tropical Science Center (1962), the Tropical Agricultural Research and Higher Education Center (1973) and the no-longer existing National Institute of Biodiversity (1989) are just a few of these organizations.

Costa Rica's lands became increasingly protected, a national and international tourism that valued nature started to increase. The country became a worldwide known place for ecotourism. This economic practice allowed a resurgence of rural areas and led to an uncommon labour influx from urban to rural zones.

Costa Rica's transformative change of biodiversity and forest recovery certainly did not happen in a vacuum but resulted from a synergy of events and actions. A mix of factors have led to this transformation. Structural changes in terms of laws and bylaws played a crucial role. Not only did the country create a Water Law, Forest Law and a Biodiversity Law, but in 1994 it also amended article 50 of the Political Constitution to incorporate the right to enjoy a healthy and ecologically balanced environment into constitutional rights. Moreover, a systemic vision of the environment, where protected areas speak to conservation, biodiversity and the economic activity of tourism allowed nature and citizens to make the most of the transformation. The knowledge of scientists and international organizations was essential to bring and adapt international environmental ideas to the local context.

Even though the country has achieved an outstanding green transformation, it is important to underline that a long road awaits in its brown and blue agendas. The contamination of surface and underground waters due to poor sewage water management and the pollution caused by poor waste management and a carbon-intensive transportation sector inhibits Costa Rica from becoming an overall environmental and climate champion. Transformative change is still pending in those realms.

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Annex 3.2. Grouping theories into six approaches

Based on the theories, frameworks and areas of study assessed in this chapter (**annex 3.3**), six clusters of theories and frameworks of transformative change were identified: 1) Science and technology; 2) Knowledge co-creation approaches; 3) systems approaches; 4) inner transformations; 5) empowerment approaches; and 6) structural approaches. Each cluster is based on grouping those theories and frameworks that share a similar rationale and approach for understanding or navigating transformative change. At the same time, clusters comprise a wide spectrum; therefore, there is also diversity within clusters.

A set of five clusters was initially developed based on the theories identified. This first categorization was made based on how theories and frameworks address the core 12 sets of questions which experts filled out (including but not limited to how transformative change occurs according to each theory and framework; their main assumptions; how they address norms, values; direct and indirect drivers of change, power and agency). Secondly, a condensed set of questions from the original 12 sets was prepared to circulate to all the transformative change assessment authors to gather and analyze additional theories and frameworks. This was followed by an assessment of whether the initial clusters were accurate/valid, or changes were needed. The condensed set of questions also informed how contributing authors would prepare their contributions for the theoretical frameworks from the expert survey². Finally, the systematic literature review on the main references from 62 theoretical frameworks on how transformative change occurs (see annex 3) contributed to the classification of approaches of transformative change and highlighted possible knowledge gaps in the review³.

An analysis of the various theories and frameworks of transformative change transformation revealed a number of elements that are important for transformation. A matrix of these elements was built to compare the clusters with one another. The key steps to do this analysis were 1) to understand and finalize the list of priority elements, 2) confirm the questions posed to each configuration of element and question, 3) complete the table, building on the analysis of the individual clusters. This involves deciding about the strength of the relationship between the cluster and the element, in order to answer the relevant question for each element.

Finally, the six clusters were mapped onto the three dimensions of change identified in chapter 1, based on the focus of the approach, its main actions and interventions and underlying theory of change.

² Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change (<https://10.5281/zenodo.10250533>)

³ Systematic review of literature on transformative change for sustainability (<https://10.5281/zenodo.10218647>)

Annex 3.3. Summaries of the theories, frameworks and fields of study assessed

This annex presents a detailed overview of 62 theoretical frameworks assessed in chapter 3. Each theoretical framework includes a description and an analysis of how it conceptualizes transformative change. The theories are classified according to their association with one of six approaches outlined in chapter 3.

Most theories address multiple approaches but are grouped by their primary focus on transformative change towards sustainability. Descriptions were developed in collaboration with global experts listed as contributing authors in chapter 3. Each theory was assessed and coded for primary and secondary approaches. The coding process involved two reviewers, with a third reviewer resolving discrepancies when necessary. Importantly, the coding is based solely on the content presented in this appendix and the approaches outlined in Chapter 3 do not reflect any opinions from contributing authors and exclude any external literature (see data management report 3.1⁴ for more details on the methodology).

Theories are listed as follow:

1. Systems approaches

- Human agency
- Agroecological transformations
- Phases of deliberate social-ecological transformations
- Panarchy theory
- Catalyzing transformation
- Seeds of the good anthropocene
- Collective action in social-ecological systems
- Integrative framework for transformative social change
- Sustainability transitions
- Social movements theories
- Transition governance
- Leverage points for sustainability transformation
- Transformation flower approach
- Metatheories of human action
- Redesigning theories of change
- Value-centred leverage points to catalyze transformative change
- Regenerative approaches

2. Structural approaches

- Karl Polanyi's "The Great Transformation"

⁴ Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change (<https://10.5281/zenodo.10250533>)

- Marxist theory
- Rational choice theory
- Institutional analysis
- Ecological civilization framework
- Governmentality
- Degrowth and post-growth studies
- Strengthening accountability frameworks
- Biodiversity policy integration
- Transition management
- Behavioural economics
- International political economy
- Transformative governance
- Environmental State and the green State
- Structuration theory
- Social Practice theory
- Actor Network theory

3. Inner Transformation

- Inner transformation
- Pathways to nature connectedness
- Relationality
- Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures
- SHIFT
- Transformative learning for socio-ecological sustainability
- Relational values and relationality

4. Empowerment

- Political ecology
- Transformative spaces
- Three spheres of transformation
- Praxis
- Environmental history: Environmentalism of the poors and environmental coloniality
- Fractal agency
- Everyday resistance
- Feminist political ecology
- Decolonial feminisms and ecofeminism

5. Knowledge co-creation

- Three horizons
- Ethnoecology
- Sustainability science
- Participatory research
- Transformative education
- Local Biodiversity Outlook (LBO) transitions
- Transdisciplinary research
- Transformative innovation policy

6. Science & Technology

- Epistemic communities
- Inclusive innovation
- Science and technology, systems
- Technological and scientific constructivism

Description of theories:

1. Systems approaches

Table SM.3.1. Human agency	19
Table SM.3.2. Agroecological transformations	20
Table SM.3.3. Phases of deliberate social-ecological transformations	21
Table SM.3.4. Panarchy theory.....	23
Table SM.3.5. Catalysing transformation.....	24
Table SM.3.6. Seeds of good anthropocenes	26
Table SM.3.7. Collective action in social-ecological systems.....	27
Table SM.3.8. Integrative framework for transformative social change.....	28
Table SM.3.9. Sustainability transitions	30
Table SM.3.10. Social movement theory	31
Table SM.3.11. Transition governance.....	33
Table SM.3.12. Leverage points for sustainability transformation	34
Table SM.3.13. Transformation flower approach.....	36
Table SM.3.14. Metatheories of human action	37
Table SM.3.15. Redesigning theories of change	38

Table SM.3.16. Value-centred leverage points to catalyse transformative change.....40
Table SM.3.17. Regenerative approaches41

Table SM.3.1. Human agency

3.1. Human agency	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Empowerment
<p>Human agency is a critically important factor for ensuring that sustainability transformation in any given social-ecological system places social justice and equity at the centre alongside meeting environmental goals. The term human agency is multi-faceted. It involves an individual’s capacity to freely make choices (K. Brown & Westaway, 2011), the capacity to define one’s goals and act on them (Kabeer, 1999) and the capacity to play an independent causal role in history (McLaughlin & Dietz, 2008). The exercise of human agency goes beyond observable action and includes the less visible aspects of the meanings, motivations and purposes that animate people’s activities (Kabeer, 1999; Manlosa, 2022). While much of literature views agency as a matter of decision-making, Kabeer (1999) considers a more nuanced view to include bargaining, negotiation, non-action as resistance and invisible cognitive processes of reflection and analysis as exercises of agency. While agency is primarily an individual’s capacity, it can also be possessed by groups history (McLaughlin & Dietz, 2008) in collective action. The concept of human agency contributes to transformative change research. One of the earlier research strands linking human agency and transformative change was done by feminist scholars theorizing the processes through which human agency contributes to gender transformative change towards more equal gender and power relations (Kantor, 2013). The discourse on sustainability transformation is much broader but some of the linkages are similar. For instance, the setting of goals to guide the direction of sustainability transformation includes the exercise of human agency. Questions of whose goals, raises issues around which groups have the opportunity to play causal roles in transformation processes in their own places. Complex decision-making and the power of participatory processes to amplify the voices of marginalized groups similarly involves the analysis and exercise of human agency of diverse social groups. Thus, human agency is foundational to the sustainability transformation discourse.</p>	
<p>Key references: Alkire, S. 2007. Measuring agency: issues and possibilities. <i>Indian Journal of Human Development</i> 1(1):169-175. https://doi.org/10.1177/0973703020070110 Brown, K. and E. Westaway. 2011. Agency, capacity and resilience to environmental change: lessons from human development, well-being and disasters. <i>Annual Review of Environment and Resources</i> 36(1):321-342. https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-052610-092905 Kabeer, N. 1999. Resources, agency, achievements: reflections on the measurement of women’s empowerment. <i>Development and Change</i> 30(3):435-464. https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-7660.00125 Manlosa, A. O. (2022). Operationalising agency in livelihoods research: smallholder farming livelihoods in southwest Ethiopia. <i>Ecology and Society</i>, 27(1). McLaughlin, P. and T. Dietz. 2008. Structure, agency and environment: toward an integrated perspective on vulnerability. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> 18:99-111. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2007.05.003</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Deliberate transformative change occurs in social-ecological systems of different scales when a new system emerges from the old one. This goes beyond surface-level changes. Transformative change occurs through different mechanisms including, among others, 1) an intentional change of system goals in order to put the system in a new trajectory, 2) a change in the structure of a system and 3) an alteration of the feedbacks between system components, such that a new social-ecological regime emerges. Human agency plays a role in these three different mechanisms. First, the setting of new goals is an exercise of agency. Ensuring that goal-setting is not narrowly captured by privileged, powerful voices but broadly reflects diverse voices in a way that is just and equitable implies that different social groups are supported and given opportunities to exercise agency in shaping the course of transformation in specific places. Second, changing the structure of a system, for instance by changing institutions and social structures to serve sustainability goals necessitate human</p>	

actors to engage in decision-making, goal setting and deliberate visible and invisible processes that involve the exercise of human agency. Third, complex social-ecological transformation processes involve both agentic and non-agentic aspects. This means that part of the series of changes leading to transformation are random, involve non-intentional drivers, feedback and effects. But deliberate transformative change occurs because actors can learn and shape responses and feedbacks between system components.

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Charli-Joseph, L., Siqueiros-García, J. M., Eakin, H., Manuel-Navarrete, D., Mazari-Hiriart, M., Shelton, R., ... & Ruizpalacios, B. (2023). Enabling collective agency for sustainability transformations through reframing in the Xochimilco social–ecological system. *Sustainability Science*, 18(3), 1215-1233.

Moore, M. L., & Milkoreit, M. (2020). Imagination and transformations to sustainable and just futures. *Elem Sci Anth*, 8(1), 081.

Westley, F., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Homer-Dixon, T., Vredenburg, H., Loorbach, D., ... & Van Der Leeuw, S. (2011). Tipping toward sustainability: emerging pathways of transformation. *Ambio*, 40, 762-780.

Westley, F. R., Tjornbo, O., Schultz, L., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Crona, B., & Bodin, Ö. (2013). A theory of transformative agency in linked social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 18(3).

Table SM.3.2. Agroecological transformations

<p>3.2. Agroecological transformations</p>	<p>Main approach: Systems</p> <p>Secondary approach: Science & Technology, Knowledge co-creation</p>
<p>Conventional agriculture has been a major driver of environmental degradation, with the expansion of the agricultural frontier displacing natural areas and intensifying land use (Tscharntke et al., 2005). This has led to increased deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions and global biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, which in turn have reduced the natural capital of agroecosystems and their capacity to provide ecosystem services (Tilman et al., 2002). However, these environments have the potential to contribute to multiple dimensions of human well-being and proper management can resolve trade-offs between production, food security and people’s quality of life. Building natural capital over the long term, such as fertile soils and more positive biotic interactions, is crucial for sustainable food systems (Tittonell, 2020).</p> <p>Agroecological transformation is an interactive horizontal change that promotes shared learning and creative solutions. It aims to comprehensively transform agroecosystems to function based on ecological processes driven by diversification strategies inside and outside the fields (Altieri, 2018). Both a multidisciplinary science and a social movement (Wezel et al., 2009), agroecology⁵ can be implemented in systems of any scale because it is highly context-dependent and its principles adapt to each case. It comprises practices as diverse as intercropping, integrated pest management, dry mulching and water infiltration, relying most of all on a participatory approach that brings together actors from the productive, academic, political and public sectors with a common vision. Assistance from various sectors may involve technology transfers⁵, from optimizations at the logistics level in field management to service provisioning and improvements in existing farming tools.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Altieri, M. A. (2018). <i>Agroecology: The Science of Sustainable Agriculture</i>. CRC Press.</p> <p>Tilman, D., Cassman, K. G., Matson, P. A., Naylor, R., & Polasky, S. (2002). Agricultural Sustainability and Intensive Production Practices. <i>Nature</i>, 418(6898), 671-677.</p> <p>Tittonell, P., Piñeiro, G., Garibaldi, L. A., Dogliotti, S., Olf, H., & Jobbagy, E. G. (2020). Agroecology in Large Scale Farming—A Research Agenda. <i>Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems</i>, 4.</p>	

⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

<p>Tscharntke, T., Klein, A. M., Kruess, A., Steffan-Dewenter, I., & Thies, C. (2005). Landscape Perspectives on Agricultural Intensification and Biodiversity–Ecosystem Service Management. <i>Ecology Letters</i>, 8(8), 857-874.</p> <p>Wezel, A., Bellon, S., Doré, T., Francis, C., Vallod, D., & David, C. (2009). Agroecology as a Science, a Movement and a Practice: A Review. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i>, 29, 503-515.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>
<p>Conventional agricultural practices that heavily rely on synthetic inputs often display high productivity in the short term, giving a false picture of their effectiveness. However, as resources are depleted, pesticides are overused, natural enemies and pollinators are lost, pollution and climate change increase and other factors worsen, the productivity of these systems falters (Tittonell et al., 2020). This leads to a search for safer, more accessible ways of producing food that also increase the sustainability and resilience of agroecosystems and reverse biodiversity loss and nature’s decline (Jones et al., 2022). Agroecological transitions contribute to transformative change by creating integrated land-use systems that improve ecological processes while strengthening local communities (Andrieu & Kebede, 2020). The goal is to comprehensively transform landscapes to function based on biodiversity strategies. However, this approach is not limited to proposing a set of new practices. By recognizing the socio-ecological dimension of the food system, it implies a paradigm shift in production (Peters & Thilmany, 2022).</p> <p>Efficient provision of ecosystem services in agroecosystems can lead to lower production costs for farmers and even alternative sources of income. Communities that adopt agroecological strategies will often form networks that foster more direct relationships in marketing, such as community agriculture (Andrieu & Kebede, 2020). Thus, agroecological initiatives can enable progress in reterritorializing agricultural and food systems. Another benefit is that diverse landscapes provide more jobs (Garibaldi & Pérez-Méndez, 2019). Conversion also brings social benefits through education and emotional well-being.</p> <p>Yet, the complexity of system changes can be a barrier to their implementation. Incentives for good agricultural practices can lead to more efficient use of external inputs, but they are insufficient to encourage full transitions (Tittonell et al., 2020). Because of this, initiatives worldwide aim to contribute to real change by encouraging producers to develop solutions to challenges with long-term outcomes based on local needs and capacities. Agroecological systems are based on local communities’ culture and identity, allowing less-represented groups decentralized access to resources, land and tools (Andrieu & Kebede, 2020). Trust-based relationships are key to fostering public-private partnerships and changing regulations to achieve change at all levels (Jones et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Andrieu, N., & Kebede, Y. (2020). Agroecology and Climate Change: A Case Study of the CCAFS Research Program. CCAFS Working Paper.</p> <p>Garibaldi, L. A., Sáez, A., Aizen, M. A., Fijen, T., & Bartomeus, I. (2020). Crop Pollination Management Needs Flower-Visitor Monitoring and Target Values. <i>Journal of Applied Ecology</i>, 57(4), 664-670.</p> <p>Jones, S. K., Bergamini, N., Beggi, F., Lesueur, D., Vinceti, B., Bailey, A., ... & Quintero, M. (2022). Research Strategies to Catalyze Agroecological Transitions in Low-and Middle-Income Countries. <i>Sustainability Science</i>, 17(6), 2557-2577.</p> <p>Peeters, A., Ambhul, E., Barberi, P., Migliorini, P., Ostermann, O., Goris, M., ... & Batello, C. (2021). Integrating Agroecology into European Agricultural Policies. Position Paper and Recommendations to the European Commission on Eco-Schemes.</p> <p>Tittonell, P., Piñeiro, G., Garibaldi, L. A., Dogliotti, S., Olff, H., & Jobbagy, E. G. (2020). Agroecology in Large Scale Farming—A Research Agenda. <i>Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems</i>, 4.</p>

Table SM.3.3. Phases of deliberate social-ecological transformations

3.3. Phases of deliberate social-ecological transformations	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Inner, Structural
<p>Inspired by the four-phases adaptation cycle, Olsson et al (2004) proposed that social-ecological transformations generally take place in three phases: 1) preparing for change, 2) navigating the transition and 3) building resilience of the new trajectory of development. The framework was expanded by describing subprocesses that occur within each phase and emphasizing the role of power and agency for the case of deliberate, purposeful or intentional social-ecological transformations (Moore et al., 2014). Deliberate transformation theory engages with the political, as well as the inner dimensions of transformations through questioning the assumptions, beliefs, values, commitments, loyalties and interests that support current structures, systems and behaviours (Manuel-Navarrete & Pelling, 2015; O'Brien, 2012). Considering the complex interactions between agency and structural factors in particular social-ecological systems Andrachuk et al. (2018) proposed a “building blocks” heuristic to complement the three-phases model. This heuristic recognizes the interplay of bottom-up and top-down perspectives on how to foster meaningful and lasting changes.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Andrachuk, M., Armitage, D., Hoang, H. D., & Van Le, N. (2018). Building blocks for social-ecological transformations. <i>Ecology and Society</i>, 23(2).</p> <p>Manuel-Navarrete, D., & Pelling, M. (2015). Subjectivity and the politics of transformation in response to development and environmental change. <i>Global Environmental Change</i>, 35, 558-569.</p> <p>Moore, M.-L., O. Tjornbo, E. Enfors, C. Knapp, J. Hodbod, J. A. Baggio, A. Norström, P. Olsson and D. Biggs. 2014. Studying the complexity of change: toward an analytical framework for understanding deliberate social-ecological transformations. <i>Ecology and Society</i> 19(4): 54.</p> <p>O'Brien, K. (2012). Global environmental change II: From adaptation to deliberate transformation. <i>Progress in human geography</i>, 36(5), 667-676.</p> <p>Olsson, P., Folke, C., & Hahn, T. (2004). Social-ecological transformation for ecosystem management: the development of adaptive co-management of a wetland landscape in southern Sweden. <i>Ecology and society</i>, 9(4).</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>While no single agent can control the course of a deliberate transformation, each agent can influence or nudge a transformation’s trajectory on each one of its phases (Westley et al., 2013). Transformations result from collaboration among a diverse set of actors operating at different levels, often in networks, from local users to municipalities to regional and national or supranational organizations. The drivers of transformations will depend on the context and type of transformation, but social-ecological transformations will generally depend on the system’s power dynamics. Specifically, it will depend on the interplay between the intentions of the system’s agents (pondered by their power) versus the systems’ path-dependencies or inertias, the agency of these same actors versus the robustness and resilience of current system’s structures, the alignment between cognitive and material processes and the emergence of transformative collective agency from aggregated individual intentions (Charli-Joseph et al., 2018; Manuel-Navarrete et al., 2019). Deliberate transformation theory can address the root causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline through the development and implementation of tools, safe spaces and intentional processes, such as Transformation-labs, that deliberately transform the power relationships between human agents and with non-human agents in social-ecological systems (Charli-Joseph et al., 2018; Pereira, Karpouzoglou, et al., 2018). Knowledge co-production and collective forms of leadership are also emerging within deliberate transformation theory as novel approaches that can deal with the root causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline by being more inclusive of diverse ways of knowing (Gram-Hanssen, 2021).</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Charli-Joseph, L., Siqueiros-Garcia, J. M., Eakin, H., Manuel-Navarrete, D., & Shelton, R. (2018). Promoting agency for social-ecological transformation. <i>Ecology and Society</i>, 23(2).</p>	

Gram-Hanssen, I. (2021). Individual and collective leadership for deliberate transformations: Insights from Indigenous leadership. *Leadership*, 17(5), 519-541.

Manuel-Navarrete, D., Morehart, C., Tellman, B., Eakin, H., Siqueiros-García, J. M., & Aguilar, B. H. (2019). Intentional disruption of path-dependencies in the Anthropocene: Gray versus green water infrastructure regimes in Mexico City, Mexico. *Anthropocene*, 26.

Pereira, L. M., Karpouzoglou, T., Frantzeskaki, N., & Olsson, P. (2018). Designing transformative spaces for sustainability in social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 23(4).

Westley, F. R., Tjornbo, O., Schultz, L., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Crona, B., & Bodin, Ö. (2013). A theory of transformative agency in linked social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 18(3).

Table SM.3.4. Panarchy theory

3.4. Panarchy theory	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Inner, Empowerment, Structural
<p>The panarchy theory (Gunderson & Holling, 2003) offers a comprehensive framework for understanding dynamic change in complex social-ecological systems . One major concept from this theory delineates a four-phase adaptive cycle, encompassing exploitation, conservation, release and reorganization, with each adaptive cycle connected across scales, to at least one adaptive cycle “above” and “below” that scale and numerous others alongside.</p> <p>The two phases of the “front loop” of the cycle are relatively slow, involving resource accumulation and institutionalization of that system state. However, the flexibility and diversity of the system are reduced in these phases, affecting its capacity to respond to external shocks. Then, if the state of that social-ecological systems is disrupted, it may open up space for new opportunities and innovations that might shape the reorganization of a new system (the “back loop”). A system that has resilience is able to move between all of these phases of the cycle without facing total collapse. The panarchy – the cross-scale connections of multiple adaptive cycles – also shapes the social-ecological systems through dynamics such as remembrance (i.e., social-ecological memory that provides context and experience after collapse) and revolt (which arises from the interactions between radical niches that aim to break down the status quo), which are key for understanding and guiding transformative change (Olsson et al., 2022).</p> <p>Subsequent developments in the field of resilience science have built upon panarchy theory by highlighting three key aspects that are involved in resilience: persistence, adaptability and transformability (Folke et al., 2010). In particular, scholars have underscored the critical role of resilience in social-ecological systems transformations in both destabilizing existing undesirable systems and strengthening emerging ones. Three phases typically proceed social-ecological systems transformations, namely, the preparing, navigating and stabilizing phase (Olsson et al., 2014); and each phase involves specific capacities for fostering social ecological systems transformations (Westley et al., 2013).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Folke C, Carpenter SR, Walker B, et al (2010) Resilience thinking: Integrating resilience, adaptability and transformability. <i>Ecol Soc</i> 15: doi: 10.1038/nnano.2011.191</p> <p>Gunderson, L. H. and C. S. Holling. 2003. <i>Panarchy: understanding transformations in human and natural systems</i>. Island, Washington, D.C., USA.</p> <p>Olsson P, Galaz V, Boonstra WJ (2014) Sustainability transformations: A resilience perspective. <i>Ecol Soc</i> 19: doi: 10.5751/ES-06799-190401</p> <p>Olsson, P, Folke, K. and Moore M-L (2022) Capacities for Navigating Large-Scale Sustainability Transformations: Exploring the Revolt and Remembrance Mechanisms for Shaping Collapse and Renewal in Social-Ecological Systems. In: Gunderson L.H., Allen, C.R. and Garmestani, A. (ed). <i>Applied Panarchy: Applications and Diffusion Across Disciplines</i>, p. 155-180. Island Press, Washington DC, USA.</p> <p>Westley F, Tjornbo O, Schultz L, et al (2013) A Theory of Transformative Agency in Linked Social-Ecological Systems. <i>Ecol Soc</i> 18: doi: 10.5751/ES-05072-180327</p>	

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Shifting from the current trajectories of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline remains a paramount concern for social-ecological systems transformations research. Much empirical work has focused on governance transformations of ecosystems and their biodiversity.

Transformations towards sustainable and just futures involves fundamental changes in the configuration of power and resource distribution within a given social system, the practices and processes upholding these configurations, the underlying norms, values and beliefs and their interconnections with ecological systems across multiple scales (Moore & Milkoreit, 2020). Thus, some relationships in existing systems will need to be “unmade” while others will need to be re-made, both among people and between people and their ecosystems.

Diverse drivers of change (e.g., attractors, external forces, or bottom-up pressure) can create an opportunity context that reduces the resilience of the existing dominant regime and (potentially) facilitates transformations to more desirable trajectories (Elmqvist et al., 2019). Once the dominant regime becomes destabilized, innovations experimented with by niche actors during the preparation phase may gain momentum, potentially catalyzing the emergence of a new regime (Moore et al., 2023). But this means different capacities at different times and many actors will be trying to ensure the transformation goes in their preferred direction. Consequently, there will be contestation, as multiple (and sometimes competing) ideas and approaches are assessed and combined (navigation phase). There is also a risk that the legacy of the previous regime may exert pressure (the “remembrance” dynamic), potentially coercing the disruptive potential of these innovations. In such cases, the innovations could be absorbed or coopted by the business-as-usual⁶ practices (Herrfahrdt-Pähle et al., 2020). Transformations will entail deep learning and reflexivity practices given the shifts in power and resource structures and flows needed, the creation of spaces for innovations to emerge and support for networks working on the different aspects of transformations (Tuckey et al., 2023)

Specific references:

Elmqvist T andersson E, Frantzeskaki N, et al (2019) Sustainability and resilience for transformation in the urban century. *Nat Sustain* 2:267–273. doi:10.1038/s41893-019-0250-1

Herrfahrdt-Pähle E, Schlüter M, Olsson P, et al (2020) Sustainability transformations: socio-political shocks as opportunities for governance transitions. *Glob Environ Chang* 63. doi: 10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102097

Moore ML, Hermanus L, Drimie S, et al (2023) Disrupting the opportunity narrative: navigating transformation in times of uncertainty and crisis. *Sustain Sci* 18:1649–1665. doi: 10.1007/s11625-023-01340-1

Moore M-L and Milkoreit, M. (2020) Imagination and transformations to sustainable and just futures. *Elementa* 8(1). doi: 10.1525/elementa.2020.081

Tuckey A, Harmáčková Z, Peterson G, et al (2023) What factors enable social-ecological transformative potential? The role of learning practices, empowerment and networking. *Ecol Soc* 28: doi: 10.5751/es-14163-280227

Table SM.3.5. Catalysing transformation

3.5. Catalysing transformation	Main approach: Systems
	Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Inner
Catalyzing transformation is a process used by change agents called transformation catalysts (Waddock, 2023; Waddock & Waddell, 2021) in many different contexts to bring about purposeful system transformation/change by connecting, cohering and amplifying the work of multiple change agents into self-aware and effective transformation systems (Waddock et al., 2022). Catalysis draws from the idea that paradigm shift in, for example, how humans understand their relationship to nature and other-than-human beings, drives economic and societal activities that impact the natural world	

⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

(Meadows, 1999). The idea of catalysis (Hussein et al., 2017) builds on a systems-based understanding that draws from complexity theory, based on understanding that bringing together multiple actors into greater coherence and action can lend impact to their transformation activities thereby developing potential to overcome vested interested to shift towards more equitable, flourishing socio-ecological systems⁷.

Key references:

- Hussein, T., Plummer, M., & Breen, B. (2018). How Field Catalysts Galvanise Social Change (SSIR). *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, Winter, 48–54.
- Meadows, D. (1999). *Leverage Points: Places to Intervene in a System* (Vol. 2020, Issue June 17). https://donellameadows.org/wp-content/userfiles/Leverage_Points.pdf
- Waddock, S. (2023). *Catalyzing Transformation: Making System Change Happen*. Business Expert Press.
- Waddock, S., & Waddell, S. (2021). Transformation Catalysts: Weaving Transformational Change for a Flourishing World for All. *Cadmus*, 4(4).
- Waddock, S., Waddell, S., Jones, P. H., & Kendrick, I. (2022). Convening Transformation Systems to Achieve System Transformation. *Journal of Awareness-Based Systems Change*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.47061/jabsc.v2i1.2023>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Recognizing the uniqueness of each socio-ecological context, catalyzing transformation offers a process-based approach to purposeful whole system transformation that can be applied and adapted as contextually needed (Waddock, 2023). The core idea is that change agents with significant self-awareness and other change capabilities (Wamsler, 2020), act as a transformation catalysts (Waddock & Waddell, 2021). Transformation catalysts work to purposefully convene and align multiple change agents with shared aspirations to enable them to co-creatively and collectively become effective transformation systems (Waddock et al., 2022). Transformation catalysts operate through three main processes: connecting, cohering and amplifying. Connecting involves enabling convened change agents to collectively ‘see’ and understand their system using a range of stakeholder analyses and mapping processes and then make sense of what needs to change and how in a process broadly termed sensemaking. Cohering involves engaging change agents in processes through which convened actors collectively and co-creatively envision and co-emerge shared aspirations or desired futures using a range of possible collective visualization techniques (Sharpe et al., 2016). They then co-generate action plans to achieve those aspirations (i.e., visions, goals, desired futures) both collectively and independently as feasible. Amplification involves establishing an effective and purposeful transformation system in which actors implement action plans, sometimes experimentally, learning from and adapting them as necessary. To maintain change processes, they further develop additional catalytic actors to convene subsystem transformation systems as needed (Waddock, 2023). This approach can be applied in contextually-appropriate ways to many different systems and subsystems, adapting the processes of connecting, cohering and amplifying to fit the circumstances through adopting life-centred, stewardship, values-driven and complexity-based organizing and design principles that enhance the flourishing of human as well as other-than-human life.

Specific references:

- Sharpe, B., Hodgson, A., Leicester, G., Lyon, A., & Fazey, I. (2016). Three horizons: A pathways practice for transformation. *Ecology and Society*, 21(2).
- Waddock, S. (2023). *Catalyzing Transformation: Making System Change Happen*. Business Expert Press.
- Waddock, S., & Waddell, S. (2021). Transformation Catalysts: Weaving Transformational Change for a Flourishing World for All. *Cadmus*, 4(4).
- Waddock, S., Waddell, S., Jones, P. H., & Kendrick, I. (2022). Convening Transformation Systems to Achieve System Transformation. *Journal of Awareness-Based Systems Change*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.47061/jabsc.v2i1.2023>

⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Wamsler, C. (2020). Education for sustainability: Fostering a more conscious society and transformation towards sustainability. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-04-2019-0152>

Table SM.3.6. Seeds of good anthropocenes

<p>3.6. Seeds of good anthropocenes</p>	<p>Main approach: Systems</p> <p>Secondary approach: Empowerment</p>
<p>The Seeds of Good Anthropocene initiative is based on the assumption that achieving desirable futures in the Anthropocene involves imagining more radical transformative futures (Bennett et al., 2016). Current visions of the future are dominated by dystopian visions of the future, while scientific visions are often overly optimistic expectations of change despite business-as-usual approaches. The lack of a wider variety of alternative futures and the methods to create them presents a barrier to innovation and action (Pereira et al., 2019). Complexity and resilience approaches are particularly well-suited to the challenge of transforming to a more sustainable Anthropocene because of the uncertainty, novelty and uneven nature of transformative change. While most theories of change feature gradual change of dominant systems, the Seeds of Good Anthropocenes approach is based on the idea that the world is more diverse and surprising and that transformative change often comes from the combination of existing marginal experiments. A high diversity of experiments towards change is essential to provide response diversity that enables a system to cope with surprises and shocks.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Bennett, E.M., Solan, M., Biggs, R., MacPhearson, T., Norstrom, A., Olsson, P., Pereira, L., Peterson, G.D., Raudsepp-Hearne, C., Beirmann, F., Carpenter, S.R., Ellis, E., Hichert, T. Galaz, V., Lahsen, M., Martin-Lopez, B., Nicolas, K. A., Preisser, R., Vince, G., Vervoort, J., & Xu, J. 2016. Bright Spots: Seeds of a Good Anthropocene. <i>Frontiers in Ecology and Environment</i> 14(8), pp.441-448. https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1309</p> <p>Pereira, L. M., T. Hichert, M. Hamann, R. Preiser and R. Biggs. 2018. Using futures methods to create transformative spaces: visions of a good Anthropocene in southern Africa. <i>Ecology and Society</i> 23(1):19. https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-09907-230119</p> <p>Pereira, L., Bennett, E., Biggs, R., Mangnus, A., Norstrom, A.V., Peterson, G., Raudsepp-Hearne, C., Sellberg, M., & Vervoort, J. 2019. Seeding Change by Visioning Good Anthropocenes. <i>Solutions Journal</i>, 10(3). https://www.thesolutionsjournal.com/article/seeding-change-visioning-good-anthropocenes/</p> <p>Pereira, L. M., K. K. Davies, E. Belder, S. Ferrier, S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, H. Kim, J. J. Kuiper, S. Okayasu, M. G. Palomo, H. M. Pereira, G. Peterson, J. Sathyapalan, M. Schoolenberg, R. Alkemade, S. Carvalho Ribeiro, A. Greenaway, J. Hauck, N. King, T. Lazarova, F. Ravera, N. Chettri, W. W. L. Cheung, R. J. J. Hendriks, G. Kolomytsev, P. Leadley, J. Metzger, K. N. Ninan, R. Pichs, A. Popp, C. Rondinini, I. Rosa, D. Vuuren and C. J. Lundquist. 2020. Developing multiscale and integrative nature–people scenarios using the Nature Futures Framework. <i>People and Nature</i> 2(4):1172–1195.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>The Seeds of Good Anthropocene is based on the idea that many possible futures are embedded in the present. As people notice problems in the world, they take action to address those problems and an important step for fostering global transformation is to highlight those actions. These actions begin as isolated experiments. Highlighting them shows the plurality of visions of a better future; it allows for studies of when, where, why and how different approaches towards transformation work (or don't); it fosters further action via empowerment; and it might help build shadow networks among seeds. This can lead to an emerging awareness of the need for change and, ultimately new meta-narratives about changing practices, values and structures. Windows of opportunity can open through crisis, political opportunity, or other changes in the system, leading to openness to a new regime being institutionalized through changing structures such as policies, as well as through more widespread change in values and practices.</p>	

The theory of change of the Seeds of Good Anthropocene approach proposes that large (macro-scale) changes emerge from substantial periods of experimentation at the micro-level that lead to the formation of new coalitions. The preparation phase (involving periods of experimentation and coalescing) and the navigation phases are linked by a window of opportunity or the opening up of an opportunity context. This can be a crisis, or anticipated crisis, that destabilizes the existing regime and/or makes opportunities for intentional change more visible or transparent. This window of opportunity allows the coalitions of interacting actors, groups and processes emerging from the preparation phase to begin to become institutionalized at the meso-level. Understanding of how these meso-scale organizations grow to be dominant, collapse, or are co-opted by existing macro-scale remains limited. See figure from Sellberg et al. (2020), which adapted the figure from Pereira et al. (2018).

Specific references:

Raudsepp-Hearne, C, G.D. Peterson, E.M. Bennett, R. Biggs, A.V. Norström, L. Pereira, J. Vervoort, D.M. Iwaniec, T. McPhearson, P. Olsson, T. Hichert, M. Falardeau, A. Jiménez Aceituno. 2019. Seeds of good anthropocenes: developing sustainability scenarios for Northern Europe. *Sustainability Science*. 15, 605–617

Table SM.3.7. Collective action in social-ecological systems

3.7. Collective action in social-ecological systems	Main approach: Systems
Secondary approach: Structural	
<p>Collective action is a central feature and need of both people and nature, essential for enabling transformative changes by working together to establish common goals and systems to achieve them. The social-ecological systems framework developed by Elinor Ostrom and colleagues, (McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014; Ostrom, 2009a) is a comprehensive empirically-based tool for diagnosing the variables hindering or enabling collective action at the interface of people and nature. The framework provides organized sets of variables in eight first-tier categories, with the central four being Governance, Actors, Resource Users and Resource systems. Each first-tier category contains nested second-tier variables – 56 in total - that are more specific such as resource system productivity, property rights, leadership and economic value. The logic of the framework is to provide a comprehensive diagnostic checklist of the empirically-backed variables that may be influencing collective action in the commons - which are understood as social-ecological systems - such as fishery, urban gardens or land for pastoralists. Similar to medical doctors, sustainability scholars can use the framework to diagnose collective action and sustainability outcome problems with the framework by first assessing the role of each variable in the system of interest and then narrowing those down to the underlying factors that can be addressed with governance interventions to enable transformative changes in the system’s functionality towards more desirable outcomes (Cox, 2011). Both social and biophysical variables shape collective action processes and the characteristics of those variables can make it easier or harder for groups to work together and transform the system effectively. Recent reviews of the literature have suggested it’s evolution into sub-frameworks tailored to specific sectors to more effectively define and measure common variables (Partelow, 2019). Applying the framework involves interdisciplinary qualitative and quantitative methods, where recent guidelines have been proposed (Nagel & Partelow, 2022).</p>	
Key references:	
<p>Cox, M. 2011. Advancing the diagnostic analysis of environmental problems. <i>International Journal of the Commons</i> 5(2):346–363.</p>	
How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework	
<p>Transformative changes in social-ecological systems occur through governance, which means by intentionally developing and/or changing rules, norms, networks and social structures (i.e., institutions) in a way that more effectively enables collective action towards shared group goals and sustainability. Application of the social-ecological systems framework allows diagnosing what institutional changes may most effectively fit the social-ecological context, which then inform participatory and inclusive deliberative processes to develop governance institutions accordingly. Detailed case study research and</p>	

synthetic meta-analyses have helped identify key principles for governing the commons as social-ecological systems. Elinor Ostrom’s Design Principles (Cox et al., 2010; Ostrom, 1990) suggest eight features of a governance system that if present, substantially increase the likelihood of successful collective action when those collective actions are aimed at enabling transformative changes towards sustainability. These include clear social and ecological boundaries, alignment of governance with local conditions, the ability of stakeholders to participate in governance decision-making, self-monitoring by stakeholders, graduated sanctions, conflict resolution mechanisms, rights to organize and institutional alignment with external governance systems. Further synthetic assessments (e.g., (Bodin, 2017; Holahan & Lubell, 2016) argue that specific factors such as social networks and capital, strong leadership, kinship bonds, reciprocity among stakeholders, economic heterogeneity and shared norms all improve the likelihood of collective action, where policy programmes and community-based development efforts can effectively direct capacity attention. Recent meta-analyses have further suggested that specific variable configurations from the social-ecological systems framework interact in recurring patterns across many case studies such as leadership, social capital and importance of the resource (Villamayor-Tomas et al., 2020) Identifying and governing those dynamic interactions effectively can catalyze and leverage the types of intentional transformations that change the processes and outcomes in social-ecological systems towards more desirable futures.

Specific references:

Bodin, Ö. 2017. Collaborative environmental governance: Achieving collective action in social-ecological systems. *Science* 357(6352).

Table SM.3.8. Integrative framework for transformative social change

3.8. Integrative framework for transformative social change	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Structural
<p>Addressing complex environmental problems means a system-level transformations in lock-in structures such as social norms, infrastructures and institutions (Seto et al., 2016). Solutions also emerge as a result of the dynamic interaction between individual and collective actions. Individuals can contribute to sustainable pathways incrementally through their consumption and lifestyle choices, while also collectively influencing social structures through both implicit and explicit support for systemic change (O’Brien & Sygna, 2013). Because social systems and human actions are deeply interconnected, both top-down and bottom-up approaches are necessary to achieve transformative change (Geels & Schot, 2007).</p> <p>An integrative framework for transformative social change elucidates various pathways to advance environmental sustainability, explicitly treating both behavioural and social structural processes as interdependent elements for system feedbacks (Naito et al., 2022). Through behavioural processes, individuals play a crucial role in affecting social systems that in turn enable or constrain individual actions. In particular, the framework distinguishes between three types of individual actions that contribute differently to transformative change: private action that people take independently to reduce their environmental footprints (e.g., recycling); social-signaling action that people conduct to signal their environmental values (e.g., opinion sharing); and system-changing action that people engage in with a clear intent of influencing laws, policies and corporate actions (e.g., protesting). In social structural processes, it is important to analyze how existing institutions, social norms, economic systems and infrastructures are arranged and how they facilitate conditions that perpetuate environmental problems. Removing barriers to or enhancing the enablers of change within social structures is key to achieving rapid and dynamic transformations.</p> <p>The framework suggests that transformative change can be initiated from any points within either the behavioural or structural processes. However, it ultimately implies change across all aspects to establish and diffuse new pro-environmental norms (Otto et al., 2020).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Geels, F. W., & Schot, J. (2007). Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways. <i>Research Policy</i>, 36(3), 399–417. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2007.01.003</p>	

- Naito, R., Zhao, J., & Chan, K. M. A. (2022). An integrative framework for transformative social change: a case in global wildlife trade. *Sustainability Science*, 17(1), 171–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01081-z>
- O'Brien, K., & Sygna, L. (2013). Responding to climate change: The three spheres of transformation. *Proceedings of Transformation in a Changing Climate*, 16–23.
- Otto, I. M., Donges, J. F., Cremades, R., Bhowmik, A., Hewitt, R. J., Lucht, W., ... Schellnhuber, H. J. (2020). Social tipping dynamics for stabilizing Earth's climate by 2050. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 117(5), 2354–2365. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1900577117>
- Seto, K. C., Davis, S. J., Mitchell, R., Stokes, E. C., Unruh, G., & Ürge-Vorsatz, D. (2016). Carbon lock-in: Types, causes and policy implications. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 41, 425–452. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085934>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Deliberate transformative change can occur when interventions simultaneously target various leverage points along the behavioural and social structural processes. It entails the widespread adoption of sustainable behaviours from the committed minority to the general public. Additionally, it implies fundamental shifts in the systems that facilitate sustainable practices at the societal level.

The behavioural intervention process involves engaging people in not only private actions but also civic actions that might collectively help shift social norms, institutions and infrastructures (Chan et al., 2020). Behavioural interventions may benefit from tailoring their approaches to specific types of individual actions, as these actions are influenced by unique sets of social and psychological factors (Naito et al., 2023). Interventions that effectively target social and psychological factors can produce behaviour change and potentially mobilize a large number of individuals to take pro-environmental actions. In the context of transformative change, motivating people to participate in civic actions (i.e., social-signaling and system-changing actions) is particularly important, as these actions can generate ripples that extend outward through societies, potentially leading to more significant impacts once a tipping point⁸ is reached (Constantino et al., 2022).

The structural intervention process focuses on changing the current arrangements of institutions, policies, infrastructures and economic systems that can lock in most forms of social interactions and practices for a long time. Interventions need to address the barriers and enablers of transformative change within the systems at various administrative and geographical levels, spanning from local to global (Bodin, 2017). This involves enhancing institutional capacity for monitoring and adapting to environmental change, promoting knowledge sharing, fostering political will, mobilizing adequate resources and technologies and nurturing stable social networks with shared visions and strong leadership (Olsson et al., 2004). Changes in these elements will likely lead to the emergence of new norms, meanings and rules that reinforce and institutionalize pro-environmental values and sustainable pathways (P. Young, 2015).

Specific references:

- Bodin, Ö. (2017). Collaborative environmental governance: Achieving collective action in social-ecological systems. *Science*, 357(6352). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan1114>
- Chan, K. M. A., Boyd, D. R., Gould, R. K., Jetzkowitz, J., Liu, J., Muraca, B., ... Brondizio, E. S. (2020). Levers and leverage points for pathways to sustainability. *People and Nature*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10124>
- Constantino, S. M., Sparkman, G., Kraft-Todd, G. T., Bicchieri, C., Centola, D., Shell-Duncan, B., ... Weber, E. U. (2022). Scaling up change: A critical review and practical guide to harnessing social norms for climate action. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 23(2), 50–97. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15291006221105279>
- Naito, R., Zhao, J., Naidoo, R., & Chan, K. M. A. (2023). Private and civic actions as distinct types of individual engagement for transforming the exotic pet trade. *People and Nature*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10517>

⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Olsson, P., Folke, C., & Berkes, F. (2004). Adaptive comanagement for building resilience in social-ecological systems. *Environmental Management*, 34(1), 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-003-0101-7>

Young, H. P. (2015). The evolution of social norms. *The Annual Review of Economics*, 7(1), 359–387. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-080614-115322>

Table SM.3.9. Sustainability transitions

3.9. Sustainability transitions	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Structural
<p>Drawing on insights from complexity theory, the concept of transitions points at the patterns and mechanisms underlying such structural change in systems: transitions are a non-linear shift from one dynamic equilibrium to another. From natural and environmental sciences, transitions are understood as outcome of processes of self-organization, emergence and co-evolution that can keep a complex system dynamically stable. But when the context changes and the system is unable to adapt tipping points occur (Folke et al., 2004). Sustainability transitions research (Loorbach et al., 2017) explores what this could mean for transitions in the making by combining it with insights from social sciences. In complex societal systems transformative change is less straightforward: positions of actors, experiences, expectations, interests, emotions, power, imagination and preferences make societal transitions ambiguous, contested and uncertain (Rotmans et al., 2001). Yet the basic pattern has proven to be repetitive and predictable. In societal systems, actors develop so-called ‘regimes’ (shared cultures, structures and practices) that provide stability but also create path dependency (Rip, 1995). Over time ultimately context changes (technological, geopolitical, demographic changes combined with increasing sustainability concerns), internal lock-in and emerging alternatives will make established regimes ‘unsustainable’ and drive it out-of-equilibrium. The X-curve (Hebinck et al., 2022) identifies the different co-evolving patterns of increasingly destabilizing regime structures and emerging alternative technologies, practices, norms, structures and models. In this process actors will experience and develop sense of urgency, awareness and opportunity in different ways and start to work to accelerate or work against transformative pressures building up. Typically established (incumbent) actors are more likely to seek control, stability and avoid chaos and breakdown, while external actors and social innovations search for it. The understanding of transformative change in terms of the patterns and mechanisms underlying transitions does not provide a blueprint for action but it does offer a basis for new forms of governance that can influence the speed and direction of these emergent and semi-autonomous processes.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Folke, C., Carpenter, S., Walker, B., Scheffer, M., Elmqvist, T., Gunderson, L., & Holling, C. S. (2004). Regime shifts, resilience and biodiversity in ecosystem management. <i>Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution and Systematics</i>, 35, 557–581. https://doi.org/10.1146/ANNUREV.ECOLSYS.35.021103.105711</p> <p>Hebinck, A., Diercks, G., von Wirth, T., Beers, P. J., Barsties, L., Buchel, S., Greer, R., van Steenbergen, F., & Loorbach, D. (2022). An actionable understanding of societal transitions: the X-curve framework. <i>Sustainability Science</i>, 17(3), 1009–1021. https://doi.org/10.1007/S11625-021-01084-W/FIGURES/3</p> <p>Loorbach, D., Frantzeskaki, N., & Avelino, F. (2017). Sustainability Transitions Research: Transforming Science and Practice for Societal Change. <i>Annual Review of Environment and Resources</i>, 42(1), 599–626. https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102014-021340</p> <p>Rip, A. (1995). Introduction of new technology: making use of recent insights from sociology and economics of technology. <i>Technology Analysis and Strategic Management</i>, 7(4), 417–431.</p> <p>Rotmans, J., & al, E. (2001). More evolution than revolution. <i>Foresight</i>, 3(1), 1–17.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	

Deliberate transformative change, or transitions management, combines four types of strategies to be combined to support transformative change (Loorbach, 2022). First, anchoring ambitions to achieve a nature positive economy that benefits people and planet rather than to reduce negative impacts of the existing. Second, institutional support for the acceleration, diffusion and scaling of new structures, cultures and practices in support of a nature positive economy. Third, adaptation and adjustment of existing institutional conditions to fit a nature positive economy. Finally, a dedicated and managed decline and phase-out of unsustainable, fossil and linear parts of the economy.

Societal transitions are socially constructed: how actors respond to (perceived need for) transformative change determines its pattern, pathways and outcomes. Research into the agency in transitions (Grin et al., 2011). identifies the different strategies and actions that either reinforce path dependencies or explore alternatives. They make clear that institutionalized approaches (public and private) prioritize technological innovation and controlled ways to improve existing economic systems (Smink et al., 2015). Work on transformative innovation policy⁹ (Diercks et al., 2019) and transformative government (Braams et al., 2021) explores how formal policies could be redesigned to support transformative rather than incremental change⁹.

Yet it is also found that types of agency that drive transformative change typically emerge outside institutions in the form of transformative social innovation. Transformative social innovation refers to new ways of ‘thinking, doing and organizing that challenge, alter or replace an incumbent regime’ (Avelino et al., 2019). These might involve civil servants, entrepreneurs, citizens, researchers, or other societal actors that develop niches wherein they experimentally develop alternatives. The underlying governance logic is based on a critical view of the status quo, backcasting from a desired future, selective networking and a learning-by-doing approach. These principles have provided the basis for transition management, a governance approach seeking to influence both regime-led and niche-based types of agency for desired transitions (Grin et al., 2011).

Specific references:

Avelino, F., Wittmayer, J. M., Pel, B., Weaver, P., Dumitru, A., Haxeltine, A., Kemp, R., Jørgensen, M. S., Bauler, T., Ruijsink, S., & O’Riordan, T. (2019). Transformative social innovation and (dis)empowerment. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 145, 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TECHFORE.2017.05.002>

Braams, R. B., Wesseling, J. H., Meijer, A. J., & Hekkert, M. P. (2021). Legitimizing transformative government: Aligning essential government tasks from transition literature with normative arguments about legitimacy from Public Administration traditions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 39, 191–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EIST.2021.04.004>

Diercks, G., Larsen, H., & Steward, F. (2019). Transformative innovation policy: Addressing variety in an emerging policy paradigm. *Research Policy*, 48(4), 880–894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.10.028>

Grin, J., Rotmans, J., & Schot, J. (2011a). On patterns and agency in transition dynamics: Some key insights from the KSI programme. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 1(1), 76–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EIST.2011.04.008>

Loorbach, D. A. (2022). Designing radical transitions: a plea for a new governance culture to empower deep transformative change. *City, Territory and Architecture*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40410-022-00176-Z/FIGURES/1>

Table SM.3.10. Social movement theory

3.10. Social movement theory	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Empowerment, Structural
A social movement is a network of informal interactions between a plurality of individuals, groups and/or organizations, engaged in a political or cultural conflict, on the basis of a shared collective identity” (Diani, 1992). As a distinctive forms of contentious politics, social movements involve	

⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

collective claims-making which, if realized, would conflict with someone else's interests. They also act as a counterweight to oppressive power, as a summons to popular action against a wide range of injustices (Wood, 2019).

Social movements theories have highlighted the political aspect of the contentions that give to collective action. This is so because governments, in their various forms, participate as key players, whether as claimants, as actors in the claim making, objects or allies of claims, or as monitors of the contention (McAdam et al., 2001).

Different theories have focused on different dimensions of these social processes. Among the most relevant perspectives, the resource mobilization theory, drawing on a rational choice approach, have focused on the assets and capacities of aggrieved groups. Resources may be tangible, such as money and facilities and intangible, such as the solidarities, cultural commitments and identity networks (Jenkins, 2001).

Other theories have focused on the social movements' shared collective identity. Collective identity here refers to imagined as well as concrete communities. As a fluid and relational process, it involves an act of perception and construction, as well as the discovery of preexisting bonds, interests and boundaries (Polletta & Jasper, 2001). Other analytical perspectives have focused on political opportunities, taking into account the multiplicity of independent centres of power within the polity, the openness of the polity to new actors, the instability of current political alignments and the availability of influential allies or supporters - within which activists are making claims (Tilly, 1993). The rise and fall of social movements mark the expansion and contraction of democratic opportunities (Wood, 2019).

Key references:

Diani, M. (1992). The concept of social movement. *The Sociological Review*, vol. 40, 1, 1-25.

Jenkins, J. (2001). Social Movements: Resource Mobilization Theory. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 14368-14371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-043076-7/01925-2>

Mc Adam, D., Tarrow, S. and Tilly, Ch. (2001). *Dynamics of Contention*. Cambridge University Press.

Polletta, F. and Jasper, J.M. (2001). Collective Identity and Social Movements. *Annual Review of Sociology*, vol. 27, 283-305. Stable URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2678623>

Tilly, Ch. (1993). Social Movements as Historically Specific Clusters of Political Performances. *Berkeley Journal of Sociology*, vol. 38, 1-30.

Tilly, Ch. And Wood, L. (2018). 1. Social movements as politics. In: Tilly, Ch., Castañeda, E. y Wood, L. *Social Movements, 1768–2018*. Fourth Edition. Routledge.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Social movements are drivers of social changes. Approaches that include multi-site research, transnational analytical tools, dialogues with local actors and researchers and an ethic oriented towards intercultural dialogues are needed. As social movements and researchers being different producers of knowledge, constructive dialogues and participation in collective reflexivity processes are also crucial (Pleyers, 2023).

Transformation to sustainability calls for radical and systemic societal shifts, where environmental justice movements are key agents. The systemic, multi-dimensional and intersectional approach inherent in environmental justice activism is uniquely situated to contribute to the realization of this transformation (Temper et al., 2018). International and national discussions have focused on economic, technological and administrative mechanisms to renew and distribute the benefits of biodiversity. In the meantime, new social actors emerged, including local social movements, engaged in the redefinition of cultural and ethnic identities. Their political strategies constitute important interventions into what is already a highly transnationalized nature/culture field (Escobar, 1998).

“By mobilizing an appropriate mix of scientific and lay knowledge, conservation science, policy and practice would be better equipped to identify and facilitate more legitimate and effective goals and actions” (Pascual et al., 2021). These authors call to consider the breadth of multiple actors' values and the implications of doing so, including an analysis of the many causalities behind the destruction of living nature. In addition, Scheidel et al (2022) have emphasized how social and ecological processes actively co-shape each other. They have shown how specific ecological characteristics may enable social movements to create alternatives they perceive as more just and sustainable, how ecosystems

may become important resource providers to sustain protest networks, or how the ecological dynamics of the more-than human world, such as seasonality or environmental change, may shape the trajectories of resistances, whether in their favour, or against them.

Specific references:

- Escobar, A. (1998). Whose Knowledge, Whose nature? Biodiversity, Conservation and the Political Ecology of Social Movements. *Journal of Political Ecology*, Vol.5, 53-82.
- Pascual, U., Adams, W., Díaz, S., Lele, S., Mace, G. and Turnhout, E. (2021). Biodiversity and the challenge of pluralism. *Nature Sustainability*, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-021-00694-7>
- Pleyers, G. (2023). For a global sociology of social movements. Beyond methodological globalism and extractivism, *Globalizations*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2023.2173866>
- Scheidel, A., Liu, J., Del Bene, D., Mingorria, S. and Villamayor-Tomas, S. (2022): Ecologies of contention: how more-than-human natures shape contentious actions and politics. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2022.2142567>
- Temper, L., Walter, M., Rodriguez, I., Kothari, A., Turhan, E. (2018). A perspective on radical transformations to sustainability: resistances, movements and alternatives. *Sustainability Science*, 13(3), 747-764.

Table SM.3.11. Transition governance

3.11. Transition governance	Main approach: Systems
<p>Transition governance is an area of sustainability transitions research that explores the role of actors in transition processes and how these can be influenced. The focus on agency, power, institutions as well as behaviour, expectations, emotions and culture is referred to as the socio-institutional perspective. It builds on the insights from sustainability transitions research that unsustainabilities are grounded in persistent societal regimes and that transitions are non-linear disruptive processes, which are both driven and worked against by different types of strategies and actions of actors. Transition then refers to structural reconfiguration, involving patterns of build-up and breakdown, from one stable societal system to another. This process of change evolves over decades. Transition governance identifies ways of and for actors to cope with the challenges of navigating complex, ambiguous and uncertain contexts towards just sustainability.</p> <p>Societal regimes are the dominant cultures, structures and practices in a complex societal system that remain in a dynamic equilibrium. Vested interests¹⁰, established routines, discourse and institutional conditions create path-dependencies and lock-ins that resist more structural change. These societal regimes provide stability to the system as well as inertia by being wired to resist change. Societal regimes generally have an interest in sustaining the status-quo and will work against transformative change, until it is inevitable.</p> <p>Alternatives to these societal regimes often emerge as a response to feelings of discontent as to how the societal regime operates and (dis)functions. These innovations can be considered radical, alternative, marginalized and outside the social norm. Initially, these emerge in protected environments, beyond the reach of the regime, allowing alternatives practices to be ‘nurtured’. Over time, some alternatives become better organized, visible and understood, contributing to further diffusion of these alternative – allowing them to spread, scale, or translate into other contexts, until they become a viable, stable alternative to the dominant system. As not all alternatives succeed, diversity and experimentation are vital.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Loorbach, D., Frantzeskaki, N. & Avelino, F. Sustainability Transitions Research: Transforming Science and Practice for Societal Change. <i>Annu Rev Environ Resour</i> 42, 599–626 (2017).</p> <p>Hebinck, A. et al. An actionable understanding of societal transitions: the X-curve framework. <i>Sustain Sci</i> 17, 1009–1021 (2022).</p>	

¹⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Grin, J. (2010). Understanding transitions from a governance perspective. In J. Grin, J. Rotmans, & J. Schot, eds., *Transitions to sustainable development: New directions in the study of long term transformative change*, New York: Routledge, pp. 223–319.

Loorbach, D., Wittmayer, J., Avelino, F., von Wirth, T. & Frantzeskaki, N. Transformative innovation and translocal diffusion. *Environ Innov Soc Transit* 35, 251–260 (2020).

Smith, A., Fressoli, M., Abrol, D., Arond, E. & Ely, A. *Grassroots innovation movements*. (Earthscan, 2015).

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transition governance aims to identify the different types of agency that influence transition processes and to support actors in navigating societal transitions by focusing on ‘transitions in the making’. Characteristic of these emerging patterns of transformative change that might lead to full transitions, is an increasing urgency to explore breakdown of unwanted (locked-in) practices in relation to the build-up of desired practices. Being part of transitions in the making proves to be chaotic, turbulent and unstructured: Societal actors find this increasingly difficult to gauge and respond very differently to transformative pressures that develop. Overcoming the dysfunctional legacies of the unsustainable societal regime and allowing fundamental reconfiguration of the system are key to transition governance.

While current regimes prioritize technological innovation, fostering deliberate transformative change relies on transformative social innovation: ‘new ways of thinking, doing and organizing’ that ‘challenge, alter, or replace’ dominant structures, cultures and practices of unsustainable societal regimes. Embracing a plurality in perspectives and engage with diverse societal actors by overcoming the dichotomies between State, market and community, is crucial. Not only does this broaden the notion of what is considered expert knowledge used for governance, but it also empowers different type of actors as ‘agents of change’, enabling change in a multitude of ways. This in turn, creates space for transformative social innovations to flourish and experiment with alternatives to the dominant structures.

Lastly, reconceptualizing ‘power’ is vital to acknowledge and empower the various capacities needed for transformations. The distinction is made between different types of power that are important to governing sustainability transitions: innovative power, which fosters creation of new practices; reinforcing power, which has the capacity to sustain; and transformative power, which develops new institutions and structures. This allows for a governance culture that goes beyond ‘niche-regime’ power struggles and instead facilitates more diverse and hybrid power dynamics that can challenge the status quo and overcome vested interest.

Specific references:

Hebinck, A. et al. An actionable understanding of societal transitions: the X-curve framework. *Sustain Sci* 17, 1009–1021 (2022).

Loorbach, D. A. Designing radical transitions: a plea for a new governance culture to empower deep transformative change. *City, Territory and Architecture* 9, (2022).

Avelino, F. & Wittmayer, J. M. Shifting Power Relations in Sustainability Transitions : A Multi-actor Perspective. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning* 7200, 1–23 (2015).

Ghosh, B., Ramos-Mejía, M., Machado, R. C., Yuana, S. L. & Schiller, K. Decolonising transitions in the Global South: Towards more epistemic diversity in transitions research. *Environ Innov Soc Transit* 41, 106–109 (2021).

Avelino, F. Power in Sustainability Transitions: Analysing power and (dis)empowerment in transformative change towards sustainability. *Environmental Policy and Governance* 27, 505–520 (2017).

Table SM.3.12. Leverage points for sustainability transformation

3.12. Leverage points for sustainability transformation	Main approach: Systems
Leverage points are places to intervene in a system where a small shift can produce systemic change (Meadows, 1999). They occur within complex social-ecological systems and can be acted on in order	

to induce change. Interventions in leverage points can “unlock” undesirable feedbacks and unleash the transformative potential of many interconnected systems to shift onto pathways for sustainability. Leverage points can be classified into deep and shallow ones (Abson et al., 2017). Interventions at deep leverage points have greater potential to change a system, while interventions at shallow leverage points may have minor influences (Chan et al., 2020). Therefore, the distinction between shallow and deep leverage points describes the extent to which interventions at these points can fundamentally alter the trajectory of a system and transform it. Following Abson et al.’s (2017) classification, more shallow places to intervene include parameters and feedbacks. Deeper places to intervene include the designs and intents of a system, not least because changing system design and intent automatically has repercussions for feedbacks and parameters. However, because social-ecological systems are complex and adaptive, interventions can have unintended consequences, making it crucial to not just understand possible interventions at different levels of systemic depth, but also interactions among leverage points. These interactions describe how one type of change in a system might precipitate further changes across different systemic depths (i.e., parameters, feedbacks, design, intent; Fischer & Riechers, 2019). Changes in parameters could pave the way for a questioning of system goals and paradigms and vice versa. Hence, sequences of how shallow to deep systemic changes flow on from and reinforce one another can be found, creating coherent chains of leverage. Alternative chains of leverage can highlight mismatching or even conflicting elements (such as conflicting paradigms, rules, institutions) and highlight possibly more effective alternatives (Riechers et al., 2022).

Key references:

Abson, D.J., Fischer, J., Leventon, J., Newig, J., Schomerus, T., Vilsmaier, U., von Wehrden, H., Abernethy, P., Ives, C.D., Jager, N.W., Lang, D.J., 2017. Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *Ambio* 46, 30–39. doi: 10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y

Chan, K.M.A., Boyd, D.R., Gould, R.K., Jetzkowitz, J., Liu, J., Muraca, B., Naidoo, R., Olmsted, P., Satterfield, T., Selomane, O., Singh, G.G., Sumaila, R., Ngo, H.T., Boedhihartono, A.K., Agard, J., Aguiar, A.P.D., Armenteras, D., Balint, L., Barrington-Leigh, C., Cheung, W.W.L., Díaz, S., Driscoll, J., Esler, K., Eyster, H., Gregr, E.J., Hashimoto, S., Hernández Pedraza, G.C., Hickler, T., Kok, M., Lazarova, T., Mohamed, A.A.A., Murray-Hudson, M., O’Farrell, P., Palomo, I., Saysel, A.K., Seppelt, R., Settele, J., Strassburg, B., Xue, D., Brondizio, E.S., 2020. Levers and leverage points for pathways to sustainability. *People Nat.* doi: 10.1002/pan3.10124

Fischer, J., Riechers, M., 2019. A leverage points perspective on sustainability. *People Nat.* doi: 10.1002/pan3.13

Meadows, D.H., 1999. *Leverage points: Places to intervene in a system.* The Sustainability Institute, Hartland.

Riechers, M., Fischer, J., Manlosa, A.O., Ortiz-Przychodzka, S., Sala, J.E., 2022. Operationalising the leverage points perspective for empirical research. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 57. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2022.101206

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transformation may be achieved through strengthening elements within a system or by destabilizing them, e.g., destabilizing the feedbacks that keep a system locked in and then activating the drivers that push it elsewhere (Olsson et al., 2014). A diversity of alternatives is necessary to build resilient social-ecological systems, especially because the existence of these alternative elements means that when a large powerful system actor is removed, there are existing alternatives available. Hence, the transformative potential may be “unleashed” by finding leverage points that, on the one side, could strengthen an alternative chain of leverage (coherent interactions between elements on parameters-feedbacks-design-intent level), as well as dismantle or disempower an existing, unsustainable chain of leverage (Riechers et al., 2022). First, to foster system transformation, sustainable, alternative elements need to exist across systemic depth (parameters-feedbacks-design-intent). In a second step, coherent chains of leverage may be created through strengthening interlinkages between alternative system elements or destabilizing unsustainable ones. For the first step, i.e., to create or strengthen sustainable elements, locally occurring alternative visions for the systems (as alternative system intent), communities of practices or knowledges (as alternative system designs) can be helpful (Bennett et al., 2016). For leverage points to be acted upon, individuals or groups need the agency to intervene in the

system across systemic depth (O'Brien, 2018). Existing sustainable alternative can already exist (in parts) in the studied systems, but may not be widespread or well-known and hence have not yet had the power to transform the broader system in which they operate (Lam et al., 2020) or are being squeezed out by the dominant system. Empowering local initiatives, such as social innovations, new technologies, economic tools, organizations, movements or new behaviours can contribute to the creation of a future that is just, prosperous and sustainable (Bennett et al., 2016).

Specific references:

Bennett, E.M., Solan, M., Biggs, R., McPhearson, T., Norström, A.V., Olsson, P., Pereira, L., Peterson, G.D., Raudsepp-Hearne, C., Biermann, F., Carpenter, S.R., Ellis, E.C., Hichert, T., Galaz, V., Lahsen, M., Milkoreit, M., Martín López, B., Nicholas, K.A., Preiser, R., Vince, G., Vervoort, J.M., Xu, J., 2016. Bright spots: seeds of a good Anthropocene. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 14, 441–448. doi: 10.1002/fee.1309

Lam, D.P.M., Martín-López, B., Wiek, A., Bennett, E.M., Frantzeskaki, N., Horcea-Milcu, A.I., Lang, D.J., 2020. Scaling the impact of sustainability initiatives: a typology of amplification processes. *Urban Transform.* 2, 3. doi: 10.1186/s42854-020-00007-9

O'Brien, K., 2018. Is the 1.5°C target possible? Exploring the three spheres of transformation. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 31, 153–160. doi:10.1016/j.cosust.2018.04.010

Olsson, P., Galaz, V., Boonstra, W.J., 2014. Sustainability transformations: a resilience perspective. *Ecology and Society* 19. doi: 10.5751/ES-06799-190401

Riechers, M., Fischer, J., Manlosa, A.O., Ortiz-Przychodzka, S., Sala, J.E., 2022. Operationalising the leverage points perspective for empirical research. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 57. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2022.101206

Table SM.3.13. Transformation flower approach

3.13 Transformation flower approach	Main approach: Systems Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, structural
<p>The transformation flower approach is a theory of change that builds on and integrates the insights of various transformative change approaches, including transition management (Kemp et al., 2007; Rotmans & Loorbach, 2009), innovation systems¹¹ (Bergek et al., 2008; Planko et al., 2016); sustainable market transformation (Nijhof et al., 2022), small-wins approach (Termeer & Dewulf, 2019), socio-ecological systems (Olsson et al., 2014; Westley et al., 2013) and transformative governance (Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). The transformation flower approach is a holistic, transdisciplinary and practically-relevant approach to achieving transitions/transformations and realizing collective agreements (at multiple governance levels) that are targeted at sustainability, equity and justice (Huntjens et al., 2023; Huntjens & Kemp, 2022).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Bergek, A., Jacobsson, S., Carlsson, B., Lindmark, S., Rickne, A. (2008). Analyzing the functional dynamics of technological innovation systems: a scheme of analysis. <i>Research Policy</i> 37, 407–429.</p> <p>Huntjens, P., & Kemp, R. (2022). The importance of a Natural Social Contract and co-evolutionary governance for sustainability transitions. <i>Sustainability</i>, 14(5), 2976.</p> <p>Huntjens, P.; Rinscheid, A.; Kemp, R.; Van Helvoirt, B.; Aarts, N.; Visseren-Hamakers, I.; van Veen, A.; Hassink, J. (2023) The Transformation Flower Approach for Leveraging Change Towards Multiple Value Creation and Institutional Change. Preprints 2023. https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202307.1539.v1</p> <p>Kemp, R., Loorbach, D., Rotmans, J. (2007). Transition management as a model for managing processes of co-evolution for sustainable development, <i>The International Journal of</i></p>	

¹¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Sustainable Development and World Ecology (special issue on (co)-evolutionary approach to sustainable development) 14: 78-91
Nijhof, A., Wins, A., Argyrou, A., & Chevrollier, N. (2022). Sustainable market transformation: A refined framework for analyzing causal loops in transitions to sustainability. <i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i> 42, 352-361.
Olsson, P., Galaz, V, Boonstra, W.J (2014), Sustainability transformations: A resilience perspective. <i>Ecology and Society</i> 19(4): 1. http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-06799-190
Planko, J., Cramer, J.M., Chappin, M.M., Hekkert, M.P. (2016). Strategic collective system building to commercialise sustainability innovations. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> 2328– 2341
Rotmans, J. and Loorbach, D. (2009). Complexity and Transition Management. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 13: 184-196.
Termeer, C.J.A.M. & Dewulf, A. (2019). A small wins framework to overcome the evaluation paradox of governing wicked problems, <i>Policy and Society</i> , 38(2): 298–314
Visseren-Hamakers, I.J., Razzaque, J., McElwee, P., Turnhout, E., Kelemen, E., Rusch, G.M., Fernandez-Llamazares, A., Chan, I., Lim, M., Islar, M. and Gautam, A.P. (2021). Transformative governance of biodiversity: insights for sustainable development. <i>Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability</i> 53, pp.20-28.
Westley, F.R., Tjornbo, O., Schultz, L., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Crona, B., Bodin, O. (2013). A theory of transformative agency in linked social-ecological systems, <i>Ecology and Society</i> 18(3).
How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework
In particular, the transformation flower approach attends to multiple value creation and institutional change as a dual design challenge and supports social contract formation at multiple levels (global to local) towards a new natural social contract or eco-social contract ¹² as actionable and positive visions, as described in chapter 2. This distinguishes the transformation flower approach from other transformative change approaches. By creating momentum for transformative innovation, the power of incumbents is reduced, as an important condition for achieving transformative change. Lock-in is encountered via path creation policies for promising innovations. The transformation flower approach offers a framework for identifying interventions with stakeholders (participatory leverage point analysis) for achieving multiple value creation. Based on the notion of pathways, it provides a theory of change that aids in working towards desirable futures, involving both incumbents and challengers in an effort to harness untapped yet proximal potentials in a forward-looking way (Huntjens et al., 2023). Like transition management, the transformative flower approach accepts that policies could be adaptive, integrated and forward-looking and engaged with transformation pathways. The attention to multiple value creation and interdependent leverage points inserts greater reflexivity in processes of problem solving and governance, which thus far offer a weak stimulus to transformative change (because they are too much technology-focused). As described in chapter 5, the Transformation Flower Approach helps to identify opportunities to link transformative options (the what), actors (the who) and levers (the how) in dynamic interaction to embark on transformative pathways (Huntjens et al., 2023).
Specific references:
Huntjens, P.; Rinscheid, A.; Kemp, R.; Van Helvoirt, B.; Aarts, N.; Visseren-Hamakers, I.; van Veen, A.; Hassink, J. (2023) The Transformation Flower Approach for Leveraging Change Towards Multiple Value Creation and Institutional Change. Preprints 2023. https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202307.1539.v1

Table SM.3.14. Metatheories of human action

3.14. Metatheories of human action	Main approach: Systems
Many theories from across the social sciences and humanities aim to explain human action. This large number of theories can be overwhelming and hard to navigate. Yet this framework shows that this myriad of theories, at its foundation, is represented by only eight sets of assumptions, or metatheories.	

¹² See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Metatheories reflect the types of variables, timelines, scale of analysis, scale of change, levers, speed of implementation and what types of changes each theory enables. Each of the eight metatheories in this framework represents a unique perspective on human action; each is best suited for different action problems and none are sufficient to address the full range of problems facing humanity today. The synthetic understanding of human action enabled by this framework allows researchers and practitioners to determine which theory or theories may be most applicable for creating transformative change in a particular area. Sustainability solutions may be most effective when they combine insights from multiple metatheories. Nevertheless, most metatheories assume that many variables are static; this widespread assumption prevents the inclusion of feedbacks and interdependent relationships that are crucial to systems analysis and sustainability. The ‘Interdependent Metatheory’, which does account for these feedbacks, may thus be particularly important for understanding transformative change.

Key references:

Eyster, H. N., Satterfield, T., & Chan, K. M. A. (2022). Why people do what they do: an interdisciplinary synthesis of human action theories. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 725–751. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-020422-125351>
 Shove, E. (2010). Beyond the ABC: climate change policy and theories of social change. *Environment and Planning A*, 42(6), 1273–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a42282>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Each of the eight metatheories implies a different cause of change. Two metatheories focus on independent attributes of either 1) individuals or 2) structures. Because they assume that most variables are constant, these first two metatheories may be relatively less useful for understanding the causes of transformative change. Four metatheories focus on needs, including cognitive needs, psychological needs, communal needs and economic needs. The psychological needs metatheory may be particularly useful for creating sustainable changes, since satisfying psychological needs can lead to stable states. One metatheory examines often hidden, systemic factors. This metatheory may be key for unearthing the root causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, such as capitalism¹³, speciesism, anthropocentrism¹³ and particular socio-political systems. The last metatheory examines how multiple factors and action itself, interact to cocreate a practice. This metatheory is essential for navigating the transformative change process because it alone treats all variables as variable and takes nothing for granted. This metatheory is thus key for avoiding surprise consequences of transformative change. A crosscutting combination of these metatheories may present the clearest roadmap for how to transform towards sustainability.

Specific references:

Shove, E. (2014). Putting practice into policy: reconfiguring questions of consumption and climate change. *Contemporary Social Science*, 9(4), 415–429. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21582041.2012.692484>
 Eyster, H. N., Satterfield, T., & Chan, K. M. A. (2022). Why people do what they do: an interdisciplinary synthesis of human action theories. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 725–751. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-020422-125351>

Table SM.3.15. Redesigning theories of change

3.15. Redesigning theories of change	Main approach: Systems
Addressing today’s polycrisis, the set of interacting global crises that include biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, climate change and inequality, demands significant system transformation, yet there is a risk that the idea of transformation becomes simply an ‘empty buzzword’ (Vogel & O’Brien, 2022) because too little is understood about the processes or ‘how’ needed to accomplish transformative change (Bentz et al., 2022). Particular attention needs to be paid to the core values and principles,	

¹³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

mindsets including attitudes and beliefs and integrative approaches guiding significant transformative change, as well as the qualities, attributes and relationships among change stewards that motivate such change (Bentz et al., 2022; Wamsler, 2020). To date, however, rather than linking to the necessary and likely catalytic rather than direct action processes involved in accomplishing systemic change, most of the literature, which is both conceptual and empirical, currently emphasizes: 1) the different types of transition that have taken place, labelled quantum leap, convergent, emergent and gradual; 2) different transition pathways at different scales (multiple levels of analysis), including stability, four types of transition pathways (including, multilevel pathways, innovation strategies, diffusion of those innovations and acceleration to enhance niche innovations) and a sequential process and 3) overcoming a set of barriers to create enabling conditions for change (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Initial stages of organizing for transformation include understanding the socio-ecological adaptive cycle (exploitation, conservation, release and reorganization) and providing different kinds of agency at the different phases of the cycle (Westley et al., 2013). It also means recognizing that there is still a significant need for fully process-based approaches that understand and implement processes that connect, cohere and amplify the work of change agents (Waddock, 2023) to go well beyond ‘blah blah blah’ (Bentz et al., 2022) to engage and achieve deliberate transformation.

Key references:

- Bentz, J., O’Brien, K., & Scoville-Simonds, M. (2022). Beyond “blah blah blah”: Exploring the “how” of transformation. In *Sustainability Science* (2; Vol. 17, Issue 2, pp. 497–506).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01123-0>
- Fazey, I., & Leicester, G. (2022). Archetypes of system transition and transformation: Six lessons for stewarding change. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 91.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102646>
- Vogel, C., & O’Brien, K. (2022). Getting to the heart of transformation. *Sustainability Science*, 17(2), 653–659. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01016-8>
- Waddock, S. (2023). *Catalyzing Transformation: Making System Change Happen*. Business Expert Press.
- Wamsler, C. (2020). Education for sustainability: Fostering a more conscious society and transformation towards sustainability. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-04-2019-0152>
- Westley, F., Tjornbo, O., Schultz, L., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Crona, B., & Bodin, Ö. (2013). A Theory of Transformative Agency in Linked Social-Ecological Systems. *Ecology and Society*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05072-180327>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Getting beyond the ‘blah, blah, blah’ of today’s understandings of system change (Bentz et al., 2022) means avoiding the risk that ‘transformation’ simply becomes another buzzword (Vogel & O’Brien, 2022). It means moving theories of purposeful system transformation towards process-based approaches that help change stewards understand what to do, with whom and how. Most current change frameworks and theories that emphasize: 1) types (descriptions) of system transformation, 2) pathways for how transition, mostly nonintentional, occurs and 3) barriers and enabling conditions or agency of transformation (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Even core archetypes oriented towards systemic change are prone to barriers and obstacles that prevent actual transformative impact, keeping the current system in place, making only incremental changes or failing (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Purposeful systemic change demands that change stewards have significant process-based capabilities, including self-and system-awareness supporting well-being, agency and strong social cohesion (Vogel & O’Brien, 2022; Westley et al., 2013), along with numerous capacities for both inner and outer change, including awareness, connection, insight, purpose and agency (Wamsler et al., 2021). Because transformation is ‘deeply holistic, reflective and relational’ (Vogel & O’Brien, 2022), it also means holistic approaches and processes that are adaptable to multiple, always unique, socio-ecological contexts. Stewardship qualities needed include ‘seeing’ the system as a whole and acting on it as such and bringing actors into new action-oriented coalitions or networks that can work together and separately for greater impact (Westley et al., 2013). Key skills for catalyzing transformative change involve connecting and cohering relevant actors into new, aligned networks that co-emerge shared visions and knowledge, trust and emerging social innovations by capitalizing on relevant windows of

opportunity (Westley et al., 2013) and in amplification processes that involve actually mobilizing and implementing others to create change, yet these processes remain little studied (Waddock, 2023).

Specific references:
 Bentz, J., O'Brien, K., & Scoville-Simonds, M. (2022). Beyond “blah blah blah”: Exploring the “how” of transformation. In *Sustainability Science* (Vol. 17, Issue 2, pp. 497–506).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01123-0>
 Fazey, I., & Leicester, G. (2022). Archetypes of system transition and transformation: Six lessons for stewarding change. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 91.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102646>
 Vogel, C., & O'Brien, K. (2022). Getting to the heart of transformation. *Sustainability Science*, 17(2), 653–659. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01016-8>
 Waddock, S. (2023). *Catalyzing Transformation: Making System Change Happen*. Business Expert Press.
 Wamsler, C., Osberg, G., Osika, W., Herndersson, H., & Mundaca, L. (2021). Linking internal and external transformation for sustainability and climate action: Towards a new research and policy agenda. *Global Environmental Change*, 71.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102373>
 Westley, F., Tjornbo, O., Schultz, L., Olsson, P., Folke, C., Crona, B., & Bodin, Ö. (2013). A Theory of Transformative Agency in Linked Social-Ecological Systems. *Ecology and Society*, 18.
<https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05072-180327>

Table SM.3.16. Value-centred leverage points to catalyze transformative change

<p>3.16. Value-centred leverage points to catalyze transformative change</p>	<p>Main approach: Systems</p> <p>Secondary approach: inner, structure, empowerment</p>
<p>The framework focuses on values-centred leverage points to achieve transformative change towards more just and sustainable futures (Pascual et al., 2023). It emphasizes recognizing and addressing the diverse values associated with nature in order to drive meaningful change (IPBES, 2019b). The framework identifies four key 'values-centred leverage points' that work in synergy to catalyze transformative change. They range from short-term, easier to achieve actions ('shallower leverage points' namely undertaking valuation to recognize the values of nature; and embedding valuation in inclusive decision-making to meaningfully include the diverse values of nature in decision-making) to longer-term, harder to achieve efforts ('deeper leverage points' such as reforming policies, rights and regulations for institutions to embrace the diverse values of nature; and shifting societal norms and goals to mobilize sustainability-aligned values and shift developmental models; (IPBES, 2022). These leverage points are interdependent, whereby jointly activating them entails addressing feedbacks among them, adding them up (from shallow to deep) or cascading down (Pörtner et al., 2023). In summary, the framework emphasizes recognizing and integrating the diverse values of nature into decision-making processes, addressing institutional structures and societal norms and acknowledges the need for power dynamics to shift. It offers a comprehensive approach to driving transformative change for the benefit of both nature and society.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Pascual, U. et al. (2023). Diverse values of nature for sustainability. <i>Nature</i>, 1-11. IPBES, Pascual, U. et al. eds. Summary for Policymakers of the Methodological Assessment of the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. https://zenodo.org/record/6522392 (2022). Pörtner, H. O. et al. Overcoming the coupled climate and biodiversity crises and their societal impacts. <i>Science</i> 380 (2023). IPBES, Díaz, S. et al. (eds) Summary for Policymakers of the Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES Secretariat, 2019).</p>	

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Leverage Point 1: Highlights the need to recognize and account for the diverse values of nature through valuation methods. Such recognition is essential to mobilizing a broader set of specific values of nature and aligning them with sustainability-focused broad values (IPBES, 2022, Chapters 2, 4, 5).

Leverage Point 2: To drive change, information about these values generated through valuation methods can be integrated into inclusive decision-making processes. This may involve existing policy measures (like green taxes) or establishing planning guidelines that consider the many values of nature. (IPBES, 2022, Chapter 4,6; Zafra-Calvo et al., 2020).

Leverage Point 3: A deeper transformation necessitates a reconfiguration of societal structures. This includes reforms to core legal, economic and political institutions, in ways that change what and whose values gain decision-making power in society. These changes aim to shift the power dynamics towards recognizing and incorporating diverse values in decisions (Vatn, 2016).

Leverage Point 4: Transforming societal norms and goals is another vital aspect. This involves altering how society views 'progress' or a 'good life' in the context of relationships with nature (IPBES, 2022, Chapter 5). These changes are inherently transformative and can be achieved through dialogues and participative fora (OECD, 2020).

Transformative change is a multifaceted process involving engagement of the four values-centred leverage points. Fortunately, opportunities for synergies arise, as leverage points are not static; instead, there are interdependencies along the lever's action gradient. Leverage points may be activated in a cumulative way (across the levers), such as when a policy change (e.g., introducing a green tax) triggers a change in social norms over time (e.g., recycling). Values-centred leverage points can also be triggered in the opposite direction (cascading down the levers). For example, the European Common Agricultural Policy shifting the role of agriculture (Hasler et al., 2022).

Specific references:

IPBES, Balvanera, P., Unai, P., Christie, M. & González-Jiménez, D. (eds). Methodological Assessment of the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522522> (2022).

Zafra-Calvo, N. et al. Plural valuation of nature for equity and sustainability: insights from the Global South. *Glob. Environ. Change* 63 (2020).

Vatn, A. *Environmental Governance: Institutions, Policies and Actions* (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2016).

OECD. *Innovative citizen participation and new democratic institutions: catching the deliberative wave*. OECD iLibrary <https://doi.org/10.1787/339306da-en> (2020).

Hasler, B. et al. European agri-environmental policy: evolution, effectiveness and challenges. *Rev. Environ. Econ. Policy* 16, 105–125 (2022).

Table SM.3.17. Regenerative approaches

<p>3.17. Regenerative approaches</p>	<p>Main approach: Systems</p> <p>Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Inner transformation</p>
<p>Conceptualizations of regenerative discourse and praxis vary. A common theme is the need to move beyond sustainability, recognizing ecological damage and designing to produce mutual benefits across socio-technical and ecological systems (Mang & Reed, 2020). Building regenerative capacities is important, i.e., the ability of complex, interconnected, whole living systems to renew themselves. Humans participate as nature, not controlling it (Lyle, 1996; Reed, 2007; Wahl, 2016). Spirituality is infused in relations of</p>	

interbeing and interdependence (Wahl, 2016). Examples: permaculture - an ecological design system integrating human habitats and food production based on Indigenous Peoples' knowledge (Mang & Reed, 2020), biophilic design, biomimicry and living buildings (Hes & Plessis, 2014). In agriculture, holistic land management frameworks (Allan Savory) and ongoing organic restoration of complex living systems based upon healthy soils (Robert Rodale) are important. Definitions include processes (e.g., reducing tillage) and/or outcomes (e.g., improved soil health, increased biodiversity) (Newton et al., 2020). In food systems, regenerative agriculture¹⁴ is a discursive alternative to industrial-productivist systems (Gordon et al., 2022). Agricultural work sits in nested, living systems, with the overall system having capacities to self-renew via continual learning and departures from industrial approaches to varying extents (Gordon et al., 2022), including wholesale shifts to food commoning (Duncan et al., 2020). In landscape design, regenerative principles and values are integrated into development and design frameworks and technologies (Gibbons et al., 2018). Regenerative cities create mutually enhancing relations with any natural systems that sustain them (Girardet, 2015) Regenerative businesses generate value for all stakeholders, while enhancing socio-ecological well-being and human potential (Sandford, 2020). Regenerative economy concepts propose a regenerative form of capitalism (Fullerton, 2015), operating within Earth boundaries (Raworth, 2017) and requiring business, governmental and civic cooperation for natural and social capital regeneration¹⁴ (B. Caniglia, 2020).

Key references:

Duncan, J., M. Carolan, M. and J.S. Wiskerke (2021) 'Regenerating food systems: A socio-ecological approach'. in Duncan, J., Carolan, M. and Wiskerke, J.S. eds., 'Routledge handbook of sustainable and regenerative food systems.' London: Routledge.

Fullerton, J. (2015) 'Regenerative capitalism: How universal principles and patterns will shape our new economy'.

Gibbons, L.V., Cloutier, S.A., Coseo, P.J. and Barakat, A., 2018. Regenerative development as an integrative paradigm and methodology for landscape sustainability. *Sustainability*, 10(6), p.1910.

Girardet, H. (2015) 'Creating regenerative cities.' Routledge. ISBN 9780415724463

Gordon, E., Davila, F. and Riedy, C., 2022. Transforming landscapes and mindscapes through regenerative agriculture. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 39(2), pp.809-826.

Hess, D. and C. Du Plessis (2014) 'Designing for Hope: Pathways to Regenerative Sustainability'. Routledge, London. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315755373>

Lovins, H and B. Cohen (2019) 'The Way Out: Kick-Starting Capitalism to Save Our Economic Ass'.

Mang, P. and B. Reed (2020) 'Regenerative development and design' in 'Sustainable Built Environments' pp 115-141. eds. DOI:10.1007/978-1-0716-0684-1_303

Newton, P., N. Civita, L. Frankel-Goldwater, K. Bartel and C. Johns (2020) 'What Is Regenerative Agriculture? A Review of Scholar and Practitioner Definitions Based on Processes and Outcomes.' *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2020.577723

Raworth, K. (2017) 'Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to think like a 21st Century Economist'.

Reed, Bill (2007) 'Shifting from 'sustainability' to regeneration', *Building Research & Information*. DOI: 10.1080/09613210701475753 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09613210701475753>.

Sandford (2017) 'The Regenerative Business: Redesign Work, Cultivate Human Potential, Achieve Extraordinary Outcomes'.

Tillman Lyle (1994) 'Regenerative design for Sustainable Development'. John Wiley and Sons. ISBN: 0471555827

Wahl, D. C. (2016) 'Designing regenerative cultures.' Triarchy Press Ltd. Axminster, England. ISBN: 978-1-909470-774

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Change in regenerative approaches is intentional, involving active participatory design processes (Manzini, 2015) for co-creation with nature, appropriate human participation as nature and ecological principles e.g., biomimicry, nutrient cycling, soil care (Mang & Reed, 2012; Wahl, 2016). Specific pathways for change include design practice, education, community living (Wahl, 2016). Change is achieved through leverage in systems, facilitated by designs with the wider socio-ecological system in mind, creating conditions for self-renewal, adaptiveness and healthy flourishing of all life through regenerative cultures (Wahl,

¹⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

2016). Regenerative capacities are strengthened across built, cultural and natural environments (Mang & Reed, 2020).

Regenerative design solutions refer specifically to systems of technologies and strategies, generated from place particularities and understandings of whole living systems to manifest their inherent capacity for vitality and evolution (Mang & Reed, 2020). Regenerative development is broader, providing whole understandings of place and stakeholder capability strengthening for maximum systemic leverage so living beings can co-evolve and planetary self-expression in diversity, complexity and creativity (Mang & Reed, 2020). Regenerative development manifests potentials for health, well-being and happiness of all system members, shifts in worldviews, deep inhabitant and practitioner engagement in collaborative processes, attention to supportive infrastructures for mutualistic relations between dynamic system components, value addition across scales and individual and local efforts coordinated within larger scale, regional initiatives to grow wider system regenerative capacity (Gibbons et al., 2018).

Partnership with place (moving from a notion of control to one of cultivation and collaboration) and progressive harmonization (continual improvement of harmony between human and natural systems) can achieve change (Mang & Reed, 2020). Regenerative discourses may support change through bringing together relevant coalitions which share goals and principles, plus translocal organizing and collective learning, but tensions exist between discourses and there are opportunities for greenwashing¹⁵ and co-optation (Gordon et al., 2023).

Specific references:

Gibbons, L.V., Cloutier, S.A., Coseo, P.J. and Barakat, A., 2018. Regenerative development as an integrative paradigm and methodology for landscape sustainability. *Sustainability*, 10(6), p.1910.

Gordon, E., Davila, F. and Riedy, C., 2023. Regenerative agriculture: a potentially transformative storyline shared by nine discourses. *Sustainability Science*, 18(4), pp.1833-1849.

Mang, P. and B. Reed (2020) ‘Regenerative development and design’ in ‘Sustainable Built Environments’ pp 115-141. eds. DOI:10.1007/978-1-0716-0684-1_303

Manzini (2015) emphasizes communities, networks and collaborative action. Manzini, E. (2015) "Design, When Everybody Designs: An Introduction to Design for Social Innovation." MIT press. ISBN: 0262028603

Reed, Bill (2007) 'Shifting from 'sustainability' to regeneration', *Building Research & Information*,35:6,674 — 680 To link to this Article: DOI: 10.1080/09613210701475753 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09613210701475753>.

Wahl, D. C. (2016) ‘Designing regenerative cultures.’ Triarchy Press Ltd. Axminster, England. ISBN: 978-1-909470-774

2. Structural approaches

Table SM.3.18. Karl Polanyi's “The Great Transformation”.....44

Table SM.3.19. Marxist theory45

Table SM.3.20. Rational choice theory.....46

Table SM.3.21. Institutional analysis47

Table SM.3.22. Ecological civilization49

Table SM.3.23. Governmentality50

Table SM.3.24. Degrowth and post-growth studies52

¹⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Table SM.3.25. Strengthening accountability frameworks	53
Table SM.3.26. Biodiversity policy integration	55
Table SM.3.27. Transition management	55
Table SM.3.28. Behavioural economics	57
Table SM.3.29. International political economy	58
Table SM.3.30. Transformative governance	59
Table SM.3.31. Environmental State and the green State	61
Table SM.3.32. Structuration theory	62
Table SM.3.33. Social practice theory	62
Table SM.3.34. Actor network theory	63

Table SM.3.18. Karl Polanyi's “The Great Transformation”

3.18. Karl Polanyi's “The Great Transformation”	Main approach: Structural
<p>In “The Great Transformation”, Karl Polanyi (Polanyi, 2001) argued that when an expanding “self-regulating” market (read as a laissez-faire capitalist) economy takes hold, land (nature), labour and money would become “fictitious commodities”, leading the separation of the economy from society and nature—in his parlance the “first movement”. Pushed to its extreme, this separation could not only ruin societal life but also destroy the entire ecological system. Polanyi distinguishes between regular markets, where goods and services are exchanged and the self-regulating market system, which treats inputs of production as if they were commodities. This institutionalization of land (nature), labour and money as commodities is seen by Polanyi as a defining characteristic of capitalism (Dale, 2016; Devine, 2019). To the extent that the economy becomes a separate and distinct sphere, it would transform all relational aspects into mere cost-and-benefit accounting (Madra & Adaman, 2014). As such, The Great Transformation, in addition to being a fascinating economic history book on capitalism, can equally be seen as a critic of neoliberalism¹⁶ avant la letter (Adaman, 2017).</p>	
<p>Despite these consequences, Polanyi believes that the destruction he describes would never fully occur because the first movement would inevitably trigger a counter-movement of self-protection. This “double movement” would involve humanity re-establishing the integration of the economy into society and nature, thus regulating conditions favourable to market expansion. The tension between market logic and society’s efforts to protect itself from the outcomes of that logic will always exist; and as long as the economy remains detached, humanity cannot establish its dominance. Polanyi calls for a system where the market is no longer self-regulating, even in principle, as it would no longer encompass labour, land and money.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Adaman, F. (2017). “Scaling in Polanyi—Reconsidering the local in the age of neoliberalism”, <i>PArteecipazione e COnflitto; The Open Journal of Sociopolitical Studies</i>.</p> <p>Dale, G. (2016). <i>Karl Polanyi: A life on the left</i>. New York: Columbia University Press.</p> <p>Devine, P. (2019). “Doing Justice to Karl Polanyi”, <i>Capitalism Nature Socialism</i>, 30(2): 276-280.</p> <p>Madra Y.M. and F. Adaman (2014). “Neoliberal Reason and its Forms: Depoliticization through Economization”, <i>Antipode</i>, 46(3): 691-716.</p> <p>Polanyi K. (1944/1957). <i>The Great Transformation: The political and economic origins of our time</i>. Boston: Beacon Press.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>In his book “The Great Transformation”, Polanyi described the shift from a pre-capitalist to a capitalist society in early nineteenth century England. However, he also advocated for a further transformation to</p>	

¹⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

a post-capitalist system, where society would have control over the economy instead of the economy controlling society and nature. Polanyi observed that societies would attempt to embed the economy back into society and nature, but acknowledged that these efforts might well take reactionary forms. Bolshevism and Fascism in the first half of the twentieth century were seen by Polanyi as alternative ways to limit the destructive consequences of unregulated capitalism, although they came at significant societal and ecological costs. Instead, Polanyi supported a form of associational socialism¹⁶ that aimed to consciously subordinate the self-regulating market to a democratic society: “Socialism is, essentially, the tendency inherent in an industrial civilization to transcend the self-regulating market by consciously subordinating it to a democratic society” (Devine, 2019; Polanyi, 2001). His earlier writings from around 1920 provide more details about his preferred economic organizational structure (Adaman & Devine, 2022; Brie & Thomasberger, 2018)

In his influential work, Polanyi focused primarily on nation-States and, to a lesser extent, the global monetary system as the key actors responsible for taking actions (“double movement”) to control the expansion of market forces. However, he did not explicitly explore the potential actions that could be taken at different scales, such as at the local level. More recent literature has expanded on and broadened Polanyi’s vision to incorporate different scales (local, national and global) in today’s world (Adaman, 2017).

Specific references:

Adaman, F. (2017). “Scaling in Polanyi—Reconsidering the local in the age of neoliberalism”, *PArteecipazione e CONflitto; The Open Journal of Sociopolitical Studies*.

Adaman, F. and Devine, P. (2022). “Revisiting the Calculation Debate: A call for a multiscale approach”, *Rethinking Marxism*, 34(2): 162-192.

Brie, T. and Thomasberger, C. eds., (2018). *Karl Polanyi’s Vision of a Socialist Transformation*. Montreal: Black Rose.

Devine, P (2019). “Planning for Freedom”, in *Karl Polanyi’s Vision of a Socialist Transformation*, ed. M. Brie and C. Thomasberger, 209-220. Montreal: Black Rose.

Polanyi K. (1944/1957). *The Great Transformation: The political and economic origins of our time*. Boston: Beacon Press.

Table SM.3.19. Marxist theory

2.2 Marxist theory	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Empowerment
<p>Marxist theory is a theoretical framework for understanding modern capitalist societies and their historicity that builds on Karl Marx’s critique of the political economy of his time which he published in <i>Das Kapital</i> and his lifelong work. Marxist theory is concerned with understanding the exploitation of wage workers, value creation and with deciphering the dynamic of capital accumulation that is a motor of capitalist societies. Marxist theory today has been developed further and broadened, to incorporate e. g. feminism and gender issues (Federici, 2021), to account for racial inequality (Robinson, 2019) and to incorporate more clearly analyses of the metabolism between society and nature (Foster, 1999). While Marx has not specifically dealt with the problem of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, the environment is present in his original work, especially in his concept of ecological crises that originate from a metabolic rift¹⁷ in pre-capitalist society-nature-metabolisms created by industrial capitalism. Political economic research is only just beginning to address the problem of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and policies for protecting biodiversity from a political economic perspective (S. Ghosh, 2015). Yet, according to Marxist theory, the capitalist organization of the economy is a root cause of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline since capitalist profit making involves the production of environmental externalities (Saave, 2021), such as biodiversity loss and nature’s decline or global warming.</p>	

¹⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Key references:

Ghosh, Soumitra. 2015. Capitalisation of Nature: Political Economy of Forest/Biodiversity Offsets. In: Economic and Political Weekly, Vol. 50, No. 16, pp. 53-60.

Federici, Silvia. 2012. Aufstand aus der Küche. Reproduktionsarbeit in globalen Kapitalismus und die unvollendete feministische Revolution. Münster: edition assemblage.

Foster, John Bellamy. 1999. Marx's Theory of Metabolic Rift: Classical Foundations for Environmental Sociology. In: American Journal of Sociology, Vol. 105, No. 2, pp. 366-405.

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Saave, Anna. 2022. Einverleiben und Externalisieren. Zur Innen-Außen-Beziehung der kapitalistischen Produktionsweise. Bielefeld: transcript.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Deliberate transformative change in Marxist theory

People have derived from Marxist theory many different clues for how deliberate transformative change should occur, including large projects such as socialist revolution or smaller scale strategies that involve commoning or autonomous organization. Marx himself envisioned to provide the working class with knowledge about how this class is exploited under capitalism, which would inspire a class consciousness and result in workers reclaiming the means of production and reclaiming power to organize the economy in non-exploitative ways. This change is intentional because it is assumed that the working class intentionally takes control over the production process. With the broadening of Marxist theory, this understanding of change has been broadened as well. It now includes commoning, for example of resources and care responsibilities, which is a strategy inspired by materialist feminism (Dalla Costa & James, 1973). Intentional change also includes degrowing the economy as an antidote to continued capital accumulation and resource use, which inspired by the anti-capitalist strands of the degrowth movement (Schmelzer et al., 2022). Ecologically oriented Marxist thinkers today also call for stopping extractivist profit making (Svampa, 2015) that deteriorates ecosystems worldwide but most importantly in capitalist peripheries, thereby contributing to the colonial continuities in the appropriation of nature. The broadening of Marxist theory has led the focus away from solely paying attention to the working class as actors of intentional change and getting into view also unpaid workers, e.g., in the household and in peasant economies (Mies, 1986). Feminist materialist thinkers have significantly contributed to Marxist understandings of intentional change that go beyond the sphere of production, thus including reproduction and the actors responsible for upholding reproductivity, both with regards to humans and nature (Barca, 2020).

Specific references:

Barca, Stefania. 2020. Forces of Reproduction: Notes for a Counter-Hegemonic Anthropocene. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Dalla Costa, Mariarosa and Selma James. 1973. Die Macht der Frauen und der Umsturz der Gesellschaft. Berlin: Merve.

Mies, Maria. 1986. Patriarchy and Accumulation on a World Scale: Women in the International Division of Labour. London: Zed Books.

Schmelzer, Matthias, Vetter andrea and Aaron Vansintjan. 2022. The Future is Degrowth. A Guide to a World Beyond Capitalism. New York: Verso.

Svampa, Maristella. 2015. Commodities Concensus. Neoextractivism and enclosure of the commons in Latin America. South Atlantic Quarterly 114(1): 65–82.

Table SM.3.20. Rational choice theory

3.20. Rational choice theory	Main approach: Structures
	Secondary approach: Science & Technology

Rational choice theory assumes that individuals are rational in their choices and actions. According to this theory, rational individual behaviour in markets and social choice processes includes the comparison of costs and benefits of taking an action such that individuals or societies try to receive the highest benefit at the least possible cost. Bounded by their preferences, individuals are assumed to act on their free will and consistently based on the premise of individual utility maximization and self-interest. The repercussions of the theory can be traced in organizational theory, game theory, Coase theorem, utilitarianism and so on.

Key references:

Foundations of social theory / James S. Coleman. Cambridge, Mass. : Harvard University Press, 1990.
 Rational choice / edited by Jon Elster. Oxford : B. Blackwell, 1986.
 Decision-making : descriptive, normative and prescriptive interactions / edited by David E. Bell, Howard Raiffa and Amos Tversky. Cambridge [Cambridgeshire] ; New York : Cambridge University Press, 1990.
 Notes on the theory of choice / David M. Kreps. Boulder : Westview Press, 1988.
 Microeconomic Theory / Andreu Mas-Colell, Michael D. Whinston and Jerry R. Green. Oxford University Press

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

According to this theory, deliberate transformative change may occur when preferences of individuals change or when the costs and/or benefits of a certain decision change. Most economic valuation studies and environmental assessments assume that a transformation or a change regarding an environmental outcome can happen if the rationality principle is fulfilled. For instance, according to the Coase theorem, bargaining and negotiation will lead to an efficient outcome in solving the problem of market externalities in the case of low transaction costs. Negotiation is supposed to take place on terms that accurately reflect the full costs and under perfect information and equal market power amongst the parties. The theorem is proposed as a solution to transform negative externalities into positive externalities. However, relevant literature suggests that in many decision-making processes, factors such as cognitive limitations, behavioural biases and distribution of decision-making over actors and in time play an important role in transformation as well (Kørnøv & Thissen, 2000).

Specific references:

Pouta E., Rekola M., Kuuluvainen J., Li C-Z., Tahvonon O. (2002). Willingness to pay in different policy-planning methods: insights into respondents' decision-making processes. *Ecological Economics* 40: 295–311. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009\(01\)00274-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(01)00274-9)
 Plott C.R. (1996). Rational individual behaviour in markets and social choice processes: the discovered preference hypothesis. In: Arrow K.J., Colomatto E., Perlman M., Schmidt C. (ed.) *The rational foundations of economic behaviour: proceedings of the IEA conference held in Turin, Italy*, St. Martin's Press, New York. p. 225–250
 Fuster G, Schuhmacher M, Domingo JL. Cost-benefit analysis as a tool for decision making in environmental projects. Application to a reduction of dioxin emissions in Tarragona Province, Spain. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2004;11(5):307-12. doi: 10.1007/BF02979644. PMID: 15506633.
 Naidoo R, Ricketts TH. Mapping the economic costs and benefits of conservation. doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.0040360. PMID: 17076583; PMCID: PMC1629040.
 L. Kørnøv, W. Thissen (2000). Rationality in decision- and policy-making: implications for strategic environmental assessment. *Impact Assess. Proj. Apprais.*, 18 (3), pp. 191-200, doi: 10.3152/147154600781767402

Table SM.3.21. Institutional analysis

3.21. Institutional analysis	Main approach: Structural
	Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Systems, Empowerment

Institutional analysis, rooted in new institutionalism, is a methodological approach that offers invaluable insights into comprehending and addressing natural resource governance issues (Cumming et al., 2020). This interdisciplinary field, primarily advanced by Elinor Ostrom and her colleagues, delves into the intricate web of rules, norms and shared strategies that mold human behaviours (Ostrom, 2009b).

Central to institutional analysis is its challenge to the conventional wisdom that governance solutions can be solely derived from the State or market. The groundbreaking work of Elinor Ostrom and her collaborators revealed a richness in the diverse institutions that co-evolved to successfully govern common-pool resources. Moving beyond conventional approaches towards community-based and polycentric institutions have played a crucial role in fostering sustainable resource management practices and especially in shifting power towards local and/or historically marginalized communities (Nagendra & Ostrom, 2012).

At the core of institutional analysis lies the Institutional Analysis and Development Framework, which serves as a cornerstone of this field. This framework provides a conceptual structure for comprehending the generation of rules, norms and shared strategies and how they exert influence over human decision-making within specific action arenas (Ostrom, 2009b).

A pivotal concept within institutional analysis is polycentric governance, which encompasses a complex interplay of entities, including governments and non-governmental organizations, in the creation and maintenance of institutions (Morrison et al., 2023). Although sometimes employing a polycentric lens, empirical institutional literature infrequently considered multiple levels dimensions with the richest case studies focused on the community levels. Contemporary institutional biodiversity research has shifted to multi-level institutional analyses that focus on the local to international. This evolution provides a more holistic understanding of governance structures necessary to transform for the current biodiversity challenges.

Institutional analysts' examination of rules, norms and shared strategies, alongside exploration of institutional change within multi-level and polycentric governance systems provides a foundation for understanding how to shape human behaviour and more sustainably govern biodiversity (Dietz et al., 2003).

Key references:

- Cumming, G. S., Epstein, G. anderics, J. M., Apetrei, C. I., Baggio, J., Bodin, Ö., ... & Weible, C. M. (2020). Advancing understanding of natural resource governance: a post-Ostrom research agenda. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 44, 26-34.
- Dietz, T., Ostrom, E., & Stern, P. C. (2003). The struggle to govern the commons. *science*, 302(5652), 1907-1912.
- Morrison, Tiffany H., Örjan Bodin, Graeme S. Cumming, Mark Lubell, Ralf Seppelt, Tim Seppelt and Christopher M. Weible. "Building blocks of polycentric governance." *Policy Studies Journal* (2023).
- Nagendra, H., & Ostrom, E. (2012). Polycentric governance of multifunctional forested landscapes. *International Journal of the Commons*, 6(2).
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge university press.
- Ostrom, E. (2009). *Understanding institutional diversity*. Princeton university press.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Deliberate transformative change, viewed through an institutional lens, manifests through several critical mechanisms. Key to this process is "institutional navigation," whereby actors manoeuvre through existing institutional landscapes to shape governance systems and drive change (Lubell & Morrison, 2021). This navigation includes adapting to, co-learning with and co-producing institutions that are more responsive to the needs and preferences of relevant communities and constituencies (Wyborn, 2015).

Institutional scholarship also may address epistemic diversity, procedural justice and recognitional justice to facilitate novel governance arrangements that foster more just, sustainable and equitable systems (York & Yazar, 2022). Historically marginalized communities and peoples with diverse knowledge systems and priorities have been absent, systematically excluded, from biodiversity

governance structures - in turn reproducing inequity and also fueling biodiversity loss and nature's decline.

In the context of biodiversity conservation, institutional analysis provides insights into the root human causes of biodiversity challenges and offers potential pathways that facilitate institutional change through collective action and environmental justice. The path to deliberate transformative change within biodiversity governance involves acknowledging historical exclusions and striving for meaningful inclusivity. This transformation seeks to incorporate individuals who have been marginalized, broadening the scope of biodiversity governance discussions to include diverse preferences, knowledge systems and approaches. In doing so, it challenges and redefines the very concept of biodiversity itself (Kashwan et al., 2021).

Recognizing and addressing power imbalances and injustices within governance, particularly concerning recognition and procedural justice (York & Yazar, 2022), are pivotal steps in addressing pressing biodiversity concerns. Transformation also emphasizes the need to question the dominant global economic system in order to examine alternative approaches to biodiversity management (Kashwan et al., 2021).

The Inuit Circumpolar Council's shift towards food sovereignty, self-governance and rejection (for example) of single-species management, underscores the potential of localized, multi-level approaches that transcend traditional harvest management approaches (Inuit Circumpolar Council Alaska, 2020). Ultimately, deliberate transformative change involves redesigning institutions, confronting power asymmetry and addressing injustice.

Specific references:

Inuit Circumpolar Council - Alaska, (2020). Food sovereignty and self-governance: Inuit role in managing Arctic marine resources.

Kashwan, P., Mudaliar, P., Foster, S. R., & Clement, F. (2021). Reimagining and governing the commons in an unequal world: A critical engagement. *Current Research in Environmental Sustainability*, 3.

Lubell, M., & Morrison, T. H. (2021). Institutional navigation for polycentric sustainability governance. *Nature Sustainability*, 4(8), 664-671.

Wyborn, C. (2015). Co-productive governance: a relational framework for adaptive governance. *Global Environmental Change*, 30, 56-67.

York, A., & Yazar, M. (2022). Leveraging shadow networks for procedural justice. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 57.

Table SM.3.22. Ecological civilization

3.22. Ecological civilization	Main approach: Structural
<p>Secondary approach: Systems, Science & Technology</p> <p>Ecological civilization¹⁸ framework is a comprehensive and systematic regulation and ideological system that encourages coexistence between human and nature, among human beings and their relation to the society (Ma & Wei, 2021; Xue et al., 2023). Its root lies in ancient Chinese Taoist philosophy of the “Unity of Man and Nature”. It advocates the harmonious relationships between socioeconomic development and environmental protections, including biodiversity conservation (Ma & Wei, 2021). It evolves from philosophical and academic concepts to practical endeavours, especially after 2007 when it became the fundamental framework to build a moderately prosperous society in China (Xue et al., 2023). It manifests in various ways including developing environmental laws and policies, encouraging green technological innovations, protecting natural ecosystems and conserving biodiversity, as well as involving multiple stakeholders in decision-making (IPBES, 2019b; Ma & Wei, 2021). Under the umbrella of the framework, the ideas of “lucid waters and lush mountains are invaluable assets” and “mountains, rivers, forests, fields, lakes, grass and deserts are a community of life” are proposed to foster ecological civilization constructions (Geall & Ely, 2018).</p>	

¹⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Key references:

- Geall, S. and Ely, A., 2018. Narratives and pathways towards an ecological civilization in contemporary China. *The China Quarterly*, 236, 1175-1196.
- IPBES (2019): Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. E. S. Brondizio, J. Settele, S. Díaz and H. T. Ngo (editors). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 1148 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>
- Ma, K. and Wei, F., 2021. Ecological civilization: a revived perspective on the relationship between humanity and nature. *National Science Review*, 8(7).
- Ma, T., Hu, Y., Wang, M., Yu, L. and Wei, F., 2021. Unity of Nature and Man: a new vision and conceptual framework for the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. *National Science Review*, 8(7).
- Xue, B., Han, B., Li, H., Gou, X., Yang, H., Thomas, H. and Stückrad, S., 2023. Understanding ecological civilization in China: From political context to science. *Ambio*, 1-15.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

The ecological civilization framework has been adopted to guide activities from central to local governments. An important national level practice is the Ecological Redline Policy (Jiang et al., 2019) which establish regulatory targets at the landscape level in a spatially explicit way to protect ecosystem functions and their services to people. A series of initiatives and plans were formulated, such as national park establishment, main function-oriented zoning and nature reserve conservation, in light of ecological civilization framework. These policies and plans play critical roles in attainments of various sustainable development goals, such as poverty reduction, environmental protection, safeguarding ecological integrity and improving human health (Bryan et al., 2018). Another nationwide practice is the establishment of eco-civilization construction demonstration zones. It is reported that during 2017 and 2022, 462 zones and 187 practical innovation bases were approved in China (Zhang & Fu, 2023). Some of these zones focus on ecological restoration and improving livelihood of local residents, e.g., the Loess Plateau (Fu et al., 2017). Some emphasize the “end-of-pipe” treatment of environmental pollution, such as “Dongguan pollution treatment model” (Xue et al., 2023). Some are dedicated to develop natural resource products, eco-industrialization and eco-tourism (Xue et al., 2023). Some explore technical innovations, especially in terms of improving resource efficiency and reducing waste charges. For these demonstration zones, a new metric system for evaluating the performance of local officers is developed and a “chief executive accountability system” is developed to manage natural resources in an integrated and coordinated way (Gu et al., 2020). It is noting that these policies, plans and demonstrations evolve in an adaptive and iterative way and they may generate diverse benefits for sustainable development goals and biodiversity conservation.

Specific references:

- Bryan, B.A., Gao, L., Ye, Y., Sun, X., Connor, J.D., Crossman, N.D., Stafford-Smith, M., Wu, J., He, C., Yu, D., Liu, Z., Li, A., Huang, Q., Ren, H., Deng, X., Zheng, H., Niu, J., Han, G., Hou, X. 2018. China’s response to a national land-system sustainability emergency. *Nature* 559, 193-204.
- Fu, B., Wang, S., Liu, Y., Liu, J., Liang, W. and Miao, C., 2017. Hydrogeomorphic ecosystem responses to natural and anthropogenic changes in the Loess Plateau of China. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 45, pp.223-243.
- Gu, Y., Wu, Y., Liu, J., Xu, M. and Zuo, T., 2020. Ecological civilization and government administrative system reform in China. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 155, p.104654
- Jiang, B., Bai, Y., Wong, C.P., Xu, X. and Alatalo, J.M., 2019. China’s ecological civilization program—Implementing ecological redline policy. *Land Use Policy*, 81, 111-114.
- Zhang, J. and Fu, B., 2023. Eco-civilization: A complementary pathway rooted in theory and practice for global sustainable development. *Ambio*, 1-13.

Table SM.3.23. Governmentality

3.23. Governmentality	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Science & Technology
<p>Drawing on his observations of the change in statecraft in 18th-century Western Europe, Foucault redefines “government” as “a form of activity aiming to shape, guide, or affect the conduct of some person or persons,” i.e., “the conduct of conduct” (Burchell et al., 1991). He refers to the exercise of government as “governmentality”. Environmental social scientists have developed Foucault’s ideas of government and governmentality to understand the various ways through which pro-environmental behaviours are shaped. By combining governmentality with environmental governance—referred to as “environmentality”—Agrawal (2005) and others use governmentality to examine how technologies of government produce “environmental subjects” (Dressler, 2014; P. West, 2006). Critical political ecologists relate environmental governmentality with the neoliberalization of environmental regulation, developing the concepts of “green governmentality” (Rutherford, 2011) “neoliberal governmentality” (Fletcher, 2010). They argue that recent market-based environmental schemes such as payment for ecosystem services, ecotourism and carbon offsetting are designed to promote market-centred understandings of nature and consumption-based environmental behaviours.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Agrawal, A., 2005. <i>Environmentality: Technologies of Government and the Making of Subjects</i>. Duke University Press, Durham, NC.</p> <p>Burchell, G., Foucault, M., Gordon, C. and Miller, P., 1991. <i>The Foucault Effect: Studies in Governmentality (with two Lectures by and an Interview with Michel Foucault)</i>, University of Chicago Press, Chicago.</p> <p>Fletcher, R., 2010. Neoliberal environmentality: towards a poststructuralist political ecology of the conservation debate. <i>Conservation and Society</i> 8 (3), 171–181.</p> <p>Rutherford, S., 2011. <i>Governing the Wild: Ecotours of Power</i>. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, MN.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Governmentality serves as an analytical tool for examining the creation and operation of environmental governance. From a governmentality perspective, the regime of governance consists of programmes, strategies and subjects. The practice of government entails specific “programmes” (e.g., ecotourism, payment for ecosystem services) that aim to transform human behaviours. These programmes are mediated through an array of “technologies of intervention” including sovereign (e.g., rules, penalties), disciplinary (e.g., norms) and regulatory mechanisms. The practice of governmentality then produces “environmental subjects” who are willing to think and act in accordance with the mentality of government. Recent studies on governmentality draw attention to the complex operation of power in governmentalities, which diversifies the forms and processes of environmental governmentality projects in practice. (Fletcher & Breitling, 2012) identifies the simultaneous operation of multiple forms of governmentalities—sovereign, disciplinary, neoliberal and truth forms of governmentality—within the same mode of environmental governance, which he refers to as “multiple governmentalities”. Others are concerned with the site-specific historical, political and social conditions under which governmentalities are being operated (Bluwstein, 2017; Choi, 2022; Dressler, 2014; Fletcher & Breitling, 2012; Roth & Dressler, 2012). These authors are particularly interested in identifying various and sometimes unanticipated, changes to the intervening strategies and subject positions, not all of which neatly align with the plan of the governors. This renewed thinking of governmentalities as situated and variegated processes provides a useful framework for understanding and designing biodiversity-related environmental governance for transformative changes.</p>	

Specific references:

- Cortes-Vazquez, J. A. & Ruiz-Ballesteros, E., 2018. Practising nature: A phenomenological rethinking of environmentality in natural protected areas in Ecuador and Spain. *Conservation and Society*, 16, 232–242.
- Dressler, W., 2014. Green governmentality and swidden decline on Palawan Island. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers* 39 (2), 250–264.
- Fletcher, R., Breitling, J., 2012. Market mechanism or subsidy in disguise? Governing payment for environmental services in Costa Rica. *Geoforum* 43 (3), 402–411.
- West, P., 2006. *Conservation is Our Government Now: The Politics of Ecology in Papua New Guinea*. Duke University Press, Durham, NC.

Table SM.3.24. Degrowth and post-growth studies

3.24. Degrowth and post-growth studies	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Systems
<p>A sustainable society equitably meets everybody’s needs within the ecological limits of the planet. Economic growth (i.e., gross domestic product growth) has become a central goal and measure of success for societies around the world. However, economic growth has been driving biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and climate change, because all economic activity needs energy and materials and results in some amount of pollution. There is no evidence that economic growth can be sufficiently decoupled from environmental pressures. Furthermore, the last few decades of global economic growth has left the poor in poverty and made the rich richer. Thus, addressing today’s social and environmental crises implies fundamental changes to socio-economic systems, to equitably meet needs without economic growth. This entails re-orienting societal goals away from economic growth to material sufficiency. Communities that are currently overconsuming need to reduce their consumption so that deprived communities can increase their consumption to a level of sufficiency.</p> <p>Degrowth scholarship and degrowth policy recommendations are diverse. However, there is a high level of consensus on the following aspects. Policies could shift from focusing on gross domestic product to focus instead on public health indicators (including ecological functioning). An increased sharing and swapping of existing resources can meet more needs with less impact. Production, consumption and work could decrease. Accordingly, businesses and markets would shift away from for-profit structures. For-profit markets tend to drive overconsumption, growth, inequality, market concentration and political capture, because their legal purpose is to enrich private owners. Instead, not-for-profit businesses and markets can complement community provisioning, because they treat profit only as a means to achieve social benefit. All of this can result in society’s limited resources (including the surplus) going to where they are needed most, rather than accumulating in the hands of the wealthy. This can increase the quality of life for most people within ecological limits.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Hickel, J., 2019. <i>Degrowth: A Theory of Radical Abundance</i>. <i>real-world economics review</i> 54–68.</p> <p>Hinton, J.B., 2021. <i>Relationship-to-Profit: A Theory of Business, Markets and Profit for Social Ecological Economics</i> (Doctoral dissertation). Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden.</p> <p>Jackson, T., 2011. <i>Prosperity without Growth: Economics for a Finite Planet</i>, Reprint edition. ed. Routledge, London ; Washington, DC.</p> <p>Kallis, G., 2018. <i>Degrowth</i>. Agenda Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne.</p> <p>Parrique, T., 2020. <i>The political economy of degrowth</i>. Université Clermont Auvergne, Clermont-Ferrand, France.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Degrowth scholarship encompasses a range of theories and frameworks of how deliberate transformative change occurs. One approach is a synthesis of institutional theory and systems</p>	

thinking¹⁹. Institutions are broadly defined as social rules. Institutional theory describes how formal institutions (e.g., laws, property rights, contracts) and informal institutions (e.g., beliefs, norms, logics) influence each other over time, by either reinforcing or undermining the other to some degree. Both formal and informal institutions shape actors' behaviour, by guiding and constraining their behaviour. (An actor can be an individual or a group of people, like an organization.) Actors, in turn, can shape the institutions around them, by accommodating, resisting, or changing these social rules. It is through this triad of actors' agency, formal institutions and informal institutions that societies change over time. A systems thinking lens enhances this understanding of transformative change by identifying key feedback loops that are either keeping the system structure in place or creating opportunities for change (e.g., leverage points). When key institutions in society begin to contradict each other (institutional misalignment), there are opportunities for intentional change. For instance, when society's values increasingly support environmental protection but policy goals and legal frameworks still encourage overconsumption, the resulting tension creates the space for transformative degrowth actions.

Policymakers can shift from monetary goals to social and ecological ones (e.g., Happy Planet Index, public health indexes). They can redistribute wealth via taxes and reparations. They can implement a shorter work week. They can shift subsidies, tax benefits, public procurement and seed-funding away from for-profit organizations to the social economy (e.g., social enterprises, consumer cooperatives, foundation-owned businesses, etc.).

Citizens can identify the social economy around them and shift their consumption accordingly. They can create networks of sharing and swapping to maximize the use of existing goods. For-profit companies can shift to not-for-profit legal structures (e.g., Patagonia, Steward Ownership). Not-for-profit companies can focus more on ecological impacts (e.g., Saltå Kvarn, Blue Star Recyclers).

Social movements (incl. social justice and environmental) can collaborate to raise awareness and push for the above-actions (e.g., Degrowth Movement, Well-being Economy Alliance) and hold leaders accountable for implementing the above actions.

Specific references:

Hinton, J.B., 2021. Relationship-to-Profit: A Theory of Business, Markets and Profit for Social Ecological Economics. Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden. (see pages 21- 30; 94-99)

Meadows, D.H., 1999. Leverage Points: Places to Intervene in a System. Hartland, VT: The Sustainability Institute.

Meadows, D.H., 2008. Thinking in Systems: A Primer. Edited by Diana Wright. White River Junction: Chelsea Green Publishing.

North, D., 1990. Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Scott, W. R., 2014. Institutions and Organizations: Ideas, Interests and Identities. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Table SM.3.25. Strengthening accountability frameworks

3.25. Strengthening accountability frameworks	Main approach: Structural
<p>Broadly understood, accountability entails giving an account of one's actions or being answerable for one's actions and behaviours (Bovens, 2007, 2010). Accountability is fundamentally a relational concept: one set of actors is accountable to another for adhering to an agreed standard of behaviour. This also implies a judgement about whether the standard of behaviour is being met and sanctions or penalties for non-adherence. Only when each of these elements are present can a relationship of accountability be said to exist. Thus, both the concept and actual practice of accountability can be</p>	

¹⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

broken down into four elements: 1) a relational element, linking those who are held accountable to those who have the right to hold to account; 2) a normative element, that is, a standard of behavioural defined with sufficient precision; 3) a decision element, that is, a judgment by those holding others to account about whether an expected standard of behaviour has been met; and 4) a behavioural element that allows the account-holder to sanction non-adherence to the standard by those being held accountable. All four elements combined secure meaningful accountability of key actors, both public and private, in order to further desired sustainability transformations (Biermann & Gupta, 2011). Furthermore, transformative change entails that a diverse array of public and private actors need to be accountable to each other for their sustainability performance or non-performance. This need for accountability permeates all levels of sustainability governance, from the local to the global. It includes a need for accountability of public regulation and authorities, as well as novel types of private governance arrangements within and beyond the nation-State.

Key references:

Biermann, Frank and Gupta, Aarti. 2011. Accountability and Legitimacy in Earth System Governance: a Research Framework. *Ecological Economics*, 70, 1856-1864.
 Bovens, Marks. 2007. Analyzing and assessing accountability: A Conceptual Framework, *European Law Journal*, 13, 4, 447-468.
 Fox, Jonathan. 2007. The Uncertain Relationship between Transparency and Accountability. *Development in Practice* 17, 663-671.
 Gupta Aarti and Michael Mason (eds.) (2014) *Transparency in Global Environmental Governance: Critical Perspectives*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
 Keohane, Robert (2006) Accountability in world politics. *Scandinavian Political Studies* 29 (2), 75-87.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

In operationalizing meaningful accountability relationships as a key means to fuel transformative change, an important question is how to secure the consent of those who are to be held accountable and who has the right to hold whom to account. This is a crucial test for the possibility to realize transformative change and is related to an important distinction between what Keohane (2006) calls internal and external accountability. In internal accountability, those holding to account and those to be held accountable are institutionally linked to each other, making this form of accountability relatively easier to secure than external accountability, where those impacted by the behaviours of others they may wish to hold accountable may not be directly (or institutionally) linked.

Another important element of accountability relationships—and an oft-assumed precondition for accountability relationships to drive transformative change—is the transparency of sustainability governance processes and outcomes (Fox, 2007; Hood, 2010). Transparency is widely assumed to be critically important to securing more accountability, yet this means that such transparency shines a light on those most responsible for unsustainable outcomes. Thus, transparency can only further accountability if information disclosure is actionable and meaningful and does not place further burden on, or seek to control, those already disenfranchised, (Gupta & Mason, 2014; Gupta & van Asselt, 2019).

Finally, accountability is also a core element of deliberative democracy, which focuses on questions of inclusion and exclusion in transformation processes (Lehtonen, 2005). Who decides who is to be included in diverse processes of transformative change, especially those designed to further accountability of key actors? Designing meaningful forms of accountability that operationalize all four key pillars of the accountability relationship in practice is crucial to realizing transformative change, especially given the vast discrepancies of wealth and power that currently drive unsustainable behaviours (Park & Kramarz, 2019).

Specific references:

Bovens, Marks. 2010. Two Concepts of Accountability: Accountability as a Virtue and as a Mechanism, *West European Politics*, 33:5, 946-967.
 Gupta, A. & H. van Asselt (2019) Transparency in Multilateral Climate Politics: Furthering (or Distracting from Accountability? *Regulation & Governance*, 13:1, 18-34.

Hood, C. (2010) Accountability and Transparency: Siamese Twins, Matching Parts, Awkward Couple? *West European Politics*, 33, 989-1009.

Markku Lehtonen, 2005. OECD Environmental Performance Review Programme: Accountability (f)or Learning? *Evaluation* 11(2): 169–188.

Park, Susan and Theresa Kramarz, eds. (2019). *Global Environmental Governance and the Accountability Trap*. Cambridge (MA): MIT Press.

Table SM.3.26. Biodiversity policy integration

3.26. Biodiversity policy integration	Main approach: Structural
<p>Biodiversity policy integration (also referred to as ‘biodiversity mainstreaming’) refers to the incorporation of biodiversity considerations into policies, plans and practices of public and private actors in sectors that rely on and/or impact biodiversity, such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, mining and spatial planning (Huntley, 2014). Biodiversity policy integration aims to avoid or at least mitigate trade-offs between biodiversity and sectoral objectives and to promote synergies (think of approaches such as eco-engineering, nature-based solutions, building with nature and agroecology (Persson et al., 2018).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Huntley, B.J. (2014), Good news from the South: Biodiversity mainstreaming – A paradigm shift in conservation? <i>South African Journal of Science</i>, 110 (9/10). http://doi.org/10.1590/sajs.2014/a0080</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Because of its explicit aim “to target the underlying driving forces, rather than merely symptoms, of environmental degradation” (Persson et al., 2018; Zinngrebe et al., 2022), biodiversity policy integration has transformative potential. Examples of driving forces include high-input/high-output agriculture, monocultures in forestry, locational choices in urban planning, etc. Deliberate transformative change is strived after via a variety of biodiversity policy integration instruments and strategies, ranging from public commitment to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity, which has biodiversity mainstreaming as an explicit focus, to concrete interventions such as ‘no net loss of biodiversity’ regulations, financial incentive schemes such as payments for ecosystem services and green procurement and communicative instruments such as eco-labels. Insight into enablers of and barriers to biodiversity policy integration in terms of outputs, outcomes and impacts is still in its infancy. Recent work takes a layered approach to analyzing enablers and barriers, distinguishing between enablers and barriers that are observable in concrete biodiversity policy integration cases (e.g., a lack of resources or collaboration) and more structural factors (in particular, the institutional setting, including the absence or presence of mechanisms to hold specific actor(s) accountable for biodiversity action; a culture of collaboration between public and private actors within a policy sector; the regular evaluation and reconsideration of policies; and, more generally, the flexibility or rigidity -‘lock-in’- of institutions).</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Persson, Å., H. Runhaar, S. Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, G. Mullally, D. Russel and A. Widmer (2018), Editorial: Environmental Policy Integration: taking stock of policy practice in different contexts, <i>Environmental Science and Policy</i>, 85, pp. 113-115.</p>	

Table SM.3.27. Transition management

3.27. Transition management	Main approach: Structural
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	Secondary approach: Science & technology, Systems
<p>Transition management is a prescriptive model for governance for sustainable development based on complexity theory and the goal-oriented modulation of dynamics. It is oriented at changing (sectoral) systems of production and consumption, through “guided processes of variation and selection, the outcomes of which act as stepping stones for further change” (Kemp et al., 2007). The underlying premise is that “a better understanding of the dynamics of complex, adaptive systems provides insight into the opportunities, limitations and conditions under which it is possible to influence such systems” (Rotmans & Loorbach, 2009). Examples of system innovation are: an energy system based on renewable energy, low-carbon transport (motorized and non-motorized) and regenerative agriculture based on agroecology. Such changes involve the nurturing of alternatives and pressures on regime-actors. Transition management seeks to make “the future more clearly manifest in current decisions, by adopting longer time frames, explore alternative trajectories (...) in critical societal subsystems”; foster collaborative networks for particular innovations and experiments with novel practices and technologies and allow “a diversity of innovations (‘variation’) and competition among different approaches (‘selection’) to fulfill societal needs”(Meadowcroft, 2009). The model of transition management was used by the Dutch government for promoting low-carbon energy innovation for a number of years (Kemp, 2010), but criticized for being functionalist and technocratic (democracy deficit), making too little use of environmental assessment, paying too little attention to distributional consequences & justice and acknowledging the (conflict-ridden) politics of policy design (Voß et al., 2009).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Kemp, R., Loorbach, D., Rotmans, J. (2007). Transition management as a model for managing processes of co-evolution for sustainable development, <i>The International Journal of Sustainable Development and World Ecology</i> (special issue on (co)-evolutionary approach to sustainable development) 14: 78-91</p> <p>Rotmans, J. and Loorbach, D. (2009). Complexity and Transition Management. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i>, 13: 184-196.</p> <p>Meadowcroft, J.. (2009). What about the politics? <i>Sustainable Development, Transition Management and Long-Term Energy Transitions. Policy Sciences</i> 42: 323-340. 10.1007/s11077-009-9097-z.</p> <p>Kemp, R. (2010) The Dutch Energy Transition Approach, <i>International Economics and Economic Policy</i>, 7: 291–316.</p> <p>Voß, J.-P., Smith, A., Grin, J. (2009). Designing long-term policy: Rethinking transition management. <i>Policy Sciences</i> 42: 275–302.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Transition management offers a framework for the choice of instruments and institutional arrangements, putting policy choices in a different perspective: more future-oriented with an explicit focus on transition pathways. Transition management is not being done by “transition managers”, but the outcome of transition pathways-oriented choices by private and public decision makers. While economists prefer carbon pricing (carbon taxes and tradeable carbon permits), transition experts favour policy mixes that are innovation-specific (designed to overcome identified barriers). For dealing with politics of design in a good way, Rosenbloom et al.(2019) suggest to embed the low-carbon transition in a broader transformative agenda, build societal legitimacy for climate policy, encourage the growth of constituencies with a material interest in climate-friendly transformations and to create a supportive ecosystem of institutions. The theory of change contains a mega-frame that says that policy could be more oriented towards altering systems of production and consumption through forward-looking and adaptive strategies by expanding actor-networks.</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Rosenbloom, D., Meadowcroft, J., Cashore, B. (2019). Stability and climate policy? Harnessing insights on path dependence, policy feedback and transition pathways, <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 50: 168-178.</p> <p>Kemp, R., Loorbach, D., Rotmans, J. (2007). Transition management as a model for managing processes of co-evolution for sustainable development, <i>The International Journal of</i></p>	

Sustainable Development and World Ecology (special issue on (co)-evolutionary approach to sustainable development) 14: 78-91

Meadowcroft, J.. (2009). What about the politics? Sustainable Development, Transition Management and Long-Term Energy Transitions. *Policy Sciences* 42: 323-340. 10.1007/s11077-009-9097-Z.

Voß, J.-P., Smith, A., Grin, J. (2009). Designing long-term policy: Rethinking transition management. *Policy Sciences* 42: 275–302.

Table SM.3.28. Behavioural economics

3.28. Behavioural economics	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Systems, Inner transformation
<p>The standard neoclassical economics approach assumes a representative agent that is a selfish, perfectly informed and a rational utility maximize with stable preferences and a long-term perspective. The empirical evidence shows though that human choices are more complex than this (Kahneman, 2003). Behavioural economics involve three groups of deviations from the standard rational choice model: bounded rationality, bounded willpower and bounded self-interest. Bounded rationality implies that human problem-solving is constrained by limited cognitive abilities (Simon, 1955). There are four main implications of this. First, many human decisions are determined by how information is presented to us more than by the consequences of decisions (a so-called "framing effect"). Second, individuals are more likely to take action to avoid a loss than to pursue a gain, leading to inaction and lost opportunities (so-called "loss aversion"). Third, the judgment of a particular situation is heavily influenced by what first comes to mind rather than by a careful assessment of information, resulting in poor choices (so-called "availability bias"). Finally, many choices are not a choice but automatic responses that do not resort to analytical capacity and could hence be damaging to the planet and humans. Bounded willpower refers to humans frequently failing to follow up on their commitments or failing to take commitments altogether. Humans fail to see the consequences of their actions (myopia of intertemporal choices). Another feature of bounded willpower is called cognitive dissonance, i.e., a mismatch between what people want and what they do. Procrastination regarding reducing your impact on the environment is a prime example. The third behavioural deviation is bounded self-interest. Evidence shows that individuals perceive themselves as herd animals, frequently willing to sacrifice themselves to help others, or capable of punishing those that act against the benefit of the group. Evidence shows that individuals have pro-social or others-regarding preferences. This is a potentially positive feature of social comparisons, but it can also be dangerous in those cases where herd behaviour leads to large environmental or social damages.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Kahneman, D. (2003). A Psychological Perspective on Economics. Source: <i>The American Economic Review</i>, 93(2), 162–168</p> <p>Simon, H. A. (1955). A Behavioral Model of Rational Choice. Source: <i>The Quarterly Journal of Economics</i>, 69(1), 99–118.</p> <p>Fehr, E., & Schmidt, K. (1999). A theory of fairness, competition and cooperation. <i>The Quarterly Journal of Economics</i>, August.</p> <p>Thaler, Richard H. 2018. "From Cashews to Nudges: The Evolution of Behavioral Economics." <i>American Economic Review</i>, 108 (6): 1265-87.</p> <p>World Bank 2015. <i>World Development Report 2015: Mind, Society and Behavior</i>. Washington, DC. (Overview)</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>The power of behavioural economics is in informing and developing better environmental and resource management models and policies (G. Brown & Hagen, 2010; Shogren & Taylor, 2008). A switch to more realistic human behaviour assumptions of individual and collective behaviours to produce truly transformative changes, instead of short-term patches. Traditional market-based policy instruments²⁰ and command and control measures need to be complemented and sometimes upgraded to account for the behavioural reactions of individuals and firms. To achieve that, the contribution of behavioural economics</p>	

²⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

to policy design can be structured in three sets of tools: i) tools that change the choice architecture, ii) tools focused on peer comparison or social norms and iii) improved analytics.

Choice architecture refers to how policies are presented and how those influences decisions (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). Simplifying the way information is presented, changing the default alternative and making efficient decisions a matter of habit (e.g., introducing efficient light bulbs) are helpful examples. Social norms and peer comparisons to change people's pro-environmental behaviour is also essential (Abrahamse & Steg, 2013). This tool has been extensively used in context of water and energy use, green options, tourism and recycling (Byerly et al., 2018). Moreover, policymakers would know agents' responses to past or current policies. Frequently policies are designed under the presumption that agents will remain inert to the policy itself. But a critical analytical insight is that individuals always react to policies and rules by ignoring them, hating them, using them in their favour or against someone, interpreting them and, now and then, obeying them.

Specific references:

Abrahamse, W., & Steg, L. (2013). Social influence approaches to encourage resource conservation: A meta-analysis. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(6), 1773–1785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.07.029>

Byerly, H., Balmford, A., Ferraro, P. J., Hammond Wagner, C., Palchak, E., Polasky, S., Ricketts, T. H., Schwartz, A. J., & Fisher, B. (2018). Nudging pro-environmental behavior: evidence and opportunities. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 16(3), 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1777>

Cialdini, R. B. (2003). Crafting normative messages to protect the environment. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 12(4), 105–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.01242>

Downs, J. S., Loewenstein, G., & Wisdom, J. (2009). Strategies for promoting healthier food choices. *American Economic Review*, 99(2), 159–164. <https://doi.org/10.1257/AER.99.2.159>

Farrow, K., Grolleau, G., & Ibanez, L. (2017). Social Norms and Pro-environmental Behavior: A Review of the Evidence. In *Ecological Economics* (Vol. 140, pp. 1–13). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.04.017>

Table SM.3.29. International political economy

3.29. International political economy	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Systems, Empowerment
<p>Political economy approaches to transformative change seek to understand both the actors, interests and institutions which benefit from the status quo that might be resistant to change, as well openings for moving beyond it. Political economy is an umbrella term for a diversity of approaches which have in common the fact that they place questions of power and politics centrally in their analysis, moving beyond the narrower study of socio-technical transitions which describe narrower changes in the provision of key services around mobility, heating and cooling, food or potentially biodiversity conservation (Newell, 2021).</p> <p>Transformative change in political economy accounts looks to address the causes and drivers of the problem rather than how its symptoms are treated through governance reform or technological and market innovation. Applied to biodiversity and ecosystem services, the focus might be on the concentrated power of agrifood corporations and the impacts this has on land use and deforestation (Clapp & Fuchs, 2009), on the key drivers of production and consumption which are driving biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, which might be thought to lie in economic incentive structures, inequitable property rights and the lack of value given to people and environments: what some authors have called ‘cheap nature’ and ‘cheap labour’ (Patel & Moore, 2018). They are also attentive to longer-term historical processes of transformation which they look to for parallels and inspiration about what might be possible going forward (Newell & Simms, 2021; Perez, 2002).</p> <p>Though traditionally focused on economic structures and the relationship between States and markets (Strange, 1998), more recent political economy thinking has been brought to bear on debates in systems thinking about leverage, intervention and tipping points and promoted the idea of ecosystems of transformation to recognize both the plurality of approaches to generating change from individual to system change (Newell, 2021), as well as the interrelated nature of transformation processes led by States, markets,</p>	

<p>technology and citizens (Scoones et al., 2015). This is helpful in creating ripple and multiplier effects where, for example, shifts in finance can trigger change in corporate behaviour and allow States to raise their level of ambition around biodiversity and ecosystem protection.</p>
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Newell, P. (2021). <i>Power Shift: The Global Political Economy of Energy Transitions</i>. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Patel, R. & Moore, J. (2018). <i>A History of the World in Seven Cheap Things</i>. London: Verso.</p> <p>Perez, C. (2002) <i>Technological Revolutions and Financial Capital: The Dynamics of Bubbles and Golden Ages</i>. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.</p> <p>Scoones, I., Leach, M., & Newell, P. (2015). (eds). <i>The Politics of Green Transformations</i>. Abingdon: Routledge.</p> <p>Strange, S. (1988) <i>States and Markets: An Introduction to International Political Economy</i>. London: Pinter.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>
<p>Key actors in political economy accounts of transformative change are States, corporate actors (often referred to more generically as capital), regional and global institutions and social movements. Drivers of change, therefore, include social pressure and civil society activism challenging State authority and corporate practice and surfacing new social norms around biodiversity conservation and use (Scoones et al., 2015); technological revolutions often brought about large scale shifts in finance, as occurred at the time of the Industrial Revolution, under Fordism and in relation to the information technology revolution (Perez, 2002) and which would be similar now around food production and State-led visions and plans to restructure economies as some governments are attempting to do with Green New Deals and the Inflation Reduction Act. Regional and international institutional institutions can either support more transformative change by mobilizing finance and building capacity or lock in unsustainable pathways through using aid and development finance to support projects and investments that accelerate biodiversity loss and nature’s decline as has happened so often in the place through large infrastructural projects and promoting the export of monoculture agriculture and forestry products, for example.</p> <p>Since the drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline are numerous and interconnected, political economy accounts would highlight the need to use a range of tools and approaches to trigger change within an ecosystem of transformation made up of States with uneven power and capacity, businesses of different sizes and civil societies faced with closing civic space in many parts of the world. No one approach will work in all contexts, but getting to the drivers of the problem will mean following and redirecting public and private finance, efforts to reduce consumption in richer parts of the world through dietary change and other means, addressing huge inequities in land distribution and access which concentrate power over our collective future in the hands of actors most resistant to transformative change and whose overrepresentation in political decision-making needs to be challenged as part of a broader shift in power.</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Clapp, J. and D. Fuchs (eds) (2009) <i>Corporate Power in Global Agrifood Governance</i>. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.</p> <p>Fuchs, D., Di Giulio, A., Glaab, K. et al. (2016). ‘Power: The missing element in sustainable consumption and absolute reductions research and action’. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>, 132, 298–307.</p> <p>Newell, P., Daley, F., & Twena, M. (2022). <i>Changing our ways: Behaviour change and the climate crisis</i>. Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Newell, P. & Simms, A. (2020). ‘How did we do that? Histories and political economies of rapid and just transitions’. <i>New Political Economy</i>, 26 (6): 907–922.</p> <p>Princen, T., Maniates, M., & Conca, K. (2002). (eds.) <i>Confronting Consumption</i>, Cambridge: MIT Press.</p>

Table SM.3.30. Transformative governance

<p>3.30. Transformative governance</p>	<p>Main approach: Structural</p> <p>Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Empowerment</p>
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Transformative governance approaches deal with the governance of transformative change, or how fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic and social factors for sustainable development can be governed, or facilitated by governance. Transformative governance represents a recently developed approach. However, it builds on extensive scholarship from fields such as environmental governance and sustainability transformations. In the conceptualization of IPBES of (2019a) and Visseren-Hamakers et al. (2021), transformative governance combines the following four approaches to governance: 1) Integrative approaches focus on the relationships between sectors and policies and ensure policy coherence and effectiveness, 2) Inclusive approaches, including rights-based ones, reflect a plurality of values and thus promote equity, 3) Informed governance entails new strategies for knowledge production and coproduction that are inclusive of diverse values and knowledge systems, 4) Adaptive approaches—including learning, monitoring and feedback loops—help coping with inevitable uncertainties and complexities (IPBES, 2019a). The approach attempts to facilitate transformative change by the employment of such transformative governance approaches. It can also be conceptualized as an approach for governing transformative change, or for transforming governance in order to realize transformative change.

Key references:

IPBES. 2019. Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Chapter 6.
 Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021. Transformative governance of biodiversity: insights for sustainable development. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 53: 20-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>;
 Chaffin et al. 2016. Transformative Environmental Governance. *Annual review of environment and resources* : 41:399-423. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085817>;
 Rusch et al. 2022. A joint climate and nature cure: A transformative change perspective. *Ambio* 51: 1459–1473.
 Visseren-Hamakers, I., & Kok, M. (Eds.). (2022). *Transforming Biodiversity Governance*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/9781108856348

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transformative governance approaches emphasize the aspects of transformation related to governance processes. The transformation of governance is seen as a crucial ingredient for wider transformative change. The approach does not entail a very clear distinction between initiating or steering transformative change. However, it is clearly promoting an intention for transformative change (that could involve both steering ongoing processes or initiate new ones). There is a strong emphasis on inclusive governance²¹, that is to include different (and otherwise marginalized) actors, worldviews and knowledges in deliberative and democratic political processes. Actors implicated by the approach are those that can transform governance processes and actors participating in transformed governance processes. This includes representatives for of diverse cultural and social norms, values, worldviews, knowledges and beliefs. Uneven distribution of power across scales and sectors and in particular actors with vested interest in upholding status quo, is recognized as a barrier to transformative governance (Rusch et al., 2022). Explicit recognition and deliberation of power-relations and their effects in governance processes is seen as a prerequisite to transformative governance. This is also relevant for processes of knowledge assessment and use. Cross-sectoral integration is also seen as a central driver for transformative change.

Specific references:

IPBES. 2019. Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Chapter 6.
 Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021. Transformative governance of biodiversity: insights for sustainable development. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 53: 20-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>;
 Chaffin et al. 2016. Transformative Environmental Governance. *Annual review of environment and resources* : 41:399-423. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085817>;
 Rusch et al. 2022. A joint climate and nature cure: A transformative change perspective. *Ambio* 51: 1459–1473.

²¹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Table SM.3.31. Environmental State and the green State

3.31. Environmental State and the Green State	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Science and technology, Systems
<p>There is a plurality of approaches in environmental politics, including but not limited to liberal institutionalist accounts of environmental cooperation, international environmental regimes; and environmental governance. Theories of environmental State and the green State are one important set of approaches that gained considerable attention in recent years, emphasizing the role of the State in the politics of environmental protection. This came as a response to the approaches that prioritize non-State actors, mechanisms and networks in addressing environmental problems, with the aim to ‘bring the State back in’ as “the more traditional object of political inquiry” (Duit et al., 2016). Environmental State is defined as: “a State that possesses a significant set of institutions and practices dedicated to the management of the environment and societal–environmental interactions” (Duit et al., 2016). This conceptualization is largely based on empirical observation. On the other hand, theory of the green State is different in that it is a normative approach that aims to elaborate the “constitutional structures of a green democratic State that might be more amenable to protecting nature than the liberal democratic State” (Eckersley, 2004). The environmental State is viewed as a partial transformation (from the welfare State) of the ways in which State exercises its authority (Duit et al., 2016). Recently, the term “glass ceiling of environmental transformation” (Hausknost, 2020) have been introduced referring to the structural limits that the environmental State faces in fostering transformation.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Robyn Eckersley, (2004). <i>The Green State: Rethinking Democracy and Sovereignty</i>. The MIT Press.</p> <p>Robyn Eckersley (2021) Greening states and societies: from transitions to great transformations, <i>Environmental Politics</i>, 30:1-2, 245-265, DOI:10.1080/09644016.2020.1810890</p> <p>Duit, A.; Feindt, P.H. and James Meadowcroft. (2016). Greening the leviathan? Rise of the environmental state. <i>Environmental Politics</i>, 25 (1): 1-23. Vol. 25, No. 1, 1–23, http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2015.1085218.</p> <p>Daniel Hausknost (2020) The environmental state and the glass ceiling of transformation, <i>Environmental Politics</i>, 29:1, 17-37, DOI: 10.1080/09644016.2019.1680062.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Environmental State theories envisage both emergent and deliberate transformative change, emergent in the sense that it is based on an evolutionary perspective, with changes brought about by environmental degradation, the State needs to rework its authoritative claims and imperatives, leading to the partial transformation of the State itself and possibly transformative change. Intentional in the sense that science provides knowledge on cause-effect relations in environmental degradation and depending on the nature of political coalitions, a change in the perspective of the State on how to tackle these problems with a transformative potential (Duit et al., 2016). Similar to the formation of the welfare State and its evolution to the environmental State because of State imperatives, because of the depth of environmental problems, evolution of the environmental State to a green State possibly bringing about socio-ecological transformation is envisaged. Intentional transformation involves rethinking the relationship between the State, political economy and democracy (Hausknost & Hammond, 2020). For Green State theories, deliberate transformative change comes with the potential of the State to facilitate and accelerate socio-ecological transformation, but cannot fully plan it (Eckersley, 2021). For the green State, critical conjunctures are crucial and “the practical task is to identify the next best transition steps with the greatest transformative potential.” (Eckersley, 2021).</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Robyn Eckersley (2021) Greening states and societies: from transitions to great transformations, <i>Environmental Politics</i>, 30:1-2, 245-265, DOI:10.1080/09644016.2020.1810890</p>	

Duit, A.; Feindt, P.H. and James Meadowcroft. (2016). Greening the leviathan? Rise of the environmental state. *Environmental Politics*, 25 (1): 1-23. Vol. 25, No. 1, 1–23, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2015.1085218>.

Daniel Hausknot (2020) The environmental state and the glass ceiling of transformation, *Environmental Politics*, 29:1, 17-37, DOI: 10.1080/09644016.2019.1680062.

Table SM.3.32. Structuration theory

3.32. Structuration theory	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Systems, Inner transformation, Empowerment
<p>Structuration theory, first outlined by sociologist Anthony Giddens, explains how social systems are created and reproduced through a synthesis of structure and agency without giving primacy to one of them. Instead, they are mutually constitutive – what Giddens terms the “duality of structure.” The structures are not stable. While they can restrict the possible action alternatives, they provide means and forms by which actors can take action and, consequently, possibly transform the structure itself.</p> <p>According to structuration theory, societies are made up of a collective of individuals whose interactions are structured by persistent patterns of rules and resources. These structures are upheld by institutions, norms, power relations and cultural contexts that shape and constrain individuals’ actions. Conversely, through their actions actors reproduce but also potentially also challenge the structures. Giddens emphasizes the importance of reflexivity for structural change, that is the ability to reflect critically on one's actions in relation to societal structures.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Giddens, A. (1984) <i>The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration</i>, Cambridge: Policy Press.</p> <p>Lippuner, R. & Werlen, B. 2009. Structuration theory. In: Kitchin, R. & Thrift, N. (eds.) <i>International Encyclopedia of Human Geography</i>. Amsterdam, NL: Elsevier.</p> <p>Stone, R. (2005). <i>Structuration Theory</i>. New York, NY, Palgrave MacMillian</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework?</p>	
<p>While structures restrict and guide individuals’ action, they are also formed by human agency. Agency refers to the capacity to act with intent within present structures. Through their actions, individuals can both reproduce and challenge these structures. This creates a possibility of transforming societies in spite of deep-seated structures. Reflexivity – the critical reflection of how actions interact with existing structures – provides some empowerment within the structural constraints whereby a transformative change is possible. The interplay between structures and agency, provides space for human agency to challenge existing social structures, which enables new forms of social organization and cultural practices to emerge, which ultimately leads to societal transformations.</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Giddens, A. (1984) <i>The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration</i>, Cambridge: Policy Press.</p> <p>Wendt, A. 2015. <i>Quantum mind and social science: unifying physical and social ontology</i>, Cambridge, UK, Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Stone, R. (2005). <i>Structuration Theory</i>. New York, NY, Palgrave MacMillian</p> <p>Sewell Jr, W. H. 2005. <i>Logics of history: Social theory and social transformation</i>, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.</p>	

Table SM.3.33. Social practice theory

3.33. Social practice theory	Main approach: Structural Secondary approach: Systems, Inner transformation, Empowerment
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<p>Social practice theory explains society and culture emerge as a result of structure and individual agency. It addresses the dualism of agency and structure by proposing that ‘practice’ is the primary organizing concept of social life and thus a way how societal transformations can occur despite deep seated structures.</p>
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Nicolini, Davide. 2012. <i>Practice Theory, Work and Organization: An Introduction</i>. First Edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>
<p>Social practice theory explains society and culture emerge as a result of structure and individual agency. It is also known as praxeology or theory of social practices and is primarily rooted in social theories within anthropology and sociology to understand how everyday practices – behaviour, routines, habits and activities – shape and are shaped by social order. It addresses the dualism of agency and structure by proposing that ‘practice’ is the primary organizing concept of social life and thus a way for societal transformations to occur despite deep-seated structures. Practices are embedded within broader social structures of cultural norms, institutional arrangements and historical contexts.</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Behagel, Jelle Hendrik, Bas Arts and Esther Turnhout. 2019. ‘Beyond Argumentation: A Practice-Based Approach to Environmental Policy’. <i>Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning</i> 21 (5): 479–91. https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2017.1295841.</p> <p>Hargreaves, T. (2011). Practice-ing behaviour change: Applying social practice theory to pro-environmental behaviour change. <i>Journal of consumer culture</i>, 11(1), 79-99.</p> <p>Nicolini, Davide. 2012. <i>Practice Theory, Work and Organization: An Introduction</i>. First Edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press."</p>

Table SM.3.34. Actor network theory

<p>3.34. Actor network theory</p>	<p>Main approach: Structural</p> <p>Secondary approach: Systems, Empowerment</p>
<p>Actor-networks are the web of associations that constitute entities and relations between human and nonhuman elements such as bodies, groups, ecologies, that maintain them together with the capacity to act (Blok et al., 2020). The concept of association is crucial for actor-network theory, since it indicates the capacity of actors to link between each other and form networks (Sismondo, 2009). In that way, associations are a type of connection able to maintain together and create new relations between elements as diverse as humans, microbes, regulations, animals, viruses and more (Latour, 2005). This theory is characterized by its sensibility towards relationality, heterogeneity and materiality. Regarding relationality, actor-network theory argues that no entity exists outside a web of relations, so it is a network and its internal relations that shape different entities within it and the network itself (Law, 2008). About heterogeneity, actor network theory states the importance of symmetry with the assumption that in principle human and nonhumans could have the capacity to become actors once they are associated within a network (Latour, 2005). In its material sensibility, actor network theory emphasizes the need to attend to materials, devices, artefacts and other objects that shape the social world and its networks (Blok et al., 2020; Farías & Bender, 2009). This means that actor-networks could not be understood without the materials and components that allow networks to sustain action. Given its anti-essentialism and non-foundational style, actor network theory is a robust theory to understand how transformative change occurs, since this approach is concerned with the material associations through which different kind of actors are brought together to work together and change the ways in which they act (Callon & Law, 1995). For this reason, actor network theory can be a toolkit to follow the often-overseen chains of associations that produce transformative change, which could take us to surprising places such as mountains, laboratories, scientific texts, social movement meetings, satellites and more.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Callon, M., & Law, J. (1995). Agency and the Hybrid Collectif. <i>South Atlantic Quarterly</i>, 94(2), 481–507.</p>	

<p>Farias, I., Roberts, C., & Blok, A. (Eds.). (2020). <i>The Routledge companion to actor-network theory</i>. Routledge.</p> <p>Latour, B. (2005). <i>Reassembling the Social – An Introduction to Actor Network Theory</i>. Oxford University Press.</p> <p>Law, J. (2008). Actor Network Theory and Material Semiotics. In B. Turner (Ed.), <i>The New Blackwell Companion to Social Theory</i> (3rd ed., pp. 141–158). Blackwell.</p> <p>Sismondo, S. (2010). <i>An introduction to science and technology studies</i> (2nd ed.). Wiley-Blackwell.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>
<p>Actor network theory explores the contingencies of power, generating tools to undo the inevitability of that power while working on the possibility that other and better worlds are possible (Law & Singleton, 2013). This brings interesting possibilities for studying how deliberate transformative change occurs. For example, in the field of politics and policy, actor network argues that policy is a scenario²² where nature and the social are negotiated and handled together to create the potential for transformative change (Law & Singleton, 2014). In this way, for actor network theory, transformative change is not to be analyzed by following individual actors that are assumed to have the intrinsic agency to generate transformative change. Instead, it focuses on the practical and material processes of construction through which collective life is organized. Transformative change is to be studied as a collective achievement organized through networks that constitute and distribute agency capacities among humans and nonhumans (Farias & Bender, 2009). Here, transformative change occurs as an effect of the associations capable of generating processes of transformative change within a network. They can be analyzed by following the series of movements that activate relations between heterogeneous elements (human and nonhuman), that allows us to see how these associations mobilize a world and enable courses of action that produce transformative change. That is why the potential of actor network theory for addressing biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and its implications for generating and navigating transformative change processes lies in its sensitivity to follow associations. According to Latour (2004), this relational and associative understanding of transformative change could help redefine politics and transformative change as the progressive composition of a good common world. Therefore, actor network theory can be better understood as a sensibility of working in the world to create analytical contexts, but also on the world to articulate and press particular transformative changes and their politics (Law & Singleton, 2013).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Farias, I., & Bender, T. (Eds.). (2010). <i>Urban assemblages: How actor-network theory changes urban studies</i>. Routledge.</p> <p>Latour, B. (2004). <i>Politics of nature</i>. Harvard University Press.</p> <p>Law, J., & Singleton, V. (2013). ANT and Politics: Working in and on the World. <i>Qualitative Sociology</i>, 36, 485–502.</p> <p>Law, J., & Singleton, V. (2014). ANT, multiplicity and policy. <i>Critical Policy Studies</i>, 8(4), 379–396.</p> <p>Rodríguez-Giralt, I., Marrero-Guillamón, I., & Milstein, D. (2018). Reassembling activism, activating assemblages: An introduction. <i>Social Movement Studies</i>, 17(3), 257–268.</p>

3.Inner transformation

Table SM.3.35. Inner transformation	65
Table SM.3.36. Pathways to nature connectedness	67
Table SM.3.37. Relationality	68
Table SM.3.38. Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures	70
Table SM.3.39. SHIFT	71

²² See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Table SM.3.40. Transformative learning for social-ecological sustainability	72
Table SM.3.41. Relational values and relationality.....	73

Table SM.3.35. Inner transformation

3.35. Inner Transformation	Main approach: Inner transformation, Empowerment
	Secondary approach: Structural
<p>Inner transformation for sustainability is an emergent field of research, education and practice (Ives et al., 2023). The aim is to support integrative approaches that link inner and outer dimensions of transformation across sectors and levels to, consequently, enhance individual, collective and planetary well-being, regeneration and flourishing (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). Inner dimensions are defined as individual and collective mindsets, beliefs, values, worldviews and associated inner capacities/qualities (cognitive, emotional, relational). The concept recognizes that inner and outer dimensions are never separate, but are co-created (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). On this basis, inner transformation involves changes in the sphere of human inner dimensions and refers to all kinds of actions at individual, collective and system levels that support integrative changes in views, structures and practices, which address the impacts, drivers and causes of today’s polycrisis, including biodiversity loss and nature’s decline (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). The field of inner transformation addresses unsustainable narratives and paradigms of separation (alienation from self, others, nature) that underlie today’s polycrisis. They are an integral element of modern life forms and they are reflected in modern societies’ culture, the institutional and political landscape and associated power structures (Ives et al., 2023; Walsh et al., 2021; Wamsler et al., 2021; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022; S. West et al., 2020). Inner transformation is thus about enabling intra- and inter-generational, human- and non-human relationships and ways of connecting to self, others and the world in ways that support integrative action-taking across sectors and scales (Ives et al., 2023).</p> <p>Related research, practice and education recognize: i) the interdependence of inner and outer phenomena across individual, collective and system levels (and associated views, practices and structures); ii) the potential that is latent within every human to enable transformative change; iii) the need to address inner dimensions across all levels; iv) the possibility to generate inner, transformative capacities/qualities²³ through intentional practices; and v) the need to include diverse perspectives and expand associated knowledge systems (including Indigenous and local) for sustainability (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). Related key theories and conceptualizations include the IMAGINE framework, integral theory, the three spheres of transformation, the inner-outer transformation model, clusters of transformative capacities/qualities, the mind-sustainability nexus and the framework for contemplative scientific inquiry, practice and education (Ives et al., 2020, 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021, 2022).</p>	
Key references:	
<p>Ives, C., Schöpke, N., Woiwode, C., Wamsler, C. (2023) IMAGINE sustainability: integrated inner-outer transformation in research, education and practice. <i>Sustain Sci</i> 18, 2777–2786 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01368-3</p> <p>Wamsler, C., Osberg, G., Osika, W., Hendersson, H., Mundaca, L. (2021) Linking internal and external transformation for sustainability and climate action: Towards a new research and policy agenda, <i>Global Environmental Change</i>, 71. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102373.</p> <p>Walsh, Z., Böhme, J., Wamsler, C. (2021) Towards a relational paradigm in sustainability research, practice and education. <i>Ambio</i> 50, 74–84. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-020-01322-y</p> <p>West S., Haider L.J., Stålhammar S., Woroniecki S. (2020) A relational turn for sustainability science? Relational thinking, leverage points and transformations, <i>Ecosystems and People</i>, 16(1):304-325. https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2020.1814417</p> <p>Wamsler, C., Bristow, J. (2022) At the intersection of mind and climate change: Integrating inner dimensions of climate change into policymaking and practice, <i>Climatic Change</i>, 173(7). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03398-9</p>	

²³ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Wamsler C., Bristow J., Cooper K., Steidle G., Taggart S., Søvold L., Bockler J., Oliver T.H., Legrand T. (2022). Theoretical foundations report: Research and evidence for the potential of consciousness approaches and practices to unlock sustainability and systems transformation. Report of the UNDP Conscious Food Systems Alliance (CoFSA), United Nations Development Programme UNDP. Available online.

O'Brien, K. and Sygna, L. (2013) Responding to Climate Change: The Three Spheres of Transformation. Proceedings of Transformation in Changing Climate International Conference, Oslo, 19-21 June 2013, 16-23.

Ives, C.D., Freeth, R. Fischer, J. (2020) Inside-out sustainability: The neglect of inner worlds. *Ambio* 49, 208–217 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019-01187-w>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Inner transformation addresses deep leverage points and involves measures and methods that can support more relational and regenerative views, practices and structures (Ives et al., 2023; Walsh et al., 2021; Wamsler et al., 2021; S. West et al., 2020). Change is mobilized through integrative measures that link inner and outer dimensions of transformation across sectors and levels (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). There are complementary ways to activate such integration, in order to, ultimately, address mindsets, behaviour, culture and systems change in combination (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021, 2022; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022). Measures at individual and collective levels include linking ‘outer’ approaches with activities that help people tap into their inner potential, discover their internalized messages of separation, superiority and instrumentalization, develop alternative approaches and create fields of change (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022). This can, for instance, be supported through appropriate working environments, communities of practice, social movements, aesthetics and transformative leadership and education (Wamsler et al., 2021, 2022). The latter involves holistic, contemplative, psychological, cognitive-behavioural and ethical learning approaches (e.g., worldview journeys, mindfulness-, arts- and nature-based methods) that nurture transformative capacities/qualities (e.g., self-reflection, intrinsic value orientation, compassion, individual and collective agency) (Hedlund-de Witt et al., 2014; B. Scott et al., 2021; Wamsler, 2018; Wamsler et al., 2021, 2022; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022). Measures at system level aim to mainstream the consideration of inner dimensions into institutional and political systems to foster more integrative approaches (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). This institutionalization entails modifying organizations’ vision statements, policies, regulations, working structures and tools for project management, resource allocation, communication, monitoring and evaluation (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2020, 2021; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022).

From an ethical standpoint, it is crucial to highlight that inner transformation is not about fixing other people’s views. This would turn them into objects to be changed, rather than seeing them as agents of change (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2020, 2021). Instead, it is about creating integrative measures, spaces and conditions that nurture a culture of inner development, mutual support and engagement. Building on a foundation of shared, universal values and interconnection, the aim is, ultimately, to rattle unsustainable norms and systems (Bentz et al., 2022; Ives et al., 2023; Leichenko & O’Brien, 2019; Wamsler et al., 2021). Inner transformation is a dynamic field. It has attracted professionals from many disciplines and domains and is thus conceptualized using various terms, e.g., inner-outer transformation, inner transition, existential resilience, existential sustainability (Ives et al., 2023; Wamsler et al., 2021). Actors include governmental, United Nations, private, non-profit and faith-based organizations, educational bodies, citizen groups and local and Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Bentz et al., 2022; Hedlund-de Witt et al., 2014; Ives et al., 2020, 2023; Leichenko & O’Brien, 2019; O’Brien & Sygna, 2013; B. Scott et al., 2021; Walsh et al., 2021; Wamsler, 2018; Wamsler et al., 2020, 2021, 2022; Wamsler & Bristow, 2022; S. West et al., 2020).

Specific references:

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Bentz, J., O'Brien, K., Scoville-Simonds, M. Beyond (2022) “blah blah blah”: exploring the “how” of transformation. *Sustainability Science* 17(497–506). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01123-0>

Leichenko, R., O'Brien, K. (2019) *Climate and society: Transforming the future*, John Wiley & Sons.

Table SM.3.36. Pathways to nature connectedness

3.36. Pathways to nature connectedness	Main approach: Inner transformation
Secondary approach: Systems	
<p>The pathways to nature connectedness (Lumber et al., 2017) provide a typology of activities that provide a framework for improving the human–nature relationship through targeting nature connectedness, an internationally recognized psychological construct that captures how an individual thinks about nature, their affective relationship with nature and the extent to which they see themselves as part of nature (Mayer & Frantz, 2004). The pathways have a theoretical basis in Kellert’s (1993) nine values of biophilia. Through ascertaining engagement with and perceived importance of each of the nine values, five types of activity associated with nature connectedness were identified. These were contact through the senses, emotional engagement, noticing nature’s beauty, finding meaning in nature and acting with compassion towards nature. The pathways can be used to inform the design of new initiatives to improve human-nature relationships or used as a lens to review existing initiatives. The pathways framework encourages specific types of active engagement, moving away from traditional human-nature relationships of utility, control and knowledge that have dominated the human relationship with the rest of the natural world and thus contributed to a failing relationship with nature and the environmental crises.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Lumber, R., Richardson, M., & Sheffield, D. (2017). Beyond knowing nature: Contact, emotion, compassion, meaning and beauty are pathways to nature connection. <i>PLoS one</i>, 12(5).</p> <p>Kellert SR. 1993. The biological basis for human values of nature. In: Kellert SR, Wilson EO, editors. <i>The biophilia hypothesis</i>. Washington (DC): Island Press; p. 42–69.</p> <p>Mayer FS, Frantz CM. 2004. The connectedness to nature scale: A measure of individuals’ feeling in community with nature. <i>J Environ Psychol</i>. 24(4):503–515.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>From a pathways to nature connectedness perspective deliberate transformative change occurs by combining inner transformation of the human-nature relationship with a systems perspective. Firstly, research shows and robust and likely causal relationship between increased nature connectedness and pro-environmental behaviours (Mackay & Schmitt, 2019). With this including pro-nature conservation behaviours (Richardson, Passmore, et al., 2020). The pathways can be applied across a range of leverage points relevant across multiple societal scales (Meadows, 1999; Richardson, Dobson, et al., 2020). For example, interventions based on activating the pathways framework can be targeted at leverage points around system goals, design, feedback and parameters across policy areas such as education, health, housing, arts, health and transport. Demonstrating that the pathways to nature connectedness have a large scale of societal relevance and can provide solutions across a range of leverage points to foster a closer human–nature relationship across society.</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p>	

Richardson M, Passmore H-A, Hunt A, Thomas R. 2020a. The green care code: how nature connectedness and simple activities help explain pro-nature conservation behaviours. *People Nat.* 2:821–839. doi:10.1002/pan3.10117.

Richardson, M., Dobson, J., Abson, D. J., Lumber, R., Hunt, A., Young, R., & Moorhouse, B. (2020b). Applying the pathways to nature connectedness at a societal scale: a leverage points perspective. *Ecosystems and People*, 16(1), 387-401.

Mackay CM, Schmitt MT. 2019. Do people who feel connected to nature do more to protect it? A meta-analysis. *J Environ Psychol*.

Meadows DH. 1999. Leverage points: places to intervene in a system. <http://donellameadows.org/archives/leverage-points-places-to-intervene-in-a-system/#seven>

Table SM.3.37. Relationality

3.37. Relationality	Main approach: Inner transformation
Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation	
<p>Relationality is a broad field of diverse origins, including the thoughts of a Greek philosopher, Heraclitus, who stated that ‘everything flows’, emphasizing the interconnectedness and constant change or perpetual flux of the world. Other key thinkers include Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty and North Whitehead (S. West et al., 2019). More than a specific theory, relationality represents a path-breaking ontological turn across many fields of social sciences and humanities. Conceptualizations vary. For some, relational thinking may be complementary to sustainability sciences (S. West et al., 2019), for others the implications are more far-reaching (Escobar, 2016). Walsh et al. (2021) find common commitments to a ‘paradigm that i) is grounded in a relational ontology, ii) emphasizes the need for understanding human and non-human nature as mutually constitutive and iii) values more-than-human relations.’ A relational ontology challenges common assumptions about what constitutes reality, seeking to overcome longstanding rigid dichotomies between nature and culture, mind and matter, subject and object, which shape modern worldviews. Diverse knowledge systems are not premised on such divides (Walsh et al., 2021), emphasizing the process nature of life i.e., that the ‘world exists in a perpetual state of ‘becoming’, comprising continually unfolding relations (S. West et al., 2019). If humans are ‘fundamentally in the material world’, rather than prioritizing interior mental cognition (Wagenaar and Cook (2011) cited by West et al., (2019)) by humans, diverse aspects of experience, including embodied experiences and the ‘capacity to affect and be affected’ (Deleuze et al., 1987) can be recognized, including by non-human agents. Further, rather than reflecting the world, language and concepts in relationality, actively shape it, with Indo-European languages evolving within substantialist paradigms which reduce processes to static conditions (Elias (1978) cited by West et al, (2019)).</p> <p>Relational ontologies recognize continuities between actors and actants (Latour, 2005). Such assemblages of the ‘more-than-human’ include human and non-human (physical forces and phenomena such as the wind or fire, material objects and things, living beings, spiritual entities, technologies (Blaser, 2014; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017) all of which are entangled (Barad, 2007) in complex networks (Latour, 2005). Relational philosophies include many Indigenous and African cosmologies, Shintoism etc., and are flourishing within academic philosophy and in the space-time materialities of quantum physics. While entities seem relatively stable to us (DeLanda, 2006), they are ‘already constituted by movement’ (Ingold (2011) cited by West (2019)) in a departure from both modernist, mechanistic perspectives and socio-ecological systems thinking (S. West et al., 2019). In other words, any being, entity or body is conceived as ‘fundamentally constituted by relations of all kinds’(Walsh et al., 2021). In epistemologies or ‘how we come to know the world’ (Walsh et al., 2021), as in quantum physics, the observer shapes what it observes (Barad, 2007). Following Deleuze et al. (1987) on agency, it is defined not as ‘cognitive-reflective’ abilities alone, but the ‘capacity to affect and be affected’, agency is not solely about what humans do (Whatmore, 2002), but is distributed within relational networks, assemblages and configurations (Latour (2005) cited by West et al, (2019)). Transdisciplinary methods support the traversing of disciplinary boundaries, with nature being produced in situated contexts (Haraway, 1988), i.e. knowledge is always shaped by the specific social, cultural and historical contexts, with no objective, universal, neutral perspectives from which knowledge can be produced (S. West et al., 2019).</p>	

Relational ethics move beyond anthropocentrism and the valuation of nature based on instrumental values and explore how power inequalities and dynamics are infused within all assemblages of interest, including human-nature interactions (Walsh et al., 2021), towards an ethics of care (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017).

Key references:

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- Bennett J. 2010. Vibrant matter: A political ecology of things. Durham and London: Duke University Press
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- Latour, B. 2005. Reassembling the social: An introduction to actor network theory. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press
- Puig de la Bellacasa, M. 2017. Matters of care: Speculative ethics in more than human worlds. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press.
- Raymond, C.M., R. Kaaronen, M. Giusti, N. Linder & S. Barthel (2021) Engaging with the pragmatics of relational thinking, leverage points and transformations – Reply to West et al., *Ecosystems and People*, 17:1, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2020.1867645>
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How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

In terms of how change happens in relational perspectives, affect theorists, Deleuze et al. (1987) offer complex and dynamic understandings of how change happens. They emphasize that change is non-linear, interconnected and rhizomatic (i.e., growing like a rhizome or root-like structure in found in plants), occurring through lateral connections and influences, as opposed to via hierarchical structures. If relationality is a far-reaching shift in assumptions about what people do or can exist in reality (Walsh et al., 2021), then acceptance is itself a transformative act (J. S. Clark et al., 2014; Pellizzoni, 2015; Stengers, 2010); Darnhofer (2020) cited by West et al. (2019). There are political implications from this shift, which implies a move towards ethics of care (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). By recognizing that categories are not fixed, it is possible or necessary to view them in more ethical ways (Darnhofer (2020) cited by West et al. (2019)). Care then becomes actions to sustain and regenerate bodies, selves, environment, world (Tronto, 1993). Caring involves labour, but Puig de la Bellacasa (2017) challenges conventional understandings of care as an altruistic, unidirectional act and emphasizes the situated and relational nature of care practices. Further, it is not only humans that are involved in care, non-humans also participate in collective, embodied and reciprocal practice (S. West et al., 2019). Additionally, the act of creating worlds, or worlding, is a political task with ramifications for the role of researchers and the ethics of research (S. West et al., 2019). Care distinguishes stewardship from management and governance approaches in conservation and sustainability sciences (Enqvist et al., 2018). Relationality provides fertile ground for richer analyses of human-nature relations, situated empirical insights to shape decision-making and new approaches for sustainability that cultivate and nurture relations in specific places and practice (S. West et al., 2019).

Specific references:

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Tronto JC. 1993. *Moral boundaries: a political argument for an ethic of care*. New York & London: Routledge

Table SM.3.38. Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures

3.38. Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures	Main approach: Inner transformation Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Systems
<p>Modern humans excel in practices of forecasting and foresight. However, this capacity does not necessarily result in transformative action. Projections and scenario building exercises no longer foresee business-as-usual greenhouse gas emission as an option (Stocker et al., 2013), but society breaks emission records every year and climate-related disasters intensify. Science also projected in 2012 that places with high biodiversity, large human populations, poverty and environmental degradation where prone to epidemic or pandemic outbreaks of zoonotic diseases (Morse et al., 2012). Nevertheless, society did not act in anticipation to covid-19 pandemic. In other words, modern society forecasts, foresees, but does not often take anticipatory action. It is almost as if modern society does not feel the problems coming, or as if it senses that – at most – it is going to watch them happen on television or the internet. Until they happen. Since, anticipatory behaviour is about making decisions in the present based on assumptions about the future, it can be argued that the anticipatory system of modern society is impaired. Thus, it needs to regenerate. The argument is that modernity²⁴ fractured the whole into modules. Sustainability, in its broadest sense of planetary well-being, will implies that ongoing dialogues are expanded to include both non-modern worldviews (e.g., Indigenous and local knowledge; postmodern views) and non-scientific forms of interpretation of reality (e.g., arts, philosophy, religions). This comprehensive and inclusive conversation can regenerate the fractures that have ruptured the connections between the “three ecologies” – of self, social and environment – and reintegrate humans to the world, to nature as wholeness (Scarano, 2024).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Scarano FR (2024) <i>Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures</i>. Springer, Cham</p> <p>Complementing references:</p> <p>Bateson G (1972/1987) <i>Steps to an ecology of mind: collected essays in anthropology, psychiatry and epistemology</i>. Chicago University Press, Chicago</p> <p>Guattari F (1989/2000) <i>The three ecologies</i>. Athlone Press, London</p> <p>Scarano FR (2019b) The emergence of sustainability. In: Wegner LH, Lüttge U (eds) <i>Emergence and modularity in life sciences</i>. Springer, Cham, pp 51–71. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-06128-9_3</p> <p>Cited:</p> <p>IPCC (2013) <i>Climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change</i>. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge</p> <p>Morse SS, Mazet JAK, Woolhouse M, Parrish CR, Carroll D, Karesh WB, Zambrana-Torrel C, Lipkin WI, Daszak P (2012) Prediction and prevention of the next pandemic zoonosis. <i>Lancet</i> 380:1956–1965. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61684-5</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>‘Regeneration’ is a keyword behind deliberate transformative change. It consists first in a change of mindset (from reductionism to holism), which is a pre-requisite to a paradigmatic socio-ecological change. Such change implies regeneration, in the sense of reparation of relationships (between beings), systems (connectivity and wholeness of spaces and times) and rights (visions, realities, utopias). Thus, a central tenet of my theory (Scarano, 2024) is that the deliberate transformative change starts at the inner dimension and</p>	

²⁴ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

then moves to a relational ground. Modernity reduced the whole into modules. Time (past/present/future), knowledge (scientific/artistic/ spiritual/local), worldviews (traditional/modern/postmodern) and ultimately the world (nature/culture/technology) are fractured. Some modules became hegemonic (e.g., modern science, innovation as technological only and capitalism) and – despite historical improvements in many fronts – such hegemonies led the planet into its current state of multicrisis, as climate change, biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and pervasive inequalities worsen. The hegemonic modern narrative became paradigmatic and desecrated nature, turning it into commodity. There is no possible ‘adaptation’ within this paradigm: transformative change is not about adapting, but about shifting paradigms. The transition from an unsustainable to a sustainable world involves imagining and believing in desirable futures distinct from the past-present, so as to take transformative action. Regenerative dialogues (between different worldviews, different forms of interpretation of reality and between humans and more-than-humans) decolonize futures by enhancing imagination, building active hope and, ultimately, by promoting convergence of modules into wholes. The notion that a state of planetary well-being might emerge from regenerative dialogues implies the absence of a blueprint or roadmap for change. It is based on ‘open’ rather than ‘blueprint’ utopias. It circumvents the problem/solution dichotomy (another modern feature) and focuses on dialogues.

Specific references:

Scarano FR (2024) Regenerative dialogues for sustainable futures. Springer, Cham

Complementing references:

Horlings LG (2015) The inner dimension of sustainability: personal and cultural values. *Curr Opin Environ Sustain* 14:163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.06.006>
 Ives CD, Freeth R, Fischer J (2020) Inside-out sustainability: the neglect of inner worlds. *Ambio* 49:208–217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019- 01187- w>
 Woiwode C, Schöpke N, Bina O, Veciana S, Kunze I, Parodi O, Schweizer-Ries P, Wamsler C (2021) Inner transformation to sustainability as a deep leverage point: fostering new avenues for change through dialogue and reflection. *Sustain Sci* 16:841–858. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020- 00882- y>

Table SM.3.39. SHIFT

3.39. SHIFT	Main approach: Inner transformation Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation
<p>SHIFT is a framework that integrates various factors that influence individual behaviour change (White et al., 2019). The focus of the framework is on explaining the attitude-behaviour gap observed when individuals fail to change despite their willingness to do so. SHIFT is an acronym that stands for Social influence, Habit formation, Individual self, Feelings and cognition and Tangibility as factors that contribute to behaviour change.</p> <p>The framework can be seen as an extension of the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1985), one of the most fundamental theories in behavioural science. The five SHIFT factors exploit the frequently observed lack of connection between people’s intentions and behaviour. Social influence includes the influence of social norms and identity. Habit formation describes the factors that initiate long-term behaviour change, not just momentary behaviour change. Individual self describes factors such as self-efficacy and self-consistency, which are relevant for promoting motivation to change and ultimately bring about change. Feelings describe emotional factors that contribute to promoting change. And finally, tangibility refers to the importance of making the goals and outcomes immediate and proximal to the individual.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>White, K., Habib, R., & Hardisty, D. J. (2019). How to SHIFT Consumer Behaviors to be More Sustainable: A Literature Review and Guiding Framework. <i>Journal of Marketing</i>, 83(3), 22-49. https://doi.org/10.1177/0022242919825649</p> <p>Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior. Ina J. Kuhl & J. Beckmann (Eds.), <i>Action control: From cognition to behavior</i>. Berlin, Heidelberg, New York: Springer-Verlag. (pp. 11–39).</p>	

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework
<p>To bring about transformative change based on individual behavioural change, change is both deep and broad. Two factors in the SHIFT framework are particularly important to achieve depth and breadth: Habit formation and social influence.</p> <p>While some behaviours to prevent diversity loss are one-time, such as long-term investment decisions or decisions when constructing a building or garden, for instance, many individual behaviours are repeated and therefore require not just a one-time change, but a deep change in habits. While various interventions promote habit formation (e.g., facilitation, prompts and incentives), discontinuities and interruptions of old habits, e.g., a move or change of job, are beneficial for the introduction of new habits (Verplanken, 2010). The fresh start effect describes how even arbitrary, seemingly disruptive dates such as the first day of a new month or year can contribute to the development of new habits.</p> <p>Social influence is particularly relevant to achieve broad change via a so-called social tipping point²⁵. Social tipping points describe dynamics in large-scale behavioural change that lead to a shift in social norms that further promote change (P. Young, 2015).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Hengchen Dai, Katherine L. Milkman, Jason Riis (2014) The Fresh Start Effect: Temporal Landmarks Motivate Aspirational Behavior. <i>Management Science</i> 60(10):2563-2582.</p> <p>Verplanken Bas (2010), “Old Habits and New Routes to Sustainable Behaviour,” in <i>Engaging the Public with Climate Change: Behaviour Change and Communication</i>, Whitmarsh L., O’Neill S., Lorenzoni I., eds. Milton Park, England: Taylor and Francis, 17–30.</p> <p>Young, H. P. The evolution of social norms. <i>Annu. Rev. Econ.</i> 7, 359–387 (2015).</p>

Table SM.3.40. Transformative learning for social-ecological sustainability

3.40. Transformative learning for social-ecological sustainability	<p>Main approach: Inner</p> <p>Secondary approach: Empowerment, Knowledge co-creation</p>
<p>Transformative learning (Mezirow, 2000) constitutes learning that affects your whole being and your being in the world. Sometimes it is referred to as ‘deep learning’ and learning that impacts one’s inner development as it affects one’s values, convictions, assumptions, frames and ways of viewing oneself (identity) and the world of which one is a part (O’Sullivan, 1999). Often a disruption or discontinuity in one’s thinking is needed to create space for a new way of thinking. Transformative learning can be triggered by being exposed to alternative perspectives, dissonance, discomfort and disorienting dilemma’s. Some scholar connect transformative learning with transgressive learning to emphasize that fundamental change involves going against the grain, questioning the normal and learning from the resulting resistance (Kulundu-Bolus, 2020). Interaction with others through forms of dialogue and debate, as well as self-reflection are critical aspects of transformative learning (Lysaker & Furuness, 2011). Typically, transformative learning implies transformation at the individual level, it does not necessarily imply societal transformation. However, within transition movements involving a wide range of people, groups and networks, transformative learning is often viewed as an essential component of learning for and in transitions as such transitions do require a deep commitment and alignment of underlying shared values and principles (Van Mierlo et al., 2020).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Kulundu, I., McGarry, D. K., & Lotz-Sisitka, H. (2020). Think Piece: Learning, Living and Leading into Transgression—A reflection on decolonial praxis in a neoliberal world. <i>Southern African Journal of Environmental Education</i>, 36.</p> <p>Lysaker, J. T., & Furuness, S. (2011). Space for transformation: Relational, dialogic pedagogy. <i>Journal of Transformative education</i>, 9(3), 183-197.</p> <p>Mezirow, J. (2000). <i>Learning as Transformation: Critical Perspectives on a Theory in Progress</i>. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.</p>	

²⁵ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

O’Sullivan, E. (1999). Transformative Learning: Educational Vision for the 21 st Century. Van Mierlo, B., Halbe, J., Beers, P. J., Scholz, G., & Vinke-de Kruijf, J. (2020). Learning about learning in sustainability transitions. <i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i> , 34, 251-254.
How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework
<p>Transformative learning as a lever for deliberate transformative change towards sustainability</p> <p>Since transformative learning affects the inner being in relation to the outer world, transformative learning can be viewed as a prerequisite in larger societal transitions that require a fundamental shift in thinking and acting (Woiwode et al., 2021). Within socio-ecological change towards sustainability, transformative learning is viewed as a lever for becoming an intentional, relational and agentic human being that is guided by an ethic of care and affective solidarity, a sense of justice and responsibility and by both the willingness and capability to act in accordance to one’s values (Souza et al., 2019). In environmental management, water resource management, forestry and biodiversity conservation, transformative learning often connects with social learning (Borie et al., 2020). When transformative learning converges with social learning and the development of transformative capacities and reflexivity in socio-ecological systems that include multiple stakeholders at different levels, it can become a catalyst for strengthening wider social movements and transitions towards sustainability. Scoones et al. (2020) provide some examples of transformative learning as an integral component of structural, systemic and enabling approaches to sustainability transformations in sustainable seed systems, wetland conservation and peri-urban development.</p> <p>Some scholars point at the need for alignment between taking on a transformative learning perspective and the kind of research that is done. Often community-based participatory research, research as co-design but also research as activism, are mentioned as methodological approaches that are congruent with transformative learning and capacity building that seeks to engage multiple people with different ontological and epistemological vantage points in transitioning towards a world that is more sustainable than the one currently in prospect (Lotz-Sisitka et al., 2016).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Borie, M., Gustafsson, K. M., Obermeister, N., Turnhout, E., & Bridgewater, P. (2020). Institutionalising reflexivity? Transformative learning and the Intergovernmental science-policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES). <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i>, 110, 71-76.</p> <p>Lotz-Sisitka, H., Belay Ali, M., Mphepo, G., Chaves, M., Macintyre, T., Pesanayi, T., Wals, A.E.J., Mukute, M., Kronlid, D., Tuan Tran, D., Joon, D., McGarry, D. (2016). Co-designing research on transgressive learning in times of climate change. <i>Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability</i> 20:50-55 · June 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.cosust.2016.04.004</p> <p>Scoones, I., Stirling, A., Abrol, D., Atela, J., Charli-Joseph, L., Eakin, H., ... & Yang, L. (2020). Transformations to sustainability: combining structural, systemic and enabling approaches. <i>Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability</i>, 42, 65-75.</p> <p>Souza, D. T., Wals, A. E. J., & Jacobi, P. R. (2019). Learning-based transformations towards sustainability: a relational approach based on Humberto Maturana and Paulo Freire. <i>Environmental Education Research</i>, 25(11), 1605-1619.</p> <p>Woiwode, C., Schöpke, N., Bina, O., Veciana, S., Kunze, I., Parodi, O., ... & Wamsler, C. (2021). Inner transformation to sustainability as a deep leverage point: fostering new avenues for change through dialogue and reflection. <i>Sustainability Science</i>, 16, 841-858.</p>

Table SM.3.41. Relational values and relationality

3.41. Relational values and Relationality	Main approach: Inner transformation
	Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation
<p>Relational values as a values category has a recent history in the environmental values literature and was popularized with the publication by Chan et al. (2016), also outlined in Jax et al. and Muraca (2013; 2011) or Chan et al. (2018). Based on a recent systematic review, Himes et al. (2024) propose the following meaning of relational values: “values of meaningful and often reciprocal human relationships—beyond</p>	

means to an end—with nature and among people through nature, where nature is often specified as a particular landscape, place, species, forest, etc.”

Relationality can be seen as an umbrella term for ways of understanding and studying human-nature relations in a non-dichotomous way (S. West et al., 2020). This includes both by drawing on Indigenous knowledge systems (Ingold, 2006) and ideas from ideas within philosophy such as process philosophy (Whitehead, 1978).

It is important to emphasize that even though the two are strongly associated, relational values and relationality are different concepts. Relationality is broader and can be associated with different knowledge systems or worldviews rather than understood as a values category (S. West et al., 2020). The ways in which relational values are assessed methodologically does not automatically align with relationality seen as a worldview, knowledge system or epistemological approach (Stålhammar & Thorén, 2019). The concept of relational values can be operationalized and seen on a spectrum of different interpretations of relationality, where some interpretations calls for a re-evaluation of how to think about human-nature relations and a call to go beyond Cartesian dualisms and subject-object dualisms (Muraca, 2011).

Key references:

- Chan KMA, et al. 2016. Opinion: Why protect nature? Rethinking values and the environment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113: 1462–1465.
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- Stålhammar, S. Thorén, H. (2019). Three perspectives on relational values of nature. *Sustainability Science*, 14:1201–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00718-4>
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- Whitehead AN. 1978. *Process and reality* Edited by Griffin, D.R. and Sherburne, D.W. New York: The Free Press.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

There are many approaches that are relevant for relational values and could be described as falling within this category, but that have not been described in this way in the literature. This refers to any approach that deals with the intentional strengthening of non-instrumental place-based human-nature relationships, where the focus is on the meaningful relation itself. There is a wide range of literature dealing with e.g., community-based conservation and management initiatives, environmental education, environmental psychology and nature connectedness, stewardship and governance and the more-than-human that would need to be systematically reviewed in order to give a better account of these implicit uses of the idea of relational value as a “theory of change”. A few notable examples include:

Connectedness with nature has been extensively studied in environmental psychology and is known to be a predictor for various forms of pro-environmental behaviour (Mackay & Schmitt, 2019). Zylstra et al. (2014) suggest a conceptual framework that comprises: i) information about nature; ii) experience in nature;

iii) connectedness with nature; iv) and committed connectedness with nature. “Committed” connectedness is the behavioural dimension that integrates all three spheres of connectedness i.e. cognitive, affective and experiential and is described as the sustain embodiment of connectedness that serves social and ecological communities through transformative leadership (Zylstra et al., 2014).

West et al (2018) weave together relational values and care to show how these approaches to stewardship can lead to ethical sustainable pathways.

Rights-based approaches (Chapron et al., 2019) can also be considered to be based on relational values or relationality and provide examples of how such values can lead to institutional and legal transformation.

Specific references:

Chapron, G., Epstein, Y. and López-Bao, J. V. (2019). A rights revolution for nature. *Science* 363, 1392–1393. doi: 10.1126/science.aav5601

Mackay, CM, Schmitt, MT (2019) Do people who feel connected to nature do more to protect it? A metaanalysis. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 65. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101323

West, S., Haider, L. J., Masterson, V., Enqvist, J. P., Svedin, U., & Tengö, M. (2018). Stewardship, care and relational values. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 35, 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.10.008>

Zylstra, M. J., Knight, A. T., Esler, K. J., & Le Grange, L. L. L. (2014). Connectedness as a Core Conservation Concern: An Interdisciplinary Review of Theory and a Call for Practice. *Springer Science Reviews*, 2(1), 119–143. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40362-014-0021-3>

4. Empowerment

Table SM.3.42. Political ecology 75

Table SM.3.43. Transformative spaces 77

Table SM.3.44. Three spheres of transformation..... 79

Table SM.3.45. Praxis 81

Table SM.3.46. Environmental history: Environmentalism of the poors and environmental coloniality 82

Table SM.3.47. Fractal agency 83

Table SM.3.48. Everyday resistance..... 84

Table SM.3.49. Feminist political ecology 85

Table SM.3.50. Decolonial feminisms and ecofeminisms 87

Table SM.3.42. Political ecology

3.42. Political ecology	Main approach: Empowerment
Political ecology combines the concerns of ecology and a broadly defined political economy (Blaikie et al., 1988). Political ecology approaches social-ecological change through the lens of metabolic production whereby societies constantly metabolize nature, producing new socionatures	Secondary approach: Structural

(Swyngedouw, 2004)²⁶. Society and nature are not considered antithetical entities but are intertwined in a relational perspective. A central analytical focus of political ecological research is how uneven power relationships manifest in uneven distributions of the costs and benefits of social-ecological change across social groups, class, race, gender, or region (Martinez-Alier, 2003). These uneven power relationships, together with a growing metabolism under capitalism, are considered to create ecological distribution conflicts (Scheidel et al., 2018). Such conflicts arise when environmental damage affects communities, who mobilize to either prevent it or to recoup the losses stemming from it. Ecological distribution conflicts are studied as symptoms of an unsustainable development model and as proof of the existence of conflicting visions around what constitutes a good life (Scheidel et al., 2018). This relates to another crucial theoretical and analytical standpoint of political ecology, namely that in any society there is an irreducible antagonism for alternative futures and forms of power distribution (Mouffe, 2005). This insight is encapsulated in the adjective political, which stands in contrast to apolitical ecologies that attribute environmental problems to a range of causes - biophysical or social - beyond the realm of collective choice. Political ecology thus aspires to politicize public debates and choices about desired socio-natures and the necessary transformative changes to produce them.

Key references:

Blaikie, P., Brookfield, H. 1988. *Land Degradation and Society*. Methuen, London.
 Martinez-Alier, J., 2002. *The environmentalism of the poor: a study of ecological conflicts and valuation*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham.
 Mouffe, C., 2005. *On the Political*. Routledge.
 Swyngedouw, E., 2004. *Social Power and the Urbanization of Water*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
 Temper, L., Demaria, F., Scheidel, A., Del Bene, D., Martinez-Alier, J., 2018. The Global Environmental Justice Atlas (EJAtlas): ecological distribution conflicts as forces for sustainability. *Sustain Sci* 13, 573–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0563-4>

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Political ecological research asks how intentional transformative change unfolds on the ground, which actors promote or resist it and how it is able (or not) to counteract the underlying causes of unsustainability (Otero & Nielsen, 2017). In so doing, political ecology shifts attention from purely technical, managerial and governance solutions to the political, institutional and cultural conditions facilitating or preventing the production of sustainable socio-natures. It is used to better understand the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline - mostly the expansion of capitalist social-ecological relationships - and to emphasize the need to transform these relationships in a democratic and sustainable way (Pichler et al., 2017). Together with other critical social theories, it can shed light on how to unmake capitalist relationships to facilitate the emergence of post-capitalist ones (Feola et al., 2021). Lawhon and Murphy (2012) identified four main contributions of political ecology to generating and navigating transformative change: reconsidering how and by whom an environmental problem is defined; considering a broader range of legitimate actors and knowledges; addressing power as embedded in relations and structures; and anticipating negative consequences of transformative change (e.g., inequality). Actors intentionally triggering transformative change include: environmental justice movements active against environmental damages, agroecological farmers and food sovereignty networks, social movements like feminism or degrowth, activists against infrastructure or fossil energy expansion, some public agencies, etc. Through their alternative practices and visions in the making, these actors address direct (e.g., land-use changes, climate change, pollution) and indirect (e.g., economy, values) drivers of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline. Political ecology conceptualizes their activity as a driver of transformative change because it brings to light, politicized and eventually overcomes prevailing social-ecological relationships. For example, by transforming ecological distribution conflicts into collective action, environmental justice movements can produce new metabolic regimes with lower and more even material and energetic flows (Scheidel et al., 2018).

Specific references:

²⁶ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Feola, G., Koretskaya, O., Moore, D., 2021. (Un)making in sustainability transformation beyond capitalism. *Global Environmental Change* 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102290>

Lawhon, M., Murphy, J.T., 2012. Socio-technical regimes and sustainability transitions Insights from political ecology. *Prog Hum Geogr* 36, 354–378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132511427960>

Otero, I., Nielsen, J.Ø., 2017. Coexisting with wildfire? Achievements and challenges for a radical social-ecological transformation in Catalonia (Spain). *Geoforum* 85, 234–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2017.07.020>

Pichler, M., Schaffartzik, A., Haberl, H., Görg, C., 2017. Drivers of society-nature relations in the Anthropocene and their implications for sustainability transformations. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, Open issue, part II 26–27, 32–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2017.01.017>

Scheidel, A., Temper, L., Demaria, F., Martínez-Alier, J., 2018. Ecological distribution conflicts as forces for sustainability: an overview and conceptual framework. *Sustain Sci* 13, 585–598. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-017-0519-0>

Table SM.3.43. Transformative spaces

<p>3.43. Transformative spaces</p>	<p>Main approach: Empowerment, Knowledge co-creation</p> <p>Secondary approach: Structural, Inner transformation</p>
<p>Transformative spaces are social processes that aim to bring about transformative changes towards sustainability. These spaces are created through transdisciplinary and action-oriented approaches that entail co-production focusing on participants' interactions to promote desired changes. As these deliberate endeavours aim to create conditions for change towards more sustainable pathways (in terms of legitimate, just, inclusive and democratic), it is essential to understand how such interventions may enable transformative change (Chambers et al., 2022).</p> <p>Transformative spaces are safe-enough collaborative settings where change agents working in transformation can experiment with new notions, framings and practices that might help in shifting social-ecological systems onto alternative pathways (Pereira, Drimie, et al., 2020). These processes actively seek to bring into dialogue different actors, with their own experiences, expertise and affections regarding a social-ecological problem or challenge (Drimie et al., 2018). Transformative spaces also enable reflection and reflexive learning, while reframing issues in ways that allow solutions to be co-created and co-implemented (Pereira, Drimie, et al., 2020). For this to be achieved, several transformative spaces seek a configuration of actors that is not diverse in terms of sectors, but diverse in terms of the participants' experiences. Such diversity might enable, together with a safe-enough atmosphere that is attentive to power asymmetries, to challenge the status quo if collectively perceived as unjust or not sustainable.</p> <p>Transformative spaces take different formats and are informed by distinct rationales because they are context-dependent (Asenbaum & Hanusch, 2021). Some of these have been inspired by the notion of 'laboratory', as a space for collaborative experimentation aimed at tackling complex social and environmental challenges (e.g., transition labs, change labs, social innovation labs). In particular, the transformation laboratories (T-Lab) approach has as its main goal to co-create a space where participants can test multiple solutions or strategies for change, which together could address a social-ecological challenge.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Chambers, J. M., C. Wyborn, N. L. Klenk, M. Ryan, A. Serban, N. J. Bennett, R. Brennan, L. Charli-Joseph, M. E. Fernández-Giménez, K. A. Galvin, B. E. Goldstein, T. Haller, R. Hill, C. Munera, J. L. Nel, H. Österblom, R. S. Reid, M. Riechers, M. Spierenburg, M. Tengö, E. Bennett, A. Brandeis, P. Chatterton, J. J. Cockburn, C. Cvitanovic, P. Dumrongrojwathana, A. Paz Durán, J. D. Gerber, J. M. H. Green, R. Gruby, A. M. Guerrero, A. I. Horcea-Milcu, J. Montana, P. Steyaert, J. G. Zaehring, A. T. Bednarek, K. Curran, S. J. Fada, J. Hutton, B.</p>	

Leimona, T. Pickering and R. Rondeau. 2022. Co-productive agility and four collaborative pathways to sustainability transformations. *Global Environmental Change* 72.

Pereira, L. M., T. Karpouzoglou, N. Frantzeskaki and P. Olsson. 2018. Guest Editorial, part of a Special Feature on Designing Transformative spaces for sustainability in social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society* 23(4).

Drimie S, Hamann R, Manderson AP, Mlondobozi N. 2018. Creating transformative spaces for dialogue and action: reflecting on the experience of the Southern Africa Food Lab. *Ecology and Society* 23.

Pereira L, Frantzeskaki N, Hebinck A, Charli-Joseph L, Drimie S, Dyer M, Eakin H, Galafassi D, Karpouzoglou T, Marshall F, Moore ML, Olsson P, Siqueiros-García JM, van Zwanenberg P, & Vervoort JM. 2020. Transformative spaces in the making: key lessons from nine cases in the Global South. *Sustainability Science* 15:161–178

Asenbaum H. & Hanusch F. 2021. (De)future democracy: Labs, playgrounds and ateliers as democratic innovations. *Futures* 134.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transformative spaces are created when certain enabling conditions are present. The T-Lab approach identifies six conditions to convene such a process: a dominant social-ecological situation to be challenged, dissension over the issue, unsuccessful experiments with alternative solutions, collective awareness of urgency for change, identification of an opportunity for transformation and the presence of a convener with significant ownership over the issue and strong motivation to help enable participants' agency (Pereira et al., 2021).

Transformative spaces enable novel reconstructions between actors and their environment through reframing. Reframing allows actors to identify new ways of acting in the system based on their own expertise. Capacities, knowledges and skills of participants are explored to find new points and possibilities for action that are meaningful for all involved. Reframing might also entail questioning and challenging internal and external power relations and dominant narratives to rethink new forms of social-ecological organization (F. Marshall et al., 2021). This implies implementing assemblages of diverse methodological frameworks and tools that are both context-based and attractive to maintain participants' engagement.

Reframing is central to this approach as it promotes the development of the actors' sense of agency, a critical ingredient in transformations (Chambers et al., 2022). Transformative spaces promote an increasing sense of agency where it appears to be lacking, particularly in actors and/or communities historically oppressed or silenced by groups with more power (J. Marshall et al., 2018; Temper et al., 2018). Reframing situates actors as part of the system and encourages a new re-appropriation of the system where interdependent relationships become more explicit. Interdependent relationships lead to a relational view of the world, which is crucial to recognize deeper causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, include the more-than-human in the circle of concern and propose strategies that include the diversity of living forms and ways of being in transformative decision-making.

Specific references:

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Table SM.3.44. Three spheres of transformation

<p>3.44. Three spheres of transformation</p>	<p>Main approach: Empowerment</p>
<p>Secondary approach: Structural, Systems, Inner</p>	
<p>Transformations to an equitable and sustainable world occurs through simultaneous and interrelated changes in form, structure and meaning-making. These three interconnected dimensions constitute the three spheres of transformation, referred to as the practical, political and personal spheres (O’Brien, 2018).</p>	
<p>The practical sphere focuses on actions and interventions that contribute directly to measurable outcomes and tends to emphasize technical and behavioural approaches to change that are aligned with objectives and goals, such as the 23 targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.</p>	
<p>The political sphere refers to the structures and systems that influence or govern how society is organized. This includes the social and cultural norms, rules, regulations and institutions that reflect the values that are prioritized and the goals that are pursued. They also influence how solutions are negotiated, decided and implemented and by whom, recognizing conflicting interests, power differences and the impact of social movements.</p>	
<p>The personal sphere refers to individual and shared beliefs, values, worldviews and paradigms that influence how people perceive, define, or constitute systems and structures and how they relate to each other and to nature. The description of the three spheres as separate distinguishes the different dimensions, but in reality they are always integrated.</p>	
<p>Transformative potential is seldom realized when attention to any single sphere is ignored. For example, a focus on the practical sphere alone often overlooks the social, cultural and political dimensions of change in the political sphere, such as power dynamics within economic, political and socio-ecological systems and the diversity of beliefs, values and worldviews in the personal sphere that influence these dynamics (O’Brien & Sygna, 2013).</p>	
<p>By addressing the three spheres simultaneously, actors can identify the practical outcomes that are desired, the political barriers to transformation and opportunities to collaborate and strategically design and develop strategies to overcome them by connecting with the personal sphere. The three spheres of transformation focus on developing processes and patterns that shift systems and cultures across scales, recognizing the power and potential of individuals and groups to contribute to change across multiple spheres of influence.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p>	
<p>O’Brien, K. and Linda Sygna. 2013. “Responding to Climate Change: The Three Spheres of Transformation.” In Proceedings of Transformation in a Changing Climate, 16–23. Oslo, Norway: University of Oslo.</p>	
<p>O’Brien, Karen. 2018. “Is the 1.5°C Target Possible? Exploring the Three Spheres of Transformation.” Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Sustainability governance and transformation 2018, 31: 153–60. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.04.010.</p>	
<p>O’Brien, Karen. 2021. You Matter More Than You Think: Quantum Social Change for a Thriving World. cCHANGE Press.</p>	
<p>O’Brien, Karen, Dina Hestad, Irmelin Gram-Hanssen and Linda Sygna. 2022. “Responding to Biodiversity Loss in a Changing Climate: An Integrative Approach to Transformative Change.” Report commissioned by the Norwegian Environmental Agency. Oslo, Norway: cCHANGE, 2022.</p>	
<p>https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/publikasjoner/2022/juni/responding-to-biodiversity-loss-in-a-changing-climate-an-integrative-approach-to-transformative-change/.</p>	

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How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

The three spheres of transformation framework is based on a "conscious full spectrum response" model developed by Dr. Monica Sharma and tested in over 60 countries (Sharma, 2017). This is a framework for both understanding and action, with the goal of generating shifts in systems and cultures to produce measurable results. It is a framework for action that recognizes the role of individual and collective agency in systems change. However, rather than perceiving individuals as objects to be changed in the name of a particular goal, this approach recognizes that all individuals, regardless of their position, rank, role, experience, or authority, possess the capacity to lead transformations, often in partnership with communities, groups and governments (O'Brien, 2021; Sharma, 2017; Thiermann & Sheate, 2020). Strategic action is not confined to the upper tiers of hierarchies in politics, business, or organizations, or ascribed to an abstract concept of social movements; rather, it includes the individuals and groups who have courage and capacities to overcome fragmented approaches and to do things differently. Individual agency, collective agency and political agency is particularly effective when grounded in universal values that apply to all, such as equity, justice and dignity (O'Brien et al., 2022; Sharma, 2017).

Acknowledging the multifaceted nature of transformation, a central challenge lies in creating an enabling environment for individuals and groups to engage comprehensively with all three transformation spheres. In the personal sphere, transformation results when individuals and organizations feel empowered to engage in shifting structures and systems in their spheres of influence and to create optimal conditions for generating practical results across all scales. Transformative change also involves reflecting on the collective values that reinforce the root causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline, including those that underpin actions in everyday life, work and projects. In the political sphere, transformative change involves identifying specific barriers to change and being clear about which existing systems maintain the status quo and what specifically needs to shift. Promoting cultural and systemic changes and their practical manifestations involves the strategic design and implementation of projects, policies and plans based on what matters deeply to all actors. The Three Spheres framework emphasizes the importance of each actor's quality of agency; it recognizes that how people show up makes a difference to processes of transformative change (O'Brien, 2021; O'Brien et al., 2023).

Specific references:

- Gosnell, Hannah, Nicholas Gill and Michelle Voyer. 2019. "Transformational Adaptation on the Farm: Processes of Change and Persistence in Transitions to 'Climate-Smart' Regenerative Agriculture." *Global Environmental Change* 59.
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- Jacobson, Lisa, Jonas Åkerman, Matteo Giusti and Avit K. Bhowmik. 2020. "Tipping to Staying on the Ground: Internalized Knowledge of Climate Change Crucial for Transformed Air Travel Behavior." *Sustainability* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12051994>
- Palomo, Ignacio, Bruno Locatelli, Iago Otero, Matthew Colloff, Emilie Crouzat, Aida Cuni-Sanchez, Erik Gómez-Baggethun, et al. 2021. "Assessing Nature-Based Solutions for Transformative Change." *One Earth* 4, no. 5: 730–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.04.013>
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Table SM.3.45. Praxis

3.45. Praxis	Main approach: Empowerment Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Inner, Structural
<p>The concept of praxis has a rich theoretical tradition in theories of social change. It challenges the duality between theory and practice or knowing and doing (Kilminster, 1977) and underlines that change occurs through ongoing dialectics between knowledge and practice. In the Marxist and Hegelian traditions, praxis included three main components: 1) actors' critical consciousness; 2) actors' mobilization; and 3) actors' collective and multilateral action to reconstruct those social arrangements and themselves (Bernstein, 1971). Praxis challenges the idea that all change is predetermined by structural forces and emphasises that change is mutually constituted by the interplay of structure and agency as also elucidated in structuration theory, which unpacks how social order is produced, reproduced or subverted (Giddens, 1984). Freire (2000), however, takes an emancipatory understanding of praxis and links it to self-conscious social actions. Thus, praxis is an embedded, reflexive and engaged process of change aimed towards the transformation of the self and the wider social and institutional arrangements, in an attempt to reconfigure the dominant development trajectory (Mehta et al., 2021; O'Brien & Sygna, 2013; Seo & Creed, 2002). The individual is a partially autonomous actor imbued with an agency to change (through contestations, alliance building, etc.) but also constrained by structural forces that prevent action/maintain the status quo. Human praxis presupposes a change in social arrangement or their reconstruction through the agency of individuals. It mediates between social contradictions (produced as an outcome of development processes) which can potentially play a fundamental role in driving change (Seo & Creed, 2002). Key to transformative praxis is a better understanding of how the agency can be strengthened to bring about structural alterations and consequently inform wider societal changes. In this respect, it can be explored as the capability to change (Sen, 2001) linked to values of justice and equity.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Freire, P. (2000) <i>Pedagogy of the Oppressed</i>. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.</p> <p>Seo, M. G., & Creed, W. D. (2002). Institutional contradictions, praxis and institutional change: A dialectical perspective. <i>Academy of Management Review</i>, 27(2), 222-247.</p> <p>Giddens A (1984) <i>The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration</i>. Berkeley: University of California Press.</p> <p>Kilminster R (1977) <i>Praxis and Method</i>. London: Methuen</p> <p>Sen A (1999): <i>Development as Freedom</i>. Oxford: University of Oxford Press</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>For any meaningful transformation to occur, engagement with change at the individual, collective (societal scale or in particular sites) and institutional levels is needed. In several contexts, biodiversity loss and nature's decline are induced/exacerbated by top-down and aggressive neoliberal practices that have marginalized vulnerable populations through dispossession, loss of habitats, identity and well-being producing contradictions across scales, especially at the local level. Human agency is central to responses to environmental change and crises (K. Brown & Westaway, 2011) and constitutes the personal sphere through which transformations can be motivated (O'Brien & Sygna, 2013). Thus, it is important to engage with how and whether practices of coproducing socio-ecological knowledge (on agriculture, livestock, livelihoods and ecosystem conservation) can enhance the agency of people to transform existing socio-political structures of power and recognition (Mehta et al., 2021). In these</p>	

contexts, deliberate/intentional transformative initiatives can serve to counter entrenched injustices and political exclusion in current systems of knowledge-making, governance and valuation (B. Burke & Heynen, 2014). While focus through specific initiatives can facilitate transformative pathways, scaling up often meets with various challenges because of structural factors such as systemic power, knowledge politics and incumbent agency. This contradiction can lead to new alliances - across classes and categories of people, species, knowledge groups as well as relations of power and dominance- which can scan for windows of opportunity to push for change. Such alliances and their initiatives serve as ‘seeds’ or ‘socio-ecological bright spots’ that can improve environmental conditions and human well-being (Bennett et al., 2016). Deliberate transformative change implies bottom-up processes which centre the agency and voice of communities that are most affected by the climate and biodiversity crisis. It is not linear and is layered with multiple alignments and contradictions. Local level solidarities can emerge in the process which lift hidden perspectives and invisible voices (of women, children and young people) but if done hastily, these can lead to the reproduction of dominant voices and inequalities revealing the dark side of transformation (Blythe et al., 2018).

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- Bennett, E. M., Solan, M., Biggs, R., McPhearson, T., Norström, A. V., Olsson, P., ... & Xu, J. (2016). Bright spots: seeds of a good Anthropocene. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 14(8), 441-448.

Table SM.3.46. Environmental history: Environmentalism of the poors and environmental coloniality

3.46. Environmental history: Environmentalism of the poors and environmental coloniality	Main approach: Empowerment
Secondary approach: Structural	
<p>Environmental history has the potential to transform the understanding of the human past. By focusing on the impact of human activity on the biosphere, the environmental perspective not only opens new topics of investigation but also changes the understanding of the emergence of the modern world (E. Burke & Pomeranz, 2009). The environmentalism of the poors arises from social conflicts over environmental rights or titles because of the risks of pollution and the loss of access to natural resources and environmental services (Martinez-Alier, 2003). Environmental coloniality²⁷ helps explain injustice through history (Carney, 2011; Ferdinand, 2019; Grove, 1996). Environmental history allows to understand past environmental cultures and old, new and hybrid environmental knowledges. The transmission, memory and environmental oblivion of each culture can, thanks to history, be recovered as a powerful socio-cultural driver.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Burke III, E., & Pomeranz, K. (Éds.). (2009). <i>The Environment and World History</i>. University of California Press.</p>	

²⁷ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

<p>Grove, R. H. (1995). <i>Green Imperialism : Colonial Expansion, Tropical Island Edens and the Origins of Environmentalism, 1600–1860</i> (First Edition edition). Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Carney, J. A., & Rosomoff, R. N. (2009). <i>In the Shadow of Slavery. Africa’s Botanical Legacy in the Atlantic World</i>. University of California Press.</p> <p>Ferdinand, M. (2019). <i>Une écologie décoloniale. Penser l’écologie depuis le monde caribéen</i>. Seuil.</p> <p>Martinez Alier, J. (2002). <i>The environmentalism of the Poor, A Study of Ecological Conflicts and Valuation</i>. Edward Elgar Publishing.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p> <p>According to environmental history and frameworks of environmental conflicts and environmental injustice and inequalities, deliberate transformative change occurs when all actors involved in an environmental conflict become aware of the role they have played in environmental degradation. Such transformative change is often translated into agreements between the parties involved through environmental mediation. It is also often translated into legal agreements or public policies when the actors include public or legal administrations. On the other hand, the awareness gained through history and shared environmental memory is transmitted through social communication and education (Gadgil & Guha, 1995).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Escobar, A. (2008). <i>Territories of difference. Place, movements, life, redes</i>. Duke University Press.</p> <p>Cariño, M., & Ortega Santos, A. (Éds.). (2014). <i>Oasis Sudcalifornianos. Para un rescate de la sustentabilidad local</i>. Universidad de Granada</p> <p>Funes Monzote, R. (2008). <i>Farming like we’re here to stay : The mixed farming alternative for Cuba</i> [Phd, S.n.]. http://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/wurpubs/369587</p> <p>Gadgil, M., & Guha, R. (1995). <i>Ecology and Equity. The use and abuse of nature in contemporary India</i>. Routledge.</p> <p>González de Molina, M. (2020). <i>The Social Metabolism of Spanish Agriculture, 1900–2008 The Mediterranean Way Towards Industrialization</i> (1st ed. 2020.). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20900-1</p>

Table SM.3.47. Fractal agency

3.47. Fractal agency	Main approach: Empowerment
	Secondary approach: Inner transformation
<p>Fractal agency, a concept proposed by O'Brien et al.(2023), is an integrative and empowering approach to scaling transformations to sustainability that emphasizes the inter- and intra-connectedness of individual and collective actions within complex systems. A fractal approach focuses on generating patterns based on values that apply to all, such as equity and dignity. It acknowledges that addressing complex challenges like biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and climate change implies aligning and leveraging agency across multiple levels and scales, from the micro to the macro. Fractal agency can be understood as both a quality and a capacity that allows individuals, regardless of their position, educational background, role, experience, or formal authority, to generate new patterns (Sharma, 2017). A fractal approach can be tailored to specific contexts, while still being strategically aligned to transform relationships and systems that are inequitable or unsustainable. Fractal agency proposes that thoughts, decisions and actions based on oneness can generate entangled patterns that replicate across scales (O’Brien, 2021). By recognizing that values expressed through actions at all levels can have ripple effects throughout a system, fractal agency encourages the empowerment of diverse stakeholders to contribute to sustainability solutions while also ensuring accountability and responsibility.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>O’Brien, K. (2021). <i>You Matter More Than You Think: Quantum Social Change for a Thriving World</i>. Cchange.</p>	

<p>O'Brien, K., Carmona, R., Gram-Hanssen, I., Hochachka, G., & Sygna, L. (2023). Fractal Approaches to Scaling Transformations to Sustainability. <i>AMBIO</i>, 52(9), 1448–1461. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01873-w</p> <p>Sharma, M. (2017). <i>Radical Transformational Leadership: Strategic Action for Change Agents</i>. North Atlantic Books.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>A fractal approach to scaling draws on the strategic and practical "conscious full spectrum response" model for transformations developed by Sharma (2007, 2017) and the "Three Spheres of Transformation" framework proposed by O'Brien and Sygna (2013). This approach shifts the focus from scaling through "things" (e.g., technologies, behaviours, projects) to scaling through a quality of agency based on universal values – i.e., values that apply to all, with no one excluded (Sharma, 2017). Fractal approaches recognize that agency can influence different levels, from individual to collective and global scales, in a recursive manner – i.e. when the same principles and values are applied at different levels. It represents a quality of agency that generates self-similar, fractal-like patterns (O'Brien et al., 2023). Fractal agency is based on four fundamental steps. These steps are not sequential but implemented simultaneously to address the practical, political and personal spheres of transformation in an integrative manner. Step 1: Recognize the universal values that are important and identify which principles to follow. Step 2: Identify how the current problems manifest in practice and decide what visible changes and measurable results are desired. Step 3: Identify which current systems maintain the status quo and the cultural and systemic changes that need to occur for measurable outcomes to be realized in an equitable and sustainable way. Step 4: Identify and undertake specific actions to shift existing patterns based on universal values, both in the short and long term.</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>O'Brien, K., & Sygna, L. (2013). Responding to climate change: The three spheres of transformation. <i>Proceedings of Transformation in a Changing Climate</i>, 16–23.</p> <p>O'Brien, K., Carmona, R., Gram-Hanssen, I., Hochachka, G., & Sygna, L. (2023). Fractal Approaches to Scaling Transformations to Sustainability. <i>AMBIO</i>, 52(9), 1448–1461. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01873-w</p> <p>Sharma, M. (2007). Personal to planetary transformation. <i>Kosmos Journal</i>. http://www.kosmosjournal.org/articles/personal-to-planetary-transformation</p> <p>Sharma, M. (2017). <i>Radical Transformational Leadership: Strategic Action for Change Agents</i>. North Atlantic Books.</p>	

Table SM.3.48. Everyday resistance

3.48. Everyday resistance	Main approach: Empowerment
	Secondary approach: Structural
<p>The term resistance is used to describe oppositional acts that can be organized and loud, such as protest or demonstrations, as well as more quiet forms, such as foot-dragging, feigned ignorance, or sabotage (Baaz & Lilja, 2017; Johansson & Vinthagen, 2016). While political scientists interested in social change have shown the links between organized resistance and social transformations, less attention has been given to the more ordinary and quiet forms of resistance used by groups in vulnerable situations that lack the time and possibilities to engage in social movements or revolutions (J. C. Scott, 1987). Thus, the term everyday resistance has been used to describe oppositional acts that “require little or no coordination or planning; they make use of implicit understandings and informal networks; they often represent a form of individual self-help; they typically avoid any direct, symbolic confrontation with authority” (J. C. Scott, 1987). In Scott’s view, everyday forms of resistance are the ordinary means for marginalized groups to have a political voice (J. C. Scott, 1987).</p> <p>A resistance lens can help us to uncover bottom-up social needs and aspirations that can determine the possibilities for fair transformations (Falla et al., 2024). According to Bayat, resistance has a transformative power when groups in vulnerable situations use it to make advances on the powerful to survive and improve their lives, what he calls “quiet encroachment of the ordinary” (Bayat, 2000). However, Falla in line with</p>	

<p>Scott argues that acts of resistance, even when they do not result in large social transformations, have an important value to assert the agency and freedom of marginalized groups (Falla et al., 2024; Vargas & Urinbojev, 2015).</p>
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Bayat, A. (2000). From ‘dangerous classes’ to ‘quiet rebels’: Politics of the urban subaltern in the Global South. <i>International Sociology</i>, 15(3), 533–557.</p> <p>Falla, A. M. V., Brink, E., & Boyd, E. (2024). Quiet resistance speaks: A global literature review of the politics of popular resistance to climate adaptation interventions. <i>World Development</i>, 177.</p> <p>Johansson, A., & Vinthagen, S. (2016). Dimensions of Everyday Resistance: An Analytical Framework. <i>Critical Sociology</i>, 42(3).</p> <p>Lilja, M., Baaz, M., Schulz, M., & Vinthagen, S. (2017). How Resistance Encourages Resistance: Theorizing the Nexus Between Power, ‘Organised Resistance’ and ‘Everyday Resistance.’ <i>Journal of Political Power</i>, 10(1).</p> <p>Scott, J. C. (1985). <i>Weapons of the weak: Everyday forms of peasant resistance</i>. Yale university Press.</p>
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>
<p>Authors studying everyday forms of resistance pay attention to social change and transformations that occur in a more silent, but effective way (Bayat, 2000; Falla et al., 2024; J. C. Scott, 1987). They look into the quiet forms used by marginalized groups to make a living, assert their autonomy and oppose marginalization and exclusionary policies without having to confront the authorities. While everyday forms of resistance may be combined with other more louds forms of opposition such as riots, protest and legal actions, what allows for long term transformation is the fact that actions are embedded in people’s everyday lives. Examples of acts of everyday resistance that address the causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline include, farmers in Tanzania complying only on the sides of the roads to a ban on local varieties that require more water than the adapted variety of crops (Naess, 2013), farmers in Kenya renting wells and lending land to nomadic groups in times of drought, despite a national ban (Eriksen & Lind, 2009), community members in São Tomé and Príncipe gossiping about an adaptation project that only benefits certain groups (Mikulewicz, 2019) and farmers in Burkina Faso ridiculed those who worked for projects that were not in accordance to the traditional way of life (Nielsen & Reenberg, 2010). Another relevant examples is the case of residents of the Pacific islands resisting the narrative about “sinking islands” claiming a dignifying form of migration while blaming polluters countries (McNamara & Farbotko, 2017).</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Eriksen, S., & Lind, J. (2009). Adaptation as a Political Process: Adjusting to Drought and Conflict in Kenya’s Drylands. <i>Environmental Management</i>, 43(5). https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-008-9189-0</p> <p>Henrique, K. P., & Tschakert, P. (2019). Contested grounds: Adaptation to flooding and the politics of (in)visibility in São Paulo’s eastern periphery. <i>Geoforum</i>, 104, 181–192. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2019.04.026</p> <p>McNamara, K. E., & Farbotko, C. (2017). Resisting a ‘Doomed’ Fate: An analysis of the Pacific Climate Warriors. <i>Australian Geographer</i>, 48(1). https://doi.org/10.1080/00049182.2016.1266631</p> <p>Naess, L. O. (2013). The role of local knowledge in adaptation to climate change. <i>Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change</i>, 4(2). https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.204</p> <p>Phiri, K., Dube, T., Moyo, P., Ncube, C., & Ndlovu, S. (2019). Small grains “resistance”? Making sense of Zimbabwean smallholder farmers’ cropping choices and patterns within a climate change context. <i>Cogent Social Sciences</i>, 5(1). https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2019.1622485</p>

Table SM.3.49. Feminist political ecology

<p>3.49. Feminist political ecology</p>	<p>Main approach: Empowerment, Inner transformation</p> <p>Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation</p>
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Feminist political ecology is a diverse literature, grounded in feminist theories of power and inequality, that shows how social and environmental change emerge from histories of colonial capitalist exploitation and their on-going legacies (Mollett & Faria, 2018). It is distinguished from other socio-environmental theories by its attention to how power operates in the everyday, through subjectivities and scales, creating social and geopolitical inequalities based on gender, race, class, caste, ability and other embodied differences (Mollett & Faria, 2018; Sultana, 2021). Power is not simply ‘power over’ but also ‘power to’ and ‘power for’. Feminist political ecology shows how subjectivities shape uneven exposure to environmental hazards (Di Chiro, 2021; Gergan, 2020; Lyons, 2023), access to, distribution of and control over resources and knowledge of environmental change (Harcourt & Nelson, 2015; Sultana, 2021). Feminist political ecology is most often grounded in performative and emergent ontologies, meaning that relations are never fixed, rather individuals are subjected in multiple ways that change over time, scale and space (Mollett & Faria, 2018). Research attention is thus placed on the conflicts, cooperation, spaces and temporalities through which societies and environments co-evolve.

Some feminist political ecology theorists have shown how environments (or non-humans), entangle with power to shape subjectivities, meaning that some people have, for example, greater affective relations with plants and other species (Durand & Sundberg, 2022), environmental destruction shows up in terrestrial and embodied forms (Gergan, 2020; Harcourt & Nelson, 2015; Lyons, 2023) and affective relations are vital to how people cooperate over their environments (González-Hidalgo & Zografos, 2020; Nightingale et al., 2022). These insights have been combined with anti- and de-colonial approaches to environmental change which argue that it is not just humans that impact the environment, but rather that environments are also agents of change, reshaping subjectivities and understandings of environment, bringing species and human communities into particular relations with petrol capitalism (Lyons, 2023), hydropower (Gergan, 2020), climate change (Nightingale et al., 2022) and plants (Durand & Sundberg, 2022). These relations change the geopolitics of hydropower in South Asia (Gergan, 2020), botany knowledge production and conservation in Chiapas, Mexico (Durand & Sundberg, 2022), or how oil companies are held to account when territories are allowed to speak in courtrooms as the case of transitional justice in Colombia (Lyons, 2023). This kind of theoretical move is thus not simply about decentring humans as agents of change and transformation, but a more radical insistence on how human actions have affective consequences for people, other species and territories, wherein local actions spill over to affect wider territories and geopolitics (Di Chiro, 2021; Durand & Sundberg, 2022; Gergan, 2020; Harcourt & Nelson, 2015; Lyons, 2023; Mollett & Faria, 2018; Sultana, 2021).

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How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Many feminist political ecology scholars have argued that the analytical and political tools outlined above offer possibilities for transformation. The underlying ontological mechanisms differ from mainstream transformation debates, even if some principles appear similar. Transformation is not an end state, rather it is a radical reshaping of current social, political, economic-environmental relations through which change occurs (Di Chiro, 2021; Lyons, 2023). Di Chiro and the activist networks she is engaged with have argued for the importance of imagination to enact desired relations, exchanges and values in the present. This kind of environmental futuring rests upon a recognition of the histories of injustice and environmental harm that shape the future (Lyons, 2023) and kinship with all of life, regardless of whether transformation occurs (Gergan, 2020). This kind of “...critical optimism is not passive, distanced, wishing for solar panels, carbon markets and biodegradable plastics to come to the rescue; it is an active, critical and embodied form of hopefulness, it means seeing your own body, your own lifeworld in action” (emphasis in original) (Di Chiro, 2021). Feminist political ecology shows that it is not possible to promote ‘environmental

subjectivities' which remain stable, or which are always beneficial. Rather, coalitions for change come together and are successful for a period of time, but in the absence of renewal, tend to be co-opted by elites (Gergan, 2020), become dormant (Durand & Sundberg, 2022), or are subsumed by other coalitions intent on undermining their goals and more adept at moving across scales (Lyons, 2023). Affective relations show great potential for helping to create coalitions for change, at least in the short term. As Nightingale et al show (2022), it was a shared sense of grief and desires for the future of their children that allowed diverse people to work together for climate change adaptation. But these efforts are always transitory. Transformation in a feminist political ecology frame implies continual engagement, negotiation of complex relations of power and history and a radical reimagination of how inclusions and exclusions are addressed by society.

Specific references:

Di Chiro, G. (2021). Making Ecofeminism(s) Matter...Again. *Women's Studies*, 50(8), 820-828. doi:10.1080/00497878.2021.1986396

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Table SM.3.50. Decolonial feminisms and ecofeminisms

3.50. Decolonial feminisms and ecofeminisms	Main approach: Empowerment Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Inner transformation
<p>Decolonial ecofeminisms focus on the intersection of environmental issues, feminism and decolonization efforts. They also include non-essentialist (Mies & Shiva, 2004) and 'survivalist' feminisms (Svampa, 2015). They form a movement to defend territories that "is born out of obligation and not by choice" (Svampa, 2015). Decolonial ecofeminisms draw on decolonial theory, decolonial environmental justice, political ecology and degrowth theories to critique and resist the impacts of colonization on nature and people. In line with critical currents of political ecology and environmental justice, they aim to redistribute power, highlighting counter-hegemonic projects with a focus on transformation (Curiel Pichardo, 2007; Espinosa Miñoso, 2016). Such projects have an anti-essentialist approach; that is, they question the naturalisation of the links between white men and culture and between Indigenous Peoples and women and nature. While the protection of territory arises from the close relationship of communities with these, it is also a product of ontological resistance to patriarchy²⁸ and colonialism (Sanchez De Jaegher, 2020).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Curiel, O. (2007). Crítica poscolonial desde las prácticas políticas del feminismo antirracista. <i>Nómadas</i>, 26, 92–110.</p> <p>Espinosa, Y. (2016). De por qué es necesario un feminismo descolonial: Diferenciación, dominación co-constitutiva de la modernidad occidental y el fin de la política de identidad. <i>Solar</i>, 13(1), 171.</p> <p>Mies, M., & Shiva, V. (2004). Del porqué escribimos este libro juntas. In V. Vazquez & M. Velzaquez (Eds.), <i>Miradas al futuro. Hacia la construcción de sociedades sustentables con equidad de género</i>. UNAM.</p>	

²⁸ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Sanchez, C. (2019). Defendiendo mundos y visionando la justicia ambiental: ¿El surgimiento del ecofeminismo mapuche? In M. Aparicio & A. Varo (Eds.), *Resistencias indígenas. Contribuciones del X Encuentro Multidisciplinar de Pueblo Indígenas*. Documenta Universitaria.

Svampa, M. (2015). *Feminismos del Sur y ecofeminismo*. Nueva Sociedad, 256.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Decolonial, non-essentialist ecofeminisms focus on environmental justice, gender equality and decolonization simultaneously. Following decolonial theory, ecofeminisms argue that the first step to decolonization is dismantling those naturalized patterns of power and domination that exploit nature and marginalized communities (Cumes, 2009; Curiel Pichardo, 2007). They envision alternative economic and governing systems with justice at their core. These movements advocate for just transformations that challenge dominant systems of power and exploitation by recognizing the interconnectedness of social, environmental and political issues (Mies & Shiva, 2004). By centring the experiences, struggles and knowledge of Indigenous Peoples, women and other marginalized groups, these movements seek that diverse communities and peoples actively participate in decision-making processes and contribute to defining and implementing holistic solutions to the crisis (López-Serrano, 2023). Such solutions are constructed at the intersection of vindicating traditional epistemes with the construction of knowledge situated in the historical experience of subalternization. The recognition of such knowledge and experiences enables the development of new leaderships based on a ‘potentially radical communal ethos’ (Svampa, 2015) that aims to transform the relationship between humans and between humans and nature.

Specific references:

Curiel, O. (2007). Crítica poscolonial desde las prácticas políticas del feminismo antirracista. *Nómadas*, 26, 92–110.

Cumes, A. (2009). Multiculturalismo, género y feminismos: Mujeres diversas, luchas complejas. In A. Pequeño (Ed.), *Participación y políticas de mujeres indígenas en contextos latinoamericanos recientes*. FLACSO.

López-Serrano, L. (2023). Indigenous Ecofeminism? Decolonial Practices and Indigenous Resurgence in Lee Maracle’s Works. *Canada and Beyond: A Journal of Canadian Literary and Cultural Studies*, 12, 85-101.

Mies, M., & Shiva, V. (2004). Del porqué escribimos este libro juntas. In V. Vazquez & M. Velzaquez (Eds.), *Miradas al futuro. Hacia la construcción de sociedades sustentables con equidad de género*. UNAM.

Svampa, M. (2015). *Feminismos del Sur y ecofeminismo*. Nueva Sociedad, 256.

5. Knowledge co-creation

Table SM.3.51. Three horizons	88
Table SM.3.52. Ethnoecology	90
Table SM.3.53. Transformative sustainability science	92
Table SM.3.54. Participatory research	94
Table SM.3.55. Transformative education	95
Table SM.3.56. Local Biodiversity Outlook transitions	97
Table SM.3.57. Transdisciplinary research	99
Table SM.3.58. Transformative innovation policy	100

Table SM.3.51. Three horizons

3.51. Three horizons	Main approach: Knowledge co-creation Secondary approach: Systems, Empowerment
<p>Three horizons is a framework and practice for exploring the future and change, from the established patterns of activity of the first horizon, to new patterns in the third, through transitional activities in the second (Curry & Hodgson, 2008; Sharpe et al., 2016).</p> <p>The central idea of three horizons is that it draws attention to the three horizons as existing always in the present moment and that there is evidence about the future in how people (including ourselves) are behaving now. The outcome of three horizons work is a map of transformative potential which enables a group to act with more skill, freedom and creativity in the present, both individually and together.</p> <p>The first horizon – H1 is the dominant system at present. It represents ‘business-as-usual’. These systems are relied on as being stable and reliable, but as the world changes, aspects of business-as-usual begin to feel out of place or no longer fit for purpose. Eventually, business-as-usual will always be superseded by new patterns of activity.</p> <p>The third horizon – H3 emerges as the long-term successor to business-as-usual. It grows from fringe activity in the present that introduces completely new ways of doing.</p> <p>The second horizon – H2 is a pattern of transition activities and innovations, people trying things out in response to the ways in which the landscape is changing. Some of these will be sustaining innovations and will be absorbed into the H1 systems to improve them and prolong their life, while some will be transformative and pave the way for the emergence of the radically different H3 systems.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Curry, A., Hodgson, A., 2008. Seeing in Multiple Horizons: Connecting Futures to Strategy. <i>J. Futur. Stud.</i> 13, 1–20.</p> <p>Sharpe, B., Hodgson, A., Leicester, G., Lyon, A., Fazey, I., 2016. Three horizons: a pathways practice for transformation. <i>Ecol. Soc.</i> 21.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>The three horizons framework has no commitment to any particular view of how transformative change occurs except that change is viewed systemically as a transition from the first to third horizon patterns of activity. It is intended for use by those who have some concern with an issue and agency with respect to bringing about the change they desire.</p> <p>The three horizons are understood not only as descriptive of patterns of activity but also as ‘voices,’ or three perspectives, on the future. The H1 voice is the voice of the manager. It talks about maintaining the current system and usually expresses concern. The H2 voice is the voice of the entrepreneur. It talks about trying something different and often expresses a combination of urgency and frustration. The H3 voice is the voice of the visionary. It talks about dreams and deep aspirations. These are typical ways in which each position ‘hears’ the other voices, as both positive and negative. Using Three Horizons effectively means becoming aware of all of these perspectives and working with them to shift the conversation in a generative direction (Sharpe et al., 2016).</p> <p>The model offers a simple way into a conversation about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the dominant system and the challenges to its sustainability into the future, i.e. the case for change (H1); • the desirable future state, the ideal system desired and of which elements can be identified in the present that give encouragement and inspiration (H3); • the nature of the tensions and dilemmas between H3 vision and H1 reality and the processes of change, new ways of working, new capacities, new structures, required to navigate the transition between them. <p>Application of the framework provides five important insights about how transformation can be supported. First, it highlights that maintaining transformative intent in any change process is critical⁴. This may seem obvious, but most change reinforces a status quo and does not lead to something fundamentally new. Consequently, it is easy to lose sight of transformation.</p> <p>Second, most people struggle to envision a radically different third horizon. Considerable effort is thus needed to establish radically different, ambitious, visions. The concept of regenerative futures is useful here, with such systems having dynamics that ‘spiral up’ environmental and human benefit (Buckton et</p>	

al., 2023). Using the regenerative concept helps push envisioning to include a fundamentally different set of underlying dynamics. This helps with issues like biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, where new human-environment relationships are required.

Third, three horizons highlights the importance of working with existing activities already supporting transformation, rather than necessarily trying to create new ones (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Deliberate transformation can thus be viewed as a process of cohering systemic activities, so they reinforce each other.

Fourth, multiple forms of governance are needed to ensure: the current system does not collapse (H1); entrepreneurial, high risk, activities aimed at change are supported (H2); long-term explorations can thrive (H3); and that resources from the present system are re-allocated to create the new (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Ultimately, provision of hospices for the old and midwifery for the new are needed for such re-allocation to occur (Leicester & O’Hara, 2022).

Finally, using three horizons highlights that deliberate transformation along the idealized pattern of the three horizons framework is possible, but very rare (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Most human endeavours fail to support transformation because they lack the strategic action needed to overcome the strong pull of the existing system and because there is usually a limited mandate – publicly and politically – for genuine change to occur (Fazey & Leicester, 2022). Three Horizons practice, while having limits, has at least been developed with such challenges in mind. It enhances consciousness about how the present gives rise to the future and how action can be oriented for a fundamentally new future to arise.

Specific references:

Sharpe, B., Hodgson, A., Leicester, G., Lyon, A., Fazey, I., 2016. Three horizons: a pathways practice for transformation. *Ecol. Soc.* 21.

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Fazey, I. & Leicester, G. Archetypes of system transition and transformation: Six lessons for stewarding change. *Energy Research and Social Science* 91 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102646>

Fazey, I. et al. Transforming knowledge systems for life on Earth: Visions of future systems and how to get there. *Energy Research and Social Science* 70 (2020).

Buckton, S. J. et al. The Regenerative Lens: A conceptual framework for regenerative social-ecological systems. *One Earth* 6, 824-842 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.06.006>

Leicester, G. & O’Hara, M. Spaces for growth: Learning our way out of a crisis. (Triarchy Press, 2022).

Table SM.3.52. Ethnoecology

3.52. Ethnoecology	Main approach: Knowledge co-creation
Secondary approaches: Inner, Empowerment	
Ethnoecology is the discipline that studies the dynamic relationships between humans and their material and immaterial space, by examining how space is perceived by humans (local knowledge) and how humans, according to their ontologies, live their landscapes by transforming and using their natural resources (practices) inspired from (Ellen, 2006). The term "live" includes using, managing, transforming and thinking about natural entities, places and spaces on a technical, material and symbolic level, in other words, taking into account all cognitive dimensions; material and immaterial cultures are therefore jointly called upon in ethnoecology. Each human group develops its own unique way of seeing and interacting with the world. The aim of ethnoecology is to show this diversity of singularities and in particular the wealth of links, care, attachments - in short, the commitments of humans to non-humans and vice versa. These relationships are not only ethical or spiritual, but also physical. Ethnoecology is as interested in the complexity of the human world as it is in that of non-	

humans or the supranatural; the landscape scale is thus summoned (Hunn & Selam, 1990; Johnson & Davidson-Hunt, 2011).

Using a mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches, ethnoecologists are able to probe and analyze local ontologies from a holistic, emic ("from within") perspective and make them comprehensible to the bearers of other ontologies. Ethnoecology is a discipline based on field observations; ideas and inspirations come from the humans and non-humans encountered. Thus, to understand the processes, relationships, forms of organization and thought of a given social group, it is more important to observe than to investigate with (and not about) the social groups under consideration. It is a way of relating to the subject and the field work a biocultural approach. This type of approach makes it possible to encompass both the biological and cultural aspects of a system and to deal with complex relationships and feedbacks between human and ecological systems (Caillon et al., 2017; Gavin et al., 2015). Ethnoecology is a holistic science of interactions and processes between humans and non-humans.

Key references:

Caillon, S., Cullman, G., Verschuuren, B., & Sterling, E. J. (2017). Moving beyond the human-nature dichotomy through biocultural approaches : Including ecological well-being in resilience indicators. *Ecology and Society*, 22(4). <https://doi.org/10.5751/es-09746-220427>

Ellen, Roy F. « Ethnobiology and the science of humankind - Introduction » *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute* 12, no Special issue (2006).

Gavin, M. C., McCarter, J., Mead, A., Berkes, F., Stepp, J. R., Peterson, D., & Tang, R. (2015). Defining biocultural approaches to conservation. *Trends Ecol Evol*, 30(3), 140-145.

Hunn, E. S., & Selam, J. (1990). *Nch'i Wa'na "The Big River", Mid-Columbia Indians and their land* (University of Washington Press).

Johnson, M. L., & Hunt, D. I. (2011). Ethnoecology and Landscapes. In *Ethnobiology* (Wiley-Blackwell, p. 267-280)

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Ethnoecology covers a wide range of research fields: by describing practices, knowledge and uses, ethnoecologists interweave local and academic knowledge on questions of biodiversity conservation or resource sustainability; by studying more specifically the dynamics over time of these same knowledge and practices, ethnoecologists are interested in the impacts of globalization and climate change on biocultural systems and the way in which these systems integrate changes by investing in areas such as resilience or cultural adaptation ; inventorying local names and classification systems, as well as plant and animal circulation networks, adds a historical perspective to domestication and migration processes; qualitatively and quantitatively analyzing knowledge transmission mechanisms helps to better understand cultural and biological erosion phenomena. All these fields of research contribute to transformative change.

Ethnoecology also helps the pursuit of transformative change through its methods. First and foremost, ethnoecologists carry out ethical and, where possible, committed research (Posey, 1983). Darrell Posey, an entomologist turned ethnoecologist among the Kayapó in Brazil, was the driving force behind the "Belém Declaration" at the first International Society of Ethnobiology symposium in 1988, which insisted on the recognition of Indigenous Peoples' right to their local knowledge (Soldati & Albuquerque, 2016).

The biocultural approach on which ethnoecology is based offers a flexible framework that facilitates synthesis between different metrics, knowledge systems and ontologies by integrating connections - including convergences and divergences - between local and academic knowledge (Sterling et al., 2017). Ethnoecology can act as a bridge within both the academic and non-academic worlds (Sabinot, 2021). Its historical roots anchor it in both theory and rigorous fieldwork, mobilizing a rich and varied repertoire of ethical and equitable methods. Ethnoecologists have a role to play in transformative change field: after many years of experience in inter- and trans-disciplinary projects, they have proved their worth as interacting mediators between Indigenous Peoples and local communities, local institutional actors and academics.

Specific references:

Posey, D. A. (1983). Indigenous knowledge and development : An ideological bridge to the future. *Ciência e Cultura*, 35(7), 877-894.

Sabinot, C. (2021). Et si les ethnosciences facilitaient la production de passerelles au sein du monde académique comme non-académique ? *Revue d'ethnoécologie*, 20.

Soldati, G. T., & Albuquerque, U. P. (2016). Ethnobiology, Ethics and Traditional Knowledge Protection. In U. P. Albuquerque & R. R. Nóbrega Alves (Éds.), *Introduction to Ethnobiology* (p. 83-89). Springer International Publishing.

Sterling, E. J., Filardi, C., Toomey, A., Sigouin, A., Betley, E., Gazit, N., Newell, J., Albert, S., Alvira, D., Bergamini, N., Blair, M., Boseto, D., Burrows, K., Bynum, N., Caillon, S., Caselle, J. E., Claudet, J., Cullman, G., Dacks, R., ... Jupiter, S. D. (2017). Biocultural approaches to well-being and sustainability indicators across scales. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(12), 1798-1806. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0349-6>

Table SM.3.53. Transformative sustainability science

3.53. Transformative sustainability science	Main approach: Knowledge co-creation Secondary approach: Science & Technology, Systems, Empowerment, Structural
<p>Change towards sustainability needs to be transformative and bring about structural, systemic and enabling changes in the way societies are organized and governed (Scoones et al., 2020). Transformative change involves stewarding complex social, cultural, ecological, economic, institutional and technological systems towards more desirable configurations as well as to foster human agency and those capacities necessary to create change (G. Caniglia et al., 2020). Transformative processes simultaneously involve and engage with the practical, political and personal spheres (O'Brien, 2012).</p> <p>The driving and motivating question of transformative sustainability science is: how can knowledge be generated and capacities created to transform societies and generate a more just, inclusive and sustainable world? This new research field aims to generate new knowledge emerging from (and supporting) actions addressing the need for deep and enduring societal changes (Fazey et al., 2018). Such actions are adaptive and emergent processes that enhance learning and build individual and collective capacities to initiate or reinforce plural pathways towards alternative, emancipatory and more desirable futures. In generating knowledge for transformative change, importantly, different knowledge systems and ways of knowing need to be engaged, especially those of marginalized and vulnerable populations, such as Indigenous Peoples (Tengö et al., 2017). Further, different kinds of knowledge are necessary, such as strategic knowledge supporting intentional design of actions, empowering knowledge enhancing shared agency and situated knowledge enabling contextual realization (G. Caniglia et al., 2020).</p> <p>Contributing to transformative change means new, collaborative approaches that consider how to nurture transformations by “taking diverse knowledges seriously,” “taking politics seriously,” and “taking plural pathways seriously” (Scoones et al., 2020). Working with the complexities of (un)sustainability rather involves working recursively with the contrasting values and power dynamics that underlie different views about what it means to create change, for whom is change created and by whom (Turnhout et al., 2020). Social–ecological and socio–technical experiments, place-based and transdisciplinary projects, experiments in real-world laboratories and action-oriented projects in higher education are examples of research aiming to learn how to bring about such change.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Caniglia, G. et al. (2021) ‘A pluralistic and integrated approach to action-oriented knowledge for sustainability’, <i>Nature Sustainability</i>, 4(2), pp. 93–100. doi: 10.1038/s41893-020-00616-z.</p> <p>Fazey, I. et al. (2018) ‘Ten essentials for action-oriented and second order energy transitions, transformations and climate change research’, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i>. Elsevier, 40(June), pp. 54–70. doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2017.11.026.</p> <p>O'Brien, K. (2012) ‘Global environmental change II: From adaptation to deliberate transformation’, <i>Progress in Human Geography</i>, 36(5), pp. 667–676. doi: 10.1177/0309132511425767.</p>	

- Scoones, I. et al. (2020) 'Transformations to sustainability : combining structural , systemic and enabling approaches', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*. Elsevier B.V., 42, pp. 65–75. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2019.12.004.
- Tengö, M. et al. (2017) 'Weaving knowledge systems in IPBES , CBD and beyond — lessons learned for sustainability', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 26, pp. 17–25. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2016.12.005.
- Turnhout, E. et al. (2020) 'The politics of co-production: participation, power and transformation', *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*. Elsevier B.V., 42(2018), pp. 15–21. doi: 10.1016/j.cosust.2019.11.009.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transformative sustainability science in its different forms relies on knowledge co-production and transdisciplinary approaches in order to generate knowledge and change. These approaches reject the idea that knowledge is first generated through research and then translated or disseminated into society. Methodologies are here often referred to as knowledge co-production or transdisciplinarity, as they integrate perspectives and focus on processes and relationships that increase engagement and traction with policymakers, practitioners and other actors, including citizens (Chambers et al., 2022). Rather, knowledge would emerge from entangled processes of action, mutual learning and capacity building. The promise and aspiration of knowledge co-production consists in developing solutions through legitimate processes that draw on diverse and credible expertise with, by and for those best placed to use them through different research modes and priorities: 1) researching solutions; 2) empowering voices; 3) brokering power; 4) reframing power; 5) navigating differences and 6) reframing agency (Chambers et al., 2021).

In transformative approaches in sustainability science, scholars work together with multiple societal actors to contribute to creating transformative change towards sustainability in ways that are situated in context, pluralistic, goal-oriented and interactive (Norström et al., 2020). In order to contribute to transformative change, knowledge co-production also entails critical and transgressive elements, as the capacity to question and overcome oppressive social norms, such as ableism, racism, classicism, elitism, sexism (Vogel & O'Brien, 2022). Co-production processes aspire to generate change on multiple dimensions and levels. On the personal and interpersonal level, transformative knowledge co-production processes draw attention to the quality of relationships, involving being respectful of various ways of knowing and perceiving what is real (Rigolot, 2020) as well as developing capacities for navigating complex situations of conflict and disagreement towards good outcomes (G. Caniglia et al., 2023). Furthermore, knowledge co-production may create spaces and conditions for transformative change (Pereira, Frantzeskaki, et al., 2020). Such spaces represent more than opportunities for dialogues, but are rather carefully crafted spaces where people can discuss, debate and co-create complex futures. These spaces create the conditions for shifting system states in ways which may be unexpected but that reflect the values and visions of those involved.

Specific references:

- Caniglia, G. et al. (2023) 'Practical wisdom and virtue ethics for knowledge co-production in sustainability science', *Nature Sustainability*. doi: 10.1038/s41893-022-01040-1.
- Chambers, J. et al. (2022) 'Co-productive agility and four collaborative pathways to sustainability transformations', *Global Environmental Change*, (January). doi: 10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102422.
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Vogel, C. and O'Brien, K. (2021) 'Getting to the heart of transformation', Sustainability Science. Springer Japan, (0123456789). doi: 10.1007/s11625-021-01016-8.

Table SM.3.54. Participatory research

3.54. Participatory research	Main approach: Knowledge co-creation Secondary approach: Empowerment
<p>Participatory research is “an umbrella term for research designs, methods and frameworks that use systematic inquiry in direct collaboration with those affected by the issue being studied for the purpose of action or change” (Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). It is used in a wide variety of disciplines like sustainability science, health sciences, development studies and education. Consequently, there is considerable variety in the way the concept interpreted and used. Stakeholders (those that can affect or are affected by the issue being researched) are typically involved in co-producing knowledge, often with the intent to help “capture the voices and experiences of under-represented, marginalized or hard-to-reach groups in society” (Schubotz, 2020). In participatory research, power is shifted towards stakeholders, who may be involved in formulating research questions, developing study design, collecting and analyzing data, disseminating findings and/or taking action (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995; Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). Stakeholder participation can also vary in extent, from informing (where stakeholder have the least power), to consulting, involving, collaborating with, or empowering stakeholders (most power) (Arnstein, 1969; Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). It is important to note that participation is not ‘better’ if stakeholders are involved at more stages in the research process or to a greater extent. Rather, it is more important that participation is appropriate to stakeholder needs and wants and the needs of the research in question (Blackstock et al., 2007).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A ladder of citizen participation. <i>Journal of the American Institute of planners</i>, 35(4), 216-224.</p> <p>Blackstock, K. L., Kelly, G. J., & Horsey, B. L. (2007). Developing and applying a framework to evaluate participatory research for sustainability. <i>Ecological Economics</i>, 60(4), 726-742.</p> <p>Cornwall, A., & Jewkes, R. (1995). What is participatory research?. <i>Social Science & Medicine</i>, 41(12), 1667-1676.</p> <p>Schubotz, D. (2019). <i>Participatory research: Why and how to involve people in research</i>. Sage.</p> <p>Vaughn, L. M., & Jacquez, F. (2020). Participatory research methods—Choice points in the research process. <i>Journal of Participatory Research Methods</i>, 1(1).</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Participatory research aims to bring about change and therefore a transformative agenda is at its core (Ledwith & Springett, 2022). It typically involves researchers from academic institutions, (inter)governmental and/or non-governmental organizations. Other stakeholders involved vary depending on context and may include: actors from government; non-governmental policymakers; non-governmental organizations; business and industry; educators and students; media; local communities; Indigenous Peoples; and workers and trade unions.</p>	
<p>Participatory research contributes to transformative change towards sustainability by embodying sustainability values in research (‘being the change you want to see’) by including stakeholders in matters they affect or are affected by (Fiorino, 1990). It improves the quality of research by sourcing knowledge and perspectives from many different actors to ask more appropriate questions (Schubotz, 2020), offers a more complete picture of the issue being studied (Fiorino, 1990) and contributes to social learning (Collins & Ison, 2009). It can cover broad geographic areas that are too costly for traditional research, e.g., citizen science collecting data for global biodiversity monitoring (Tulloch et al., 2013), or be used to study culturally sensitive topics, e.g., studying species with cultural value to Indigenous Peoples (Krueger & King, 1998). Participatory research can increase legitimacy of research outputs amongst stakeholders and therefore the possibility that the research contributes to material changes in society (Fiorino, 1990). Participatory research can also empower stakeholders to engage in</p>	

transformative collective action, sometimes through the research process, e.g., action research) (Tandon, 1988).
Participatory research addresses biodiversity loss and nature’s decline by empowering stakeholders and providing a better understanding of the problem, the mechanisms through which it is caused and how it might best be addressed. It also increases the likelihood that action to address biodiversity loss will be informed by these improved understandings. Ongoing participatory research is necessary to respond and adapt to emergent challenges and opportunities that present during transformative change processes.
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Collins, K., & Ison, R. (2009). Jumping off Arnstein's ladder: social learning as a new policy paradigm for climate change adaptation. <i>Environmental Policy and Governance</i>, 19(6), 358-373.</p> <p>Fiorino, D. J. (1990). Citizen participation and environmental risk: A survey of institutional mechanisms. <i>Science, Technology, & Human Values</i>, 15(2), 226-243.</p> <p>Krueger, R. A., & King, J. (1998). Background And Grounding: The Emergence of Participatory Studies. In <i>Involving Community Members in Focus Groups</i> (Vol. 5, p. 1–). Sage. https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483328140.n1</p> <p>Ledwith, M., & Springett, J. (2022). <i>Participatory practice: Community-based action for transformative change</i>. Bristol University.</p> <p>Tandon, R. (1988). Social transformation and participatory research. <i>Convergence</i>, 21(2), 5.</p>

Table SM.3.55. Transformative education

3.55. Transformative education	Main approach: Inner, Knowledge co-creation
	Secondary approach: Systems, Structural
<p>Transformative education is a perspective that begins by acknowledging the most common and significant shortcomings of current education. It addresses the most enduring challenges, such as equity and equality and calls for a redefinition of the purposes and content of education for the 21st century. Transformative education seeks to ensure the right to quality education throughout life, as a public endeavour and a common good, providing learners support to learn to learn, learn to live together, learn to do and learn to be (United Nations, 2022). Within this framework, transformative education strives to articulate a vision that prepares individuals of all ages to address profound socio-environmental crises and challenges, including climate change, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and nature’s decline, poverty and inequality (O’Brien et al., 2013; United Nations, 2022).</p> <p>Transformative education promotes knowledge, skills, values and attitudes for effective problem-solving, empathy, creative thinking and critical thinking to thrive in an ever-changing world (Graham & Longchamps, 2022). To achieve this, transformative education is grounded in pedagogical principles and didactic approaches that prioritize several key elements (Graham & Longchamps, 2022): sustainable learning (focusing on the in-depth knowledge and skills in the long term), learner-centredness (Schweisfurtha, 2013), active learning, embodied cognition, integrative teaching methods (ranging from interdisciplinarity to multidisciplinary and holistic learning) and Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics education (Marín-Marín et al., 2021).</p> <p>Furthermore, transformative education contributes to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals and is an integral part of the Sustainable Development Goals targets on Education for Sustainable Development and Global Citizenship Education (United Nations, 2022). As a result, transformative education often intersects with Environmental Education, Education for Sustainable Development, Biodiversity Education (González Galli et al., 2022) and Education for a Sustainable Future (O’Brien et al., 2013). Education systems can establish the essential prerequisites for transformative education, including adequate investment and the active involvement of educators, among others (United Nations, 2022).</p>	
Key references:	

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- O'Brien, K., Reams, J., Caspari, A., Dugmore, A., Faghihimani, M., Fazey, I., ... & Winiwarter, V. (2013). You say you want a revolution? Transforming education and capacity building in response to global change. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 28, 48-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.11.011>
- Schweisfurth, M. (2013). *Learner-centred education in international perspective: Whose pedagogy for whose development?* Routledge.
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- González Galli, L., Bernal Castro, I. C., Porras Contreras, Y. A., Pérez Mesa, M. R., Prieto Piraquive, É. F., Gómez Galindo, A. A., ... & Roa Acosta, R. (2022). *Educación en Biodiversidad. Perspectivas y retos*. Cátedra 10.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Transformative change would be based on these principles:

Educate sustainably: by prioritizing concepts and theories over raw facts and data and by engaging in meaningful and authentic activities that enhance long-term memory.

Learner-centred practice: it entails a departure from subject- or teacher-centred methods, emphasizing the central role of students in education. It involves offering hands-on experiences where learners wield a substantial degree of active control over both the content and the learning process (Schweisfurth, 2013).

Active learning: involves the active and constructive engagement of learners in mindful and culturally relevant tasks. This approach fosters social and cognitive involvement, facilitating a progressive integration between the individuals' operations and the elements coming from the experience with the environment (Vosniadou, 2001).

Embodied cognition can be seen as an approach that encourages physical and tangible (including virtual) interactions within the physical and social learning environment. It is closely associated with hands-on activities (Abrahamson & Lindgren, 2014).

Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches: promote an open, non-linear, situated and heterogeneous perspective on knowledge and social-ecological systems (O'Brien et al., 2013).

STEAM: an educational project-based approach that stands for science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), which has more recently been accompanied by the 'A' (Arts) in order to improve creativity and integrate cognitive and affective domains of learning.

Expected Transformative Learning could be characterized as a co-creative process through which prior beliefs, assumptions and taken-for-granted perspectives on oneself, relationships and society are critically examined to evolve into more open, creative, adaptable and well-validated viewpoints, values and social practices (Cranton & Carusetta, 2004). Dialogue serves as a means and the primary material for co-constructing and achieving a shared understanding. Transformative learning is not a straightforward shift in opinion to adopt an authoritative 'correct' viewpoint. TL manifests itself when there is a profound transformation in perspectives, along with noticeable changes in actions.

Specific references:

- Abrahamson, D., & Lindgren, R. (2014). Embodiment and embodied design. In R. K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences* (pp. 358-376). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139519526.022>
- Cranton, P., & Carusetta, E. (2004). Developing authenticity as a transformative process. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 2(4), 276-293. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1541344604267898>

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Table SM.3.56. Local Biodiversity Outlook transitions

3.56. Local Biodiversity Outlook (LBO) transitions	Main approach: Knowledge co-creation Secondary approach: Systems, Empowerment
<p>Indigenous Peoples and local communities are significant actors for transformative change. Their contributions to conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity have increasingly become more visible during the past 10 years, including through the publication of Local Biodiversity Outlooks (2020) and the IPBES Global Assessment (2019a) and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework – See Recognition of rights in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets 1, 3, 5, 9, 13, 21, 22, 23 as well as Section C as cross-cutting considerations for the whole Framework covering Rights and contributions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, Whole-of-government and whole-of-society approach, Human rights-based approach, Diverse knowledge systems and Gender and Intergenerational equity; and Recognition and support for Community-based monitoring and information systems and tools e.g., Indigenous Navigator and citizen science.</p> <p>Local Biodiversity Outlooks highlights stories of resilience by Indigenous Peoples and local communities addressing underlying drivers of rapid declines in biological and cultural diversity. Each account speaks to inter-generational visions and commitments to building better futures through solidarity and collective actions towards renewal of nature and cultures.</p> <p>This emerging narrative of transformation is grounded in collective reflections on historical colonization and deepening understandings of contemporary confrontations with State and corporate powers pursuing extractivism and profit accumulation which underpin the current social-ecological crises.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Forest Peoples Programme, International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity, Indigenous Women’s Biodiversity Network, Centres of Distinction on Indigenous and Local Knowledge and Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2020) <i>Local Biodiversity Outlooks 2: The contributions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities to the implementation of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and to renewing nature and cultures. A complement to the fifth edition of Global Biodiversity Outlook.</i> Moreton-in-Marsh, England: Forest Peoples Programme. Available at: www.localbiodiversityoutlooks.net</p> <p>IPBES (2019) Summary for policymakers of the global assessment on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Díaz, J. Settele, E. S. Brondízio E.S., H. T. Ngo, M. Guèze, J. Agard, A. Arneth, P. Balvanera, K. A. Brauman, S. H. M. Butchart, K. M. A. Chan, L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii, J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, G. F. Midgley, P. Miloslavich, Z. Molnár, D. Obura, A. Pfaff, S. Polasky, A. Purvis, J. Razzaque, B. Reyers, R. Roy Chowdhury, Y. J. Shin, I. J. Visseren-Hamakers, K. J. Willis and C. N. Zayas (eds.). Bonn, Germany: IPBES. Available at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Emerging from their collective experiences from all over the world, Indigenous Peoples and local communities put forward six urgently needed transitions underpinning transformative change (These transitions are summarized through a problem tree illustrating the underlying drivers of the social-ecological</p>	

crises and a solution tree illustrating contributions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities towards the renewal of nature and cultures (Forest Peoples Programme et al., 2020):

1. Cultural transitions towards diverse ways of knowing and being within a living, intelligent and sacred world;
2. Land transitions towards securing customary land tenure contributing to human well-being and biodiversity and climate change solutions;
3. Governance transitions towards inclusive decision-making and self-determined development ensuring respect for human rights and diverse values of biodiversity;
4. Incentives and financial transitions towards rewarding effective culture-based solutions and ending harmful investments and perverse incentives.
5. Economic transitions towards diverse local economies respecting customary sustainable use and contributions of other small-scale producers;
6. Food transitions towards revitalizing Indigenous and local food systems ensuring genetic diversity and diverse diets, improving health, resilience and livelihoods.

Collectively, these transitions embody inter-generational visions of walking to the future in the footsteps of ancestors (The Kari-Oca Declaration and Indigenous Peoples Earth Charter was the united statement of Indigenous Peoples on the occasion of the United Nations Summit on Environment and Development. It has since been reaffirmed by subsequent meetings of Indigenous Peoples in Bali, Indonesia and in Kimberley, South Africa as follow-up gatherings to the 1992 meeting at Kari-Oca, Brazil. Its opening words – We, the Indigenous Peoples walk to the future in the footsteps of our ancestors embodies the spirit of the inter-general transitions articulated in LBO-2.). These local solutions upend dominant political, cultural and values systems positing mastery over nature through technocratic solutions and opaque financial instruments which ignore and undervalue time-tested ways of living, knowing and being in nature which are vital cultural underpinning foundations towards transformative change.

New narratives and visions of culture and nature working together can propel individual and collective actions towards a renewed planetary balance among humans and other living beings in our common home.

Specific references:

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- International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity (2020) IIFB opening statement to the Open Ended Working Group on the Post 2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, 24 February 2020, Rome, Italy.

Table SM.3.57. Transdisciplinary research

<p>3.57. Transdisciplinary research</p>	<p>Main approach: Knowledge co-creation Secondary approach: Empowerment, Structural</p>
<p>Transdisciplinary research is knowledge (co)creation that brings together disciplines; extends beyond academic disciplines into other forms of knowledge (e.g., practice, religious, Indigenous, traditional); and challenges the worldviews on which such disciplines are based. It is fundamentally normative, asking questions about what should be, rather than what is and co-creating solutions to achieve these values (Max-Neef, 2005). Transdisciplinary research implies researchers to reflect and deconstruct their own assumptions and ideas (Augsburg, 2014). Conducting transdisciplinary research often includes a period of time at the beginning of enquiries to build capacities, shared understandings and trust amongst participants (Horcea-Milcu et al., 2023). Following this phase 0, transdisciplinary research often entails stages of problem framing, analysis and integration for impact to research and practice (Lang et al., 2012). These phases are not linear and are iterative, requiring continued reflection and readjustment to emerging knowledge and understanding. Transdisciplinary research contributes to understandings of transformative change in 4 main ways. Firstly, transdisciplinary research could transform the worldviews, mindsets and understandings of those who are participating in the process (Augsburg, 2014). Secondly, transdisciplinary research is often enacted as a part of creating transformative change with communities. Thirdly, transdisciplinary research is increasingly the approach taken by researchers within sustainability science as part of exploring processes of transformative change. And fourthly, true transdisciplinary research implies broader transformations of knowledge systems (e.g., funding mechanisms, framings of legitimate knowledge, etc.) to be effectively undertaken (Fazey et al., 2021). It thus challenges the dominant hegemony of quantitative, western knowledges for ‘evidence’-informed policy and action.</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Augsburg, T. (2014). Becoming Transdisciplinary: The Emergence of the Transdisciplinary Individual. <i>World Futures</i>, 70(3–4), 233–247. https://doi.org/10.1080/02604027.2014.934639</p> <p>Fazey, I., Hughes, C., Schöpke, N. A., Leicester, G., Eyre, L., Goldstein, B. E., Hodgson, A., Mason-Jones, A. J., Moser, S. C., Sharpe, B., & Reed, M. S. (2021). Renewing Universities in Our Climate Emergency: Stewarding System Change and Transformation. <i>Frontiers in Sustainability</i>, 2. https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2021.677904</p> <p>Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Leventon, J., & Lang, D. J. (2022). Making transdisciplinarity happen: Phase 0, or before the beginning. <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i>, 136, 187–197. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.019</p> <p>Lang, D. J., Wiek, A., Bergmann, M., Stauffacher, M., Martens, P., Moll, P., Swilling, M., & Thomas, C. J. (2012). Transdisciplinary research in sustainability science: Practice, principles and challenges. <i>Sustainability Science</i>, 7(S1), 25–43. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0149-x</p> <p>Max-Neef, M. A. (2005). Foundations of transdisciplinarity. <i>Ecological Economics</i>, 53(1), 5–16. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.01.014</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>Arguably, how change happens depends on what is being researched, where and with whom. Common to many approaches is the shared, co-production of solutions, between research and non-researchers. In all explanations, there is emphasis on the process of transdisciplinarity as being the important factor in transformative change and not just the outcome itself (Mitchell et al., 2015). Schneider et al., emphasize the role of transdisciplinary research in promoting knowledge for more informed and equitable decision-making; fostering social learning for collective action; and enhancing competencies for reflexive leadership (Pereira et al., 2021). Such processes are often (but not always) in place-based cases to solve specific problems (Pereira et al., 2021). Such formats reshape the relationship between science and society away from being linear (e.g., mode 1 science) and towards a dynamic dialogue (mode 2 science). There is also often an emphasis on individuals who navigate the process of co-construction and reflection according to their own particular approach (Chambers et al., 2022), to provide leadership and care (G. Caniglia et al., 2023). These individuals often act as systems entrepreneurs who help guide the construction of ideas and enaction of practices to create tangible change. It involves significant buy-in and support from everyone engaged in the process. Often, the process involves shifts in power and surfacing tensions. For example, Chambers et al., highlight 4 pathways that transdisciplinary research can open opportunities for</p>	

transformation: 1) elevating marginalized agendas; 2) questioning dominant agendas; 3) navigating conflicting agendas; and 4) exploring diverse agendas (Chambers et al., 2022). While co-creating transformations with communities, transdisciplinary research and transdisciplinary researchers, are often pushing for broader structural changes. Such changes can include within their own universities or knowledge communities, as transdisciplinary researchers fight against funding systems and merit systems that reward more traditional science approaches more.

Specific references:

Caniglia, G., Freeth, R., Luederitz, C., Leventon, J., West, S. P., John, B., Peukert, D., Lang, D. J., Von Wehrden, H., Martín-López, B., Fazey, I., Russo, F., Von Wirth, T., Schlüter, M., & Vogel, C. (2023). Practical wisdom and virtue ethics for knowledge co-production in sustainability science. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(5), 493–501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01040-1>

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Schneider, F., Tribaldos, T., Adler, C., Biggs, R. (Oonsie), De Bremond, A., Buser, T., Krug, C., Loutre, M.-F., Moore, S., Norström, A. V., Paulavets, K., Urbach, D., Spehn, E., Wülser, G., & Zondervan, R. (2021). Co-production of knowledge and sustainability transformations: A strategic compass for global research networks. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 49, 127–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.04.007>

Table SM.3.58. Transformative innovation policy

3.58. Transformative innovation policy	Main Approach: Knowledge co-creation, Structural
Secondary approach: Systems, Science-Technology	
<p>In recent decades, policymakers and researchers have focused on science, technology and innovation as key drivers for economic growth, innovation and job creation. Transformative innovation policy, also known as the third frame for innovation policy, emerged in the early twenty-first century, responding to the pressing environmental and social challenges, aiming at long-term transformation (Schot et al., 2018).</p> <p>Transformative innovation policy builds on previous innovation policy frames (research and innovation and systems innovation), acknowledging their role in building knowledge, upgrading technology and enhancing productive capacity, but recognizing their limitations on giving a clear directionality (towards just sustainable development) and recognizing upfront and ex-ante unintended consequences of innovation (Schot & Steinmueller, 2018).</p> <p>To craft a policy that effectively addresses social and environmental needs and brings about transformation on both national and regional scales, the science, technology and innovation policy could shift focus and adopt new characteristics. Drawing from the sustainability transitions literature (Gren & Andersson, 2018), transformative innovation policy prioritizes the transformation of socio-technical systems, incorporating concepts like experimental delivery, directional focus and inclusivity. Every economy relies on numerous socio-technical systems that serve critical societal functions such as the provision of energy, food, healthcare, mobility and communication. Transformative innovation policy seeks to redirect these systems towards greater sustainability.</p> <p>Furthermore, transformative innovation policy began to broaden its understanding of innovation including civil society and citizens as not only consumers and adopters of innovation but as promoters and sources for</p>	

innovations that address social and environmental needs. It advocates for bottom-up open innovation spaces where radical alternatives to the dominant unsustainable and unfair practices evolve, involving more actors in this space and engaging them in a participatory way. This would lead to carving out directionality portfolios and sustainable pathways for moving forward (Weber & Rohracher, 2012). This is not an easy and consensus-driven process but a political one (Stirling, 2015).

Key references:

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Schot, J., & Steinmueller, W. E. (2018). Three frames for innovation policy: R&D, systems of innovation and transformative change. *Research policy*, 47(9), 1554-1567.

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Weber, K. M., & Rohracher, H. (2012). Legitimizing research, technology and innovation policies for transformative change: Combining insights from innovation systems and multi-level perspective in a comprehensive 'failures' framework. *Research policy*, 41(6), 1037-1047.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

Socio-technical transitions drive intentional change across various systems to achieve desired environmental and social outcomes, necessitating a nuanced understanding of complexity. This involves adopting transdisciplinary approaches, integrating knowledge and methodologies from diverse academic and non-academic sources to tackle intricate issues through experimentation. Ghosh et al. (2021) advocate for experimental engagements to propel transformative change, initially focused on policy but expandable to business, investment, societal groups and academia. These engagements encompass a range of activities, including initiating, supporting, or mobilizing experiments, evaluating their impact and facilitating social learning to develop alternative pathways towards desirable futures. Such endeavours are time-limited and characterized by reflexivity and learning, involving a coalition of actors collaborating to address common challenges (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021).

Socio-technical systems are constructed and maintained by actors who are guided by a set of dominant formal and informal rules, which together form a regime. These systems change when shifts occur at different levels, as theorized by the multi-level perspective (Geels, 2002; Geels & Schot, 2007; Rip & Kemp, 1998). Specifically, it occurs when dynamic and complex interactions emerge between actors advancing new solutions and ideas in niches, deviating and destabilizing dominant practices. Niches are protective spaces where different ideas, models, configurations and ways of doing are tested and developed. Although regimes seek to remain stable, they get also pressured by long-term exogenous trends and shocks, or landscape, breaking the dominant configuration of the system and giving space to the niches to replace the dominant regime. Significantly, the multi-level perspective provides analytic lenses to determine systems transitions when three conditions are met: 1) a regime is destabilized, 2) niches provide strong alternatives at scale and 3) landscape trends and shocks are perceived by the regime and niche actors as a window of opportunity for a transition.

Specific references:

Geels, F. W. (2022). 'Causality and explanation in socio-technical transitions research: Mobilizing epistemological insights from the wider social sciences', *Research Policy*, 51 (6).

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6. Science & Technology

Table SM.3.59. Epistemic communities	102
Table SM.3.60. Inclusive innovation	103
Table SM.3.61. Sociotechnical infrastructures	105
Table SM.3.62. Technological and scientific constructivism	106

Table SM.3.59. Epistemic communities

3.59. Epistemic communities	Main approach: Science and Technology
	Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Systems, Structural
<p>Epistemic communities theory comes from international relations and focuses on the influence of scientists and experts on public policy and international cooperation (P. Haas, 1992, 2015). While it has predominantly studied environmental issues, it extends to public health, particularly COVID-19, education and international political economy.</p> <p>Epistemic communities are defined as groups of individuals who share common causal understandings, normative commitments, common truth tests and are engaged in a collective policy project.</p> <p>Under conditions of uncertainty and complexity decision makers are likely to defer to those with a reputation for authoritative expertise in the wake of a publicly recognized threat, often triggered by a crisis or disaster. Epistemic communities, due to their substantive knowledge, are likely to provide better public policy advice which is capable of accurately recognizing the policy characteristics of an issue and able to provide policy advice which is likely to work, unlike traditional political responses to crises, which tend to rely on business-as-usual approaches, or to apply public policies which are politically attractive.</p> <p>Concretely, epistemic communities are associated with international regimes and treaties which are effective (P. Haas, 2017). They are most likely to be influential when they satisfy a set of conditions: they enjoy a reputation for impartial expertise, they confer “usable” knowledge which is politically salient, timely and useful at geographic and temporal scale; they are organized into standing science policy interface panels, they are able to set their own agendas, they are recruited on merit and they enjoy distance from governments (P. Haas, 2017). The IPCC, although it has produced authoritative science about climate change which keeps the issue on the international agenda, has not clearly impacted national decision-making, in part because the governments control the summary for policymakers and governments appoint the IPCC experts (P. Haas, 2004).</p>	
Key references:	
<p>Haas, P. (2004). "When Does Power Listen to Truth? A Constructivist Approach to the Policy Process." <i>Journal of European Public Policy</i> 11(4): 569-592.</p> <p>Haas, P. M., Ed. (1992). <i>Knowledge, power and international policy coordination</i>. Columbia, University of South Carolina Press.</p> <p>Haas, P. M. (2015). <i>Epistemic Communities, Constructivism and International Environmental Politics</i>. London, Routledge.</p> <p>Haas, P. M. (2017). <i>Coupling science to governance: Straddling the science-policy interface. The Politics of Expertise in International Organizations</i>. A. Littoz-Monnet. London, Routledge.</p>	

Haas, P. M. (2017). Epistemic Communities. The Oxford Handbook of International Environmental Law. L. Rajamani and J. Peel. Oxford, Oxford University Press: 698-715.
How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework
<p>Conservation regimes with epistemic community²⁹ involvement stress ecological knowledge about ecosystems by protecting habitats rather than setting quotas or outright moratoria. Salient examples of this include UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere Programme, the Polar Bears treaty (O. Young & Osherenko, 1993) and the Ramsar Convention. Moreover, they provide for the involvement of local people in the governance of the conservation regimes in which they reside.</p> <p>Epistemic communities may contribute to transformative governance (P. M. Haas, 2021). As biodiversity epistemic communities reflect the ecological perspective, their policy advice focuses on the governance of complex and coupled social and natural systems (W. C. Clark & Munn, 1986; Holdgate, 1999). In the conservation realm they contribute to the involvement of local actors in governance and value Indigenous knowledge. They are associated with more effective outcomes based on ecological realities.(P. Haas, 2017). They also contribute to more comprehensive frames, where environmental conservation is linked to economic development and vice versa. For instance, environmental conservation becomes a guard rail for economic development and economic instruments and concepts – such as the value of ecosystem services and the value of habitats are applied to the governance of biodiversity. More generally they have contributed to an increasingly intertwined global political agenda including sustainability, trade and environment, environment and finance, environment and human rights, environment and security and environment and development.</p>
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Clark, W. C. and R. E. Munn, Eds. (1986). Sustainable Development of the Biosphere. New York, Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>Fikkan, A., G. Osherenko and A. I. Arikaynen (1993). Polar bears: the importance of simplicity. Polar politics: creating international environmental regimes. O. R. Young and G. Osherenko. Ithaca, NY, Cornell University Press: 96-151.</p> <p>Haas, P. M. (2017). Coupling science to governance: Straddling the science-policy interface. The Politics of Expertise in International Organizations. A. Littoz-Monnet. London, Routledge.</p> <p>Haas, P. M. (2017). Epistemic Communities. The Oxford Handbook of International Environmental Law. L. Rajamani and J. Peel. Oxford, Oxford University Press: 698-715.</p> <p>Haas, P. M. (2021). Cognitive Evolution and the Social Construction of Complexity. Theorizing World Orders. P. Ish-Shalom, M. Kornprobst and V. Pouliot. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press: 134-168.</p> <p>Holdgate, M. (1999). The Green Web. London, Earthscan.</p>

Table SM.3.60. Inclusive innovation

3.60. Inclusive innovation	<p>Main approach: Science and Technology Solutions, Knowledge co-creation</p> <p>Secondary approach: Empowerment</p>
<p>The last two decades have been characterized by recurrent economic and social crises. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected already fragile systems of employment around the world. In many countries worldwide, opportunities for decent work have declined, fair income and security in the workplace have been undermined, social protection for families and better prospects for personal development and social integration have been reduced. Meanwhile the COVID-19 crisis has also accelerated top-down technological innovations. These include apps and online platforms which enable new forms of communication, interactive learning and employment. But they also feature automated machine</p>	

²⁹ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

technologies, such as robots and artificial intelligence, which potentially worsen the precarious position of 1.8 billion low-skilled workers worldwide by putting their jobs at risk (Solórzano et al., 2013; World Bank, 2019). Some of these excluded workers and/or their low-income communities try to collectively respond to crises by innovating in inclusive ways and thereby initiating transformative change.

Innovation is inclusive when the interests and the aspirations of low-income and marginalized communities are taken on board in processes of knowledge generation and exploitation for addressing basic needs. This theoretical agenda occupies the intellectual space between innovation, development and poverty alleviation studies (Pansera & Owen, 2018). It recognizes that social exclusion and inequality have often resulted from disruptive technological innovations and production processes. These are generally top-down, expensive capital-intensive innovations which tend to exclude the interests and aspirations of lower-income and marginalized people. Crises such as Covid-19 exacerbate socioeconomic exclusion and marginalization for ‘bottom of the pyramid’ communities. In order to provide more socially equitable, solidaristic alternatives, the concept of ‘inclusive innovation’ emphasizes accessible novelty, namely: grassroots innovations and production processes which accommodate the needs of lower-income people, enhancing their capabilities and skills, improving their welfare and potentially empowering them (Arocena & Sutz, 2003; Chataway et al., 2014; Cozzens, 2007; Kaplinsky et al., 2009; Levidow & Papaioannou, 2018; Papaioannou, 2018; Prahalad, 2004).

Key references:

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Chataway, J., Hanlin, R. and Kaplinsky, R. (2014) Inclusive innovation: an architecture for policy development, *Innovation and Development* 4(1): 33–54.

Cozzens, S. 2007. Distributive justice in science and technology policy, *Science and Public Policy* 34: 85–94.

Gómez Solórzano, M. 2013. “Trabajo precario global”. In: Gómez Solórzano y Pacheco Reyes (comp.) *Trabajo informal, economía solidaria y autogestión. Precariedad laboral y resistencia en la globalización*. Buenos Aires: Ediciones Peña Lillo/Continent.

Kaplinsky, R., J. Chataway, N. Clark, R. Hanlin, D. Kale, L. Muraguri, T. Papaioannou, P. Robbins and W. Wamae. 2009. “Below the Radar: What does Innovation in Emerging Economies have to Offer other Low-income Economies?” *International Journal of Technology Management & Sustainable Development* 8 (3): 177-197.

Levidow, L. and Papaioannou, T. (2017) ‘Which Inclusive Innovation? Competing Normative Assumptions Around Social Justice’ *Innovation and Development*, Vol. 8, No.2, pp.209-226.

Pansera, M. and Owen, R. (2018) ‘Framing Inclusive Innovation within the Discourse of Development: Insights from Case Studies in India’ *Research Policy*, Vol.47, pp.23-24.

Papaioannou, T. (2018) *Inclusive Innovation for Development: Meeting the Demands of Justice through Public Action*, London: Routledge.

Prahalad, C. K. 2005. *The Fortune of the Bottom of the Pyramid: Eradicating Poverty through Profits*. Upper Saddle River, New York: Pearson Education/Wharton School Publishing.

Radjou, N. and Prabhu, J. (2015) *Frugal Innovation: How to do better with less*. London: The Economist/Hachette India.

World Bank (2019) *The Changing Nature of Work*, Washington DC: World Bank.

How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework

As a form of inclusive innovation, grassroots innovation stimulates innovation processes that are socially inclusive towards local communities which are unable to participate in formally regulated markets. This empowers and transforms such communities, enabling them to take control of decisions about how to address their basic needs. Grassroots innovation processes respond to social injustices, socioeconomic inequalities and environmental problems often arising from conventional capital-intensive innovation models (Smith et al., 2014). They develop social technologies i.e., readily reproducible techniques and methodologies which are co-created with communities to resolve their social inclusion problems (Chataway et al., 2010); these enhance both the innovative and human

capabilities of lower income and marginalized people, improving their welfare and potentially transforming them (Heeks et al., 2013; Levidow & Papaioannou, 2018; Papaioannou, 2018).

In those ways, ‘inclusive innovation’ encompasses various implicit models for explaining current social inclusion around technoscientific innovation, for identifying socioeconomic inequities and for avoiding or remedying these outcomes. Each model involves normative assumptions about what transformative change ought to be, linked with diagnostic or prescriptive concepts. Inequity has been used as a prominent rationale for redesigning innovation to create greater value (for customers, shareholders and society) from fewer resources (natural resources, capital, time). The process becomes more equitable and transformative, providing viable alternatives and potentially disrupting conventional methods of production (Radjou et al., 2015).

Specific references:

Chataway, J., Hanlin, R., Mugwagwa, J. and Muraguri, L. (2010) ‘Global Health Social Technologies: Reflections on Evolving Theories and Landscapes’ *Research Policy*, Vol.39, No.10, pp.1277-1288.

Heeks, R., Amalia, M., Kintu, R., Shah, N. (2013) *Inclusive Innovation: Definition, Conceptualisation and Future Research Priorities*, Univ. of Manchester: Development Informatics Working Paper Series, <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/inclusive-innovation-definition-conceptualisation-and-future-rese>

Levidow, L. and Papaioannou, T. (2017) ‘Which Inclusive Innovation? Competing Normative Assumptions Around Social Justice’ *Innovation and Development*, Vol. 8, No.2, pp.209-226.

Papaioannou, T. (2018) *Inclusive Innovation for Development: Meeting the Demands of Justice through Public Action*, London: Routledge.

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Smith, A., Fressoli, M. and Thomas, H. 2014. Grassroots innovation movements: challenges and contributions, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 63: 114-124.

Table SM.3.61. Sociotechnical infrastructures

3.61. Sociotechnical infrastructures	Main approach: Science and technology, Systems Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation
<p>Sociotechnical infrastructures³⁰ are the emergent systems that organize people and technologies such as databases, information systems, maps, metrics, instruments and more to enable a wide range of actors to know and act in specific ways regarding all kind of contemporary matters including biodiversity loss and nature’s decline (Blok et al., 2016). This theory comes from the pioneering work of Susan Leigh Star (1999), who extensively studied the interrelated influence of technological systems and people (thereby the adjective “sociotechnical”) in helping to stabilize particular orderings that can be open to transformation and change. In this way, the approach takes infrastructures as much more than roads, railroads, bridges and so on. Or as Larkin (2013) has argued, sociotechnical infrastructures are the objects that create the grounds on which other objects operate, so they are things and also the relation between things. Sociotechnical infrastructures theories then, highlight the forms of politics and intervention shaped by these systems (Harvey et al., 2016), since they create in/exclusions that affect the ability of certain kinds of knowledge to count and certain kinds of actors to act in how transformative change occurs. This theory then contributes to understand transformative change by integrating the technical and social aspects involved in the ongoing material transformation of the world and its elements. As contemporary scholarship on sociotechnical infrastructures has pointed out, this concept has important implications to capture the ontological dimension of transformative change, since it helps to trace how multiple agents, including humans and non-humans meet, engage, transform and produce realities (Jensen & Morita, 2015).</p>	

³⁰ See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382223>)

Key references:	
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How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework	
<p>Within theories of sociotechnical infrastructures, transformative change can intentionally occur from diverse sites and circumstances where these systems shape both the way that critical challenges such as biodiversity can be intervened and the scope for transformative change that these systems can enable. Goldstein and Nost (2022) show that sociotechnical infrastructures organize the data that mediates socioenvironmental relationships. The effect of this, is that sociotechnical infrastructures create the practical arrangements that enable data to drive environmental governance and shape its transformative change processes. In that way, as (Beaulieu, 2022) argues, sociotechnical infrastructures contribute to assemble and maintain ways of knowing that solidify how problems related to sustainability and biodiversity loss are formulated, orient to possible solutions and legitimize and support specific actors while excluding others in processes of transformative change. As other scholars have showed, transformative change within sociotechnical infrastructures occurs through the conjunction of human and non-human actors that can transform regional economies, people’s lives, make new forms of sociality, remake landscapes, define novel forms of politics and reconfigure subjects and objects all at once (Morita, 2016). This theory then, can allow new ways of navigating transformative change process since it pays attention not to actors per se (human or non-human), but to the sociotechnical infrastructures that their relations sustain to drive actions that can transform how we engage in practice with the causes of biodiversity loss and nature’s decline. Recently, scholarship has stressed the role of sociotechnical infrastructures in composing the grounds for new affective and practical engagements between people and technologies to allow the emergence of alternative modes of repair that can be crucial for generating transformative change processes (Jiménez, 2014; Mora Gámez et al., 2023). In summary, sociotechnical infrastructures are also material resources that can be intentionally designed and created to harness transformative change.</p>	
Specific references:	
<p>Beaulieu, A. (2022). Data Practices and Sustainable Development Goals: Organising Knowledge for Sustainable Futures. In M. H. Bruun, A. Wahlberg, R. Douglas-Jones, C. Hasse, K. Hoeyer, D. B. Kristensen, & B. R. Winthereik (Eds.), <i>The Palgrave Handbook of the Anthropology of Technology</i>. Springer Nature Singapore.</p> <p>Goldstein, J. E., & Nost, E. (2022). <i>The Nature of Data: Infrastructures, Environments, Politics</i>. University of Nebraska Press.</p> <p>Corsin Jiménez, A. (2014). The Right to Infrastructure: A Prototype for Open Source Urbanism. <i>Environment and Planning D: Society and Space</i>, 32(2), 342–362.</p> <p>Mora-Gámez, F., Sánchez Aldana, E., & Papadapoulos, D. (2023). Affecting Infrastructures: Crafting and Weaving as Alternative Repairs. <i>Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, Technoscience</i>, 9(2).</p> <p>Morita, A. (2016). Infrastructuring Amphibious Space: The Interplay of Aquatic and Terrestrial Infrastructures in the Chao Phraya Delta in Thailand. <i>Science as Culture</i>, 25(1), 117–140.</p>	

Table SM.3.62. Technological and scientific constructivism

3.62. Technological and scientific constructivism	Main approach: Science and technology
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	Secondary approach: Knowledge co-creation, Systems, Empowerment
<p>The social construction, or shaping, of scientific facts and technology has been a main concern in science and technology studies. Constructivism deals with the constructedness of objects and entities. For example, studies have examined the processes in which large technological systems become established, showing that many human factors play a large role in the promotion, shaping and adapting to systems such as electricity grids, road networks and the internet (Hughes, 1998). Social construction of technology approaches studied how technological artifacts such as bikes are as much results of social processes and preferences as determined by fixed technological constraints and developments, while social construction of scientific knowledge examined the social aspects of science (Bijker et al., 1987; Latour, 1987). These theories point out that scientific and technological developments, which are often naturalized in retrospect, in fact could have developed differently depending on the social context and the human factors involved. An important contribution has been to oppose prevailing technological determinism, i.e. that technology alone drives societal developments. The denaturalization of scientific and technological developments has further opened the way for studies of the politics of science and technology, since different possible developments will benefit or burden actors in different ways (Latour, 2004).</p>	
<p>Key references:</p> <p>Bijker, Wiebe E., Thomas P. Hughes and Trevor J. Pinch, eds. <i>The Social Construction of Technological Systems: New Directions in the Sociology and History of Technology</i>. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1987.</p> <p>Hughes, T. 2000. <i>Rescuing Prometheus: Four Monumental Projects That Changed the Modern World</i>. SD Books.</p> <p>Latour, B. 1987. <i>Science in action: how to follow engineers and scientists through society</i>. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.</p> <p>Latour, B. 2004. <i>Politics of nature: how to bring the sciences into democracy</i>. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.</p> <p>Marx, L. and Smith M. R. (eds). 1994. <i>Does Technology Drive History? The Dilemma of Technological Determinism</i>. MIT Press.</p>	
<p>How transformative change occurs according to the theory/framework</p>	
<p>The focus in these approaches is on the role of science and technology in societal transformations. However, scientific and technological developments are not understood as external processes that drives change in society, but as social processes co-driven by society (Hughes, 1998; Latour, 2004). Therefore, a variety of actors are involved in such developments: those that develop, promote, use it and are affected in other ways. Since scientific and technological developments have differential impacts, with some losing out, a central tenet is that these processes could be politicized and democratized – that the built-in assumptions, contingencies and political implications are openly debated and that decisions with political implications are not taken exclusively by engineers or experts (Stirling, 2010; Turnhout, 2018). Recent studies have argued that current governance aiming to combat biodiversity loss and nature’s decline and promote just transformative change would benefit from processes that politicize and democratize how scientific knowledge is employed in decision-making (Stokland et al., 2023).</p>	
<p>Specific references:</p> <p>Hughes, T. 2000. <i>Rescuing Prometheus: Four Monumental Projects That Changed the Modern World</i>. SD Books.</p> <p>Latour, B. 2004. <i>Politics of nature: how to bring the sciences into democracy</i>. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.</p> <p>Stirling, A. Keep it complex. <i>Nature</i> 468, 1029–1031 (2010). https://doi.org/10.1038/4681029a</p> <p>Stokland, H. B., Aspøy, H., Krangle, O. and Skogen, K. (2023) Warranty for a better world? The politics of environmental knowledge in bioeconomic sustainability certificates. <i>Ambio</i> 52: 1056–1064.</p> <p>Turnhout, E. (2018). The politics of environmental knowledge. <i>Conservation and Society</i>, 16(3), 363–371.</p>	

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